

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D7.7 Analysis: Communication and information update M34

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Executive Summary

The EU-funded COVINFORM project employs intersectionality theory and complex systems analysis to examine COVID-19 responses at government (WP4), public health (WP5), community (WP6), and information and communication levels (WP7). The project includes empirical research and community-based case studies to assess responses to COVID-19. COVINFORM draws on cross-disciplinary approaches (social epidemiology, the sociology of migration, philosophy, etc.) to investigate different aspects of vulnerability in the context of the pandemic. Based on the project findings, the consortium will develop an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society integrating data streams, indices and indicators, maps, risk assessment models, primary research and case study findings, and empirically grounded policy guidance.

This report relates to Work Package (WP) 7 of the project which focuses on evaluating inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation.

This report is an update of deliverable 7.3. ‘Analysis: Communication and information’ submitted in M14 (December 2021). It is based on ten country reports from each of the COVINFORM countries. As part of a series of analysis across WP 4 to 7, it seeks to answer questions concerning planning of the response and the crisis communication, implementation of crisis communication in the field of public health, with a special focus on measures to fighting mal-/dis-/misinformation, targeted communication campaigns to influence behaviour, the public reactions to crisis communication, and the specific barriers that occurred in the different stages. Special attention is paid to how vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed in the communication strategies and actions by governments and how they changed over time. Building on D7.3 this report addresses the same five dimensions: 1.) Good and bad practices in COVID-19 communication strategies, 2.) Communication to influence behaviour change, 3.) Digital communication and exclusion, 4.) Fighting mal-information, disinformation and misinformation, 5.) Representation and justice in media.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
ACT	Autoridade para as Condições de Trabalho Working Conditions Authority
AEMPS	Spanish Medicines Agency
AGES	Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit Agency for Health and Food Safety
AGIA	Agency for Childhood and Adolescence
AS	Actor Systems
BAME	Black, Asian, minority thnic
BBK	Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response
BIT	Behavioural Insights Team
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
BMI	Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community
BZgA	the Federal Centre for Health Communication
CCA	Civil Contingencies Act
CCAES	National Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center
CCS	Civil Contingencies Secretariat
CCVO	Coordination and Crisis Center of the Flemish government
CD	Communications Director
Cepsag	Center for Promotion and Development of Geriatric Care
CIS	Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas
CTS	Technical Scientific Committee
DCMS	Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport
DGS	Directorate-General of Health
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EODY	National Public Health Organization
ERTE	temporary employment regulation files
FIMMG	Italian Federation of Family Physicians
FNOMCeO	Federazione Nazionale degli Ordini dei Medici Chirurghi e degli Odontoiatri Italian Federation of the Orders of Surgeons and Dentists
FNOPi	Federazione Nazionale Ordine Professioni Infermieristiche Italian Federation of Nursing Professions
FPÖ	Freedom Party of Austria
GS	Governance Systems
HBs	Health Boards

I	Interaction Area
IfSG	Infektionsschutzgesetz Infection Protection Act
IMV	minimum vital income
Inail	Italian Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità National Institute of Health (Italy)
ISTAT	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica Italian National Statistical Office
MFG	MFG Austria – People Freedom Fundamental Rights
MIV	minimum vital income
MOH	Ministry of Health
NCC	Government News Coordination Centre
NCCN	National Crisis Centre
NHS	National Health Service
NHS Wales	National Health Service Wales
NRR	National Risk Register
O	Outcomes
OPP	Ordem dos Psicólogos Portugueses Portuguese Psychologists Association
PAs	Autonomous Provinces
PCM	Presidency of the Council of Ministers
PHA	Public Health Agency
PHE	Public Health England
PHW	Public Health Wales
RCCE	Risk Communication and Community Engagement
RKI	Robert Koch Institute
RSU	Research Systems and Units
SAGE	Independent Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies
SKKM	Katastrophenschutzmanagement
SNCB	Belgian National Railway Company
SNS	National Health Service
TAC	Technical Advisory Cell
TAG	Technical Advisory Group
THW	Federal Agency for Technical Relief
UNHCR	United Nations High Commission for Refugees
WHO	World Health Organization

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents an analysis of COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP7: communication and information. The report focuses on specific communication strategies, formats of communication, reactions of the public, and the way different vulnerable groups were addressed and acknowledged in planning and implementing crisis communication. It is based on ten country reports, which provide an overview of how the pandemic was managed in terms of communication management, including changes over time and lessons learned. The country reports are based on expert interviews and references to country reports for D7.1, D7.3, and D7.5. Furthermore, the report includes frames for each country at the end, which were developed based on the D7.1 country reports, D7.5, data from the dashboard, and updated with the latest information which became available after D7.5. was submitted. These frames include some important indicators at country-level taken from the dashboard developed in the context of WP2 and provide an overview of the main themes addressed in the D7.7 country reports, considering different time periods during the pandemic.

D7.7. deliverable aims to address the research questions through cross-country analysis and synthesis. It is based on country reports from the 10 COVINFORM countries: Austria, Belgium, England, Greece, Germany, Sweden, Italy, Spain, Portugal, and Wales. The report starts off with an introductory chapter (Chapter 1), followed by an overview of the methods used to carry out the empirical research (Chapter 2). Here, particular attention is paid to the structure of the country reports completed by COVINFORM partners, and the governance framework (Ostrom's SES framework) adopted to accompany the country reports across all countries. In chapter 3, the country reports are presented. The final chapter (Chapter 4) provides a summary of the key findings across the COVINFORM countries organised around the following predefined in the DoA themes.

- Good and bad practices
- Communication to influence behaviour change;
- Digital communication and exclusion;
- Fighting mal-information, disinformation and misinformation,
- Representation of vulnerable groups and addressing vulnerable groups

The report is accompanied by two Annexes. Annex 1 contains the template for the country reports with the main guiding questions. Annex 2 contains the SES frameworks for each country.

The country reports from this deliverable will also be used as the basis for the D7.8 "*Synthesis and lessons learnt*" deliverable due in M35.

2 Methodology

The COVINFORM overarching research questions are:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practised?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response to certain vulnerable groups?
- RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

This deliverable addresses the overarching research questions in relation to WP7 *Inclusive COVID-19 Communication for Behavior Change & Addressing Misinformation*. The COVINFORM team is doing this by providing an update of the initial analysis of the findings presented in D7.3 report “*Analysis: Communication and Information*”. The analysis presented here utilises the data from D7.3, but also incorporates in a coherent and systematised way data from D7.1 report “*Baseline report: Communication and Information*” and D7.5 report “*Baseline report: Communication and Information – Update M26*”. Updated information has been incorporated from additional sources. In addition, the report incorporates data from the WP7 expert interviews conducted with government communicators and journalists. In total, 49 interviews were conducted across the ten countries, including 16 government communicators and 33 journalists. The interviews were conducted in the period October 2022 - January 2023. All partners, except one, managed to conduct the planned number of interviews. Trilateral Research could not recruit Government Communicators because United Kingdom Health Security Agency (UKHSA) communications were currently in the midst of responding to the Public Enquiry on COVID-19, and must be careful not to compromise that activity. The Government Communicator initially approached explained that if anything were to change, Trilateral Research would be informed. The circumstances have not changed to date. They conducted two interviews with journalists. University of Antwerp conducted two extra interviews: 3 journalists/editor, 3 government communicators and 1 communication expert working for an academic institution.

The empirical material presented in this report contains information from the previous deliverables, as well as updated information and to some extent new data. The data has been organised in country reports and so-called country frames for all the 10 countries, completed by COVINFORM partners. The country reports, presented in Chapter 3, follow standardised questions template (Annex 1), which are in line with the Research questions and with the country frames. That way each country report represents an updated coherent and focused summary of the findings relevant for WP7. The template for the country report includes questions concerning the following aspect: planning of the response and the crisis communication, implementation of crisis communication in the field of public health, with a special focus on measures to fighting mal-/dis-/misinformation, targeted communication campaigns to influence behaviour, the public reactions to crisis communication, and the specific barriers that occurred in the different stages. As a key factor of analysis to the COVINFORM project we also explored vulnerabilities acknowledged by governments and how they changed over time, the emergence of new vulnerabilities, responses in relation to vulnerable groups and how they were supported, and any new vulnerabilities that were created because of response measures. We paid

special attention to exclusion from main-stream crisis communication and measures to alleviate exclusion and vulnerabilities. All these aspects are traced over time in three periods.

Each country report is accompanied with a governance framework (known as Ostrom's SES framework) also referred to as country frame in this deliverable. The country frames can be found in Annex 2. Known for being an empirically applied conceptual framework, the purpose of the framework is to analyse complex social systems. The analysis approach does not have a methodological guide, which means this enables flexibility in how it may be adapted to diverse contexts. The frameworks consist of nested systems (Resource Systems and Units, Governance Systems, Actor Systems/Users; a description of the Interaction Area and Outcomes). This is connected to social, economic, and political settings and related ecosystems. An explanation of the SES framework methodology can be found in D3.2: "Multi-site research design and methodological framework".

In this deliverable, as well as in all of COVINFORMS Dx.7 deliverables, we used the SES framework to organise the data that we have collected over the course of the project in a systematic manner. We chose three different points in time (see below) to illustrate what has been done in terms of governmental crisis response and how this has changed over time. As such, the country frames are a visualisation of the cornerstones of governmental pandemic response and its changes over time, following the logic of the Ostrom model. Finally, the SES approach and the country frames will allow to contextualise the COVINFORM case studies (WP3) in a national setting as the same methodology is used.

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

- Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to a country and to manage a (health) crisis.
- Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis.
- Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country.
- Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the governmental crisis response.
- Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. In this concrete case it mostly describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, etc.).¹

This deliverable has taken into consideration three different phases: pre-pandemic, T1 – initial stages from 2020 until vaccination rollout had an effect on measures, and T2, from Omicron appearance until now. In this way, it focuses on temporality and change during the COVID-19 pandemic in order to understand the impact of the pandemic and its measures, key findings and best practices.

- T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020
- T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
- T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022

¹ In the country frames T0 the Interaction area is empty as T0 indicates the time prior to COVID-19. Hence, no interaction was taking place yet.

3 Country Reports

3.1 Austria

3.1.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic: crisis communication and planning of the response

Austria has a federal government. In terms of crisis management, the Staatliche Krisen- und Katastrophenschutzmanagement (SKKM), which is located within the ministry of interior, supports the federal states who are in charge of reacting to situations of crisis and catastrophe. Legal base is the Katastrophenhilfegesetz (the law regulating catastrophes) and, for the COVID-19 pandemic, the Epidemiegesetz (Epidemic law). Regarding Austria's public health system, the main actors include different federal ministries, health insurance funds, several specified health agencies as well as universities, research institutes, expert groups or non-governmental organisations.

While there was no overall crisis management plan, Austria had an Influenza Pandemic Plan and made use expert resources such as the Agency for Health and Food Safety (Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit, AGES), the European Commission, the European Medical Agency, and the World Health Organisation (WHO). Once the pandemic hit, the Corona task force was implemented, comprised of employees of the Ministry of Health, representatives from the Austrian Red Cross, medical professionals, scientists and a broad range of public health stakeholders. The Austrian Red Cross also had an important role in the crisis communication, implementing the information campaigns in close coordination with the Ministry of Health.

3.1.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic

When the pandemic hit, the Minister of Health, Rudolf Anschober, was legally in charge of handling the pandemic, as regulated in the Epidemic law. However, crisis communication happened in a constellation of four actors of the federal government, i.e., together with the chancellor Sebastian Kurz, the Minister of Interior Karl Nehammer, and the vice-chancellor Werner Kogler (the so-called virological quartet). Crisis communication happened through, 1.) a tight-knit schedule of press conferences (particularly between March-May 2020, with a decrease until August 2020 and an increase again during autumn/winter 2020/21), mainly to announce new measures and provide information about the current situation; 2.) regular updates of government-run websites and dashboards with data provided by the AGES; 3.) the Corona traffic light as early warning system for both risk of spread and systemic risk; 4.) information campaigns ("Schau auf mich, schau auf dich" launched in March 2020 to raise awareness of risk and provide actionable advice; "baby elephant" as metaphor for safety distance); 5.) hashtags on social media (e.g., #schauaufdich, #StayAtHome), and 6.) repurposing of the pre-existing health hotline 1450, as well as the installation of new hotlines as two-way communication channels. During the COVID-19 pandemic, several public health actors played a significant role in the pandemic response, but only few of them were majorly involved in formal communication strategies (e.g., Impfservice Wien, Ärztekammer).

A first important driver of change were the many changes in the federal government: chancellor Sebastian Kurz was replaced in October 2021 by Alexander Schallenberg, who was then replaced in December 2021 by Karl Nehammer, the former Minister of Interior. Minister of Health Rudolf Anschober stepped down in April 2021 and was replaced by Wolfgang Mückstein, who was replaced in March 2022 by Johannes Rauch. These changes in personnel changed crisis communication in two

ways. First, particularly chancellor Sebastian Kurz was a very prominent figure and declared Corona a “*matter for the boss*”. Also, the personal style of communication was very different between the different Ministers of Health. One example is the overall reduced communication by Mückstein, who followed a very different style compared to Anschober. Second, it influenced and somewhat complicated the internal processes. Over time, as pointed out by a government communicator, the political parties within the government got more and more involved (WP7_SYNYO_1), the political parties within the government got more and more involved in communicating the pandemic and taking political dividends out of this.

A second driver of change were conflicts and increasing politicization of the crisis management. Initially, i.e., during the first wave, crisis communication worked well and trust in the government increased: press conferences, strong leadership, simple and unified messages worked well. Trust declined over time, as also the numbers demonstrate. While in 2019 the trust in government was 50%, in 2020 it grew to 59%, but in 2021 it fell sharply to 41,5%. The tendency of initial increase and then a decrease of this indicator is observed across EU countries, however, Austria is exemplary with a significant drop below the starting level from 2019. This can be attributed to the political scandals related to the chancellors Sebastian Kurz, and the conflicts and subsequent changes within the government. The decreased trust in the government also resulted in less effective crisis communication.

As pointed out by a government communicator (WP7_SYNYO_1), due to the Epidemic law, the Minister of Health was responsible for the crisis management – not the chancellor. The government communicator assessed the pre-pandemic communication plan as old, but robust, because it took into account that the responsibility for imposing measures and taking decisions should be with the expert, in this case, the Minister of Health, rather than the chancellor (WP7_SYNYO_1). This also meant that the Minister of Health had to be careful to involve all relevant actors in the process, not only within the federal government and the coalition partner, but also the federal states because health matters are regulated within the federal states.

The same government communicator (WP7_SYNYO_1) described the increasingly difficult crisis communication during the first year of the pandemic, when the pandemic and the measures became politicised. “*It worked well. Until some poll numbers and other things suddenly played a role.*” (WP7_SYNYO_1) A lesson learned from this was to avoid turning the pandemic “*into a political show*” (ibid.). In addition to government-internal conflicts, the corona taskforce publicly criticised some of the governmental measures (e.g., the mass tests announced in November 2020). Politicizing crisis management and communication, while inevitable to a certain extent, did prove as a bad practice in terms of communicating measures, and taking decisions.

As the pandemic evolved, the one-size-fits-all communication approach was not sufficient anymore as various communities and individuals showed varying degrees of risk perception. The public opinion and the compliance with measures in Austria reflected this development. While at the beginning of the pandemic in Europe, acceptance was high – this had to do with the uncertainty in the face of an unknown threat – the willingness of the population to comply with the measures decreased in the following lockdowns as other factors came into play. As one of the respondents pointed out:

“...of course, you don't catch everyone..., but in this case, it's about getting a maximum with the available resources and that worked better at the beginning, because at the beginning compliance was much higher and with each time compliance became lower

*(pause) and if you look at it now, compliance with measures, it's just totally low.”
(WP7_SYNYO_2)*

This meant that communication needed to be more tailored to specific audiences. Particularly regarding the vaccination campaigns this was mentioned by the government communicators we interviewed: rather than trying to convince the entire population to get vaccinated, the focus was shifted towards providing fact-based information to those who are undecided.

“After more than a year of government communication what people want to hear from the government, they've already heard anyway. We will not be able to convince anyone in the media with the next chancellor or health minister, something else is necessary now. ... We set up the vaccination campaign in such a way that we gave people fact-based options for making a decision.” (WP7_SYNYO_2)

Another critical shift in the crisis communication happened with the announcement of mandatory vaccination by the federal government in autumn 2021. The Federal Act on Compulsory Vaccination against COVID-19 (law) was passed in January 2022. This led to resistance not only within the general public but also within the opposition. The Austrian populist parties Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ) and the newly funded MFG Austria – People Freedom Fundamental Rights (MFG) influenced the national communication through their anti-government and anti-vaccination rhetoric. Ultimately, the National Council voted against the COVID-19 mandatory vaccination which then got suspended in July 2022, only five months after it got installed in the first place (under the same government).

According to one of our interviewees the Minister of Health tried to be open and honest by providing numerical evidence to support their claims, but the public was not informed about the extent to which internal disagreements within the coalition government influenced decision-making. This information was apparent to those familiar with the situation and could be uncovered through confidential conversations, but was not communicated publicly: *“The fact that political interests were actually involved, which is normal in a coalition, was not transparently communicated to the public.” (WP7_SYNYO-4)*. Moreover, complexity played a central role in the decision of what to communicate: *“Well, there were things that we didn't report on because they were too complex.” (WP7_SYNYO-3)*

Associated with communication is the reaction of the population to crisis management. The public reacted to the crisis management and its changes in various ways. During the first wave, trust in the government increased due to effective crisis communication and strong leadership. However, over time, conflicts and increasing politicization of the crisis management led to a decline in trust in the government. One of the experts interviewed explains that in Austria, the proximity between legitimate criticism of the government's communication and denial of the virus' existence is due to the prevailing disillusionment with politics and antagonism towards science. This hostility towards science, in turn, is a significant problem that has stemmed from shortcomings in the country's educational policy, which have allowed people to be manipulated to some extent (WP7_SYNYO-4).

Experts also reflected on the confusion around the effectiveness of vaccines in preventing transmission, which may have been due to unclear communication in the media, leading people to believe that vaccination would guarantee complete protection against the virus. This misunderstanding has caused frustration and a lack of trust in pandemic measures among the population, further worsening the situation (WP7_SYNYO-3 and WP7_SYNYO-4).

A critique from one of our interviews is the way the government abruptly took away the population's ability to make decisions about their lives and implemented strict measures without always providing clear explanations. Although people initially complied, confusion arose when the government's communication became contradictory and targeted measures were inconsistent:

“So, the government took away from the population overnight any decision about any aspect of their lives and said, “This is no longer allowed, we are not doing this anymore.” Sometimes with explanation, sometimes without. That was a drastic change. It worked at the beginning, in the sense that people stayed at home. But it went wrong when the communication started contradicting itself, when targeted measures were obviously not coherent... And that's when people were lost. It's clear that you only let the government tell you what to do when you feel like they know what they're doing.” (WP7_SYNYO-4).

In summary, the communication strategy during the pandemic shifted abruptly without explanation to focus on individual responsibility. The government seemed to have given up on promoting vaccination, and people were left confused and uncertain about the situation. The lack of guidance and explanation left many unsure of how to proceed.

In accordance with an interviewee another lesson learned is about to see communication not just a support process, but a means of achieving operational success in a crisis. During a crisis, communication is just as critical as medical equipment or masks, as it can help prevent virus transmission. Therefore, communication must be organized differently and require individuals who understand both operational management and effective communication, rather than those who only specialize in public relations.

3.1.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the crisis communication

In terms of crisis communication, we have to differentiate between a) information provided to person with certain health vulnerabilities (e.g., older people, immunosuppressed people) and b) people who are vulnerable due to barriers to official government communication (e.g., non-German speakers). Both of the communicators in the context of the official crisis communication (WP7_SYNYO_1, WP7_SYNYO-2) described the aim of the initial crisis communication was to communicate in a simple way and reach as many people as possible, while taking into account that there would be some that are missed.

“We didn't serve niche target groups at the beginning...we have to get these eight and a half million Austrians... how do I get six million of them and not how do I translate this into 18 foreign languages. That was important and essential in the second, third, fourth step.” (WP7_SYNYO_2)

A best practice by the Austrian and also the Viennese government were the multiple communication channels they used to communicate with the population in order to reach various groups. This was inclusive and well planned from the early days on. One of the first activities to make communication more accessible was to include sign language interpreters in press conferences early on. In addition, non-profit organisations such as the Austrian Red Cross, the Caritas, the Volkshilfe or the Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund used their internal structures to communicate to vulnerable groups of both kinds. However, for example during the vaccination campaigns, a government communicated

(WP7_SYNYO_2) efforts to reach particularly vulnerable group such as immunosuppressed people to raise awareness.

Lessons learned included the importance of strong leadership, collaboration between different actors, and effective crisis communication strategies. A government communicator (WP7_SYNYO-2) also reported that a lesson learned in communicating with vulnerable populations was that there are some groups that cannot be reached through governmental communication or via mass media. Even with posters or personalised letters it is impossible to create narratives that reach these groups. One way to address this challenge was to work with key-persons, who are active in certain spheres and work with particular target groups. For example, the Muslims Youth of Austria organization assisted with translating in relevant languages. Another best practice for the future, is immediately involving CSOs working with various vulnerable groups in order to reach these groups in a more effective way through their channels. For example, CSOs who work with different groups of migrants, with care workers, especially hard-to-reach groups like live-in caseworkers, with seasonal workers, with homeless people, with elderly people etc.

To conclude, main lessons learned include: transparency and trust-building measures in place, coherent measures communicated in simple and clear terms, as well as the importance of involving civil society actors in the crisis management process.

3.2 Belgium

3.2.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic: crisis communication and planning of the response

Belgium's state structure has undergone a transition from a unitary state to a federalized country, with distinct territorial regions and language communities (see D7.1). This evolution has resulted in specific jurisdiction and policy responsibilities for each administrative layer (Derison, 2020). Because of the challenges of communicating, in March 2020, Belgium entered a "federal phase" in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. During this phase, coordination and communication regarding the pandemic were centralized at the federal level, with the National Crisis Centre (NCCN) taking the lead (CCVO, 2020). The NCCN became the focal point for crisis communication, ensuring a consistent approach throughout the country. Communication efforts at other administrative levels, such as the Coordination and Crisis Center of the Flemish government (CCVO), were aligned with the messages determined at the federal level (ibid.). However, when addressing issues falling under the responsibility of the federated entities, such as education and residential care for the elderly, these entities had the freedom to provide specific guidelines on how the federal measures applied within their respective jurisdictions.

According to the respondent from the federal government:

"You know a little bit about the Belgian structure of healthcare? In Belgium of course you have the federal level but then you also have the federal states, the regions that are competent for a whole number of parts of healthcare, including vaccination. So the coordination actually came at the federal level, so with us in the commissariat, but a lot of operational matters were with the federal states, especially vaccination. Also, the policy

consultations happened with eight health ministers.” (Communication expert_7, Belgium).

Regarding existing crisis communication plans, the following plans were available in Belgium prior to the pandemic:

1. General Emergency Plan ('03) - The relevance and specific information concerning communication within this plan are not specified.
2. National Pandemic Influenza Plan (WHO, '06) - This plan addresses crisis communication in the context of pandemic influenza.
3. Advisory Report Regarding National Pandemic Influenza Plan ('09) - This report provides additional guidance on the National Pandemic Influenza Plan.
4. Crisis Communication Guideline for local governments (by the NCCN, '07) - This guideline specifically focuses on crisis communication for local governments.
5. Guidance on the use of social media in Crisis Communication (by the NCCN, '13) - This guidance outlines the recommended use of social media during crisis communication efforts.

During the interview with the respondent from the federal government, it was noted that the response evolved organically over time. Meanwhile, the respondent responsible for the City of Antwerp’s crisis communication stated that initially, there was no concrete plan.

“The classic crisis communication planning as it had existed up until then focused on, yes, as I said a moment ago, large fires, incidents, but also police incidents that had occurred, in order to shape these in a professional way. We never thought that that was really going to be a long-term crisis in the beginning.” (Communication expert_5, Belgium)

3.2.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic

Based on the interview with the federal government respondent, traditional communication channels such as radio, television, press, posters, and leaflets were used to inform the public about the measures and vaccinations. There was a continuous flow of communication through daily press conferences, social media updates, and interaction with journalists. The helpline remained open continuously, even on weekends, to address inquiries from the public.

Healthcare professionals, including general practitioners, pharmacists, nurses, and other providers, directly interacted with citizens and played a vital role in communication efforts. They were trusted by the population, and their involvement helped in disseminating information. A website was established to provide comprehensive information about the pandemic's progression, vaccine safety, effectiveness, and overall vaccine strategy. Multiple communication channels, such as websites, telephone helplines, helpdesks, and social media platforms, were utilized to ensure accessibility and interactivity. Primary care and mutual health organizations played significant roles in disseminating information. Efforts were made to reach diverse target groups and provide information in over 40 different languages. Collaboration with civil society and intermediaries, including poverty organizations and mobile teams, was essential in reaching specific audiences and obtaining feedback. Confidants and contact points were used to facilitate effective communication.

On the operational side of vaccinations, community managers stationed at vaccination centres monitored coverage in their respective neighbourhoods. Tailored measures were taken if coverage was low, including engaging specific communities through their trusted networks. Pharmacists also played a significant role in initiating conversations about vaccination and addressing concerns.

In March 2022, the 'federal phase' ended, and regional authorities, provincial governors, and local administrations took primary responsibility for COVID-19 coordination and communication (Nationaal Crisiscentrum, 2022). National press conferences ceased, but the national COVID-19 website and helpline remained active. The Corona Commissioner's Office, established in October 2020 to improve coordination, concluded its activities in April 2022 as the crisis was deemed under control (VRT NWS, 2022).

During the crisis response, the respondents from the City of Antwerp note that there were significant changes in crisis communication, with a shift from purely informative messaging to a focus on connection, mental resilience, and people's well-being. This change reflected the recognition that addressing the pandemic required not only providing information but also supporting the overall well-being of the population. Initiatives like "Antwerpen Helpt" were introduced to facilitate effective mutual assistance among people.

Emphasizing that measures and vaccinations were based on scientific research and reliable data helped counteract the circulation of fake news and misinformation. The expert from the federal government also highlighted that communication cannot be separated from policy and vice versa. The importance of integrating communication into the decision-making process was emphasized, as communication alone cannot save inadequate policies. Well-founded policies are necessary for effective communication, and the involvement of communication experts in decision-making is crucial for successful crisis communication.

On a positive note, the collaboration between decision-makers and communicators from federal states was described as constructive. Regular meetings were held to exchange information and materials, leading to better coordination and support. Various initiatives were implemented to enhance communication, including nationwide campaigns in partnership with organizations such as the Belgian National Railway Company (SNCB) and the Post Office. Weekly Q&A sessions were conducted to keep the Dutch and French speaking press informed across the country, and consultations with different stakeholders, such as patient associations and the hotel and catering industry, were organized to address specific issues and concerns. Maintaining a network of contacts and trust was identified as a valuable lesson learned. It was emphasized that sustaining these connections beyond the crisis is important to facilitate quick reactivation during future problems, highlighting the significance of proactive communication.

As stated by the respondent from the federal government, "*One of our lessons learned is that you have to maintain such a network. You have to maintain those contacts even after such a crisis, so as soon as there is a problem again you can reactivate it very quickly. It's a matter of people trusting each other and working well together.*" (Communication expert_7, Belgium).

The respondent from the Belgian public broadcaster mentioned a key challenge during the pandemic was the limited number of scientists, especially science journalists, in the journalism workforce. This resulted in a gap in expertise when reporting on scientific topics like the pandemic. In an era of funding cuts and layoffs, this problem does not seem to be being addressed. However, it was acknowledged that there has been progress in expanding the pool of experts and knowledge related to pandemics, which would be beneficial in future similar situations.

Another challenge discussed from the perspective of journalists was the increasing criticism they faced throughout the pandemic. Journalists had the responsibility of allowing criticism to be heard while

avoiding the spread of objective disinformation. Striking the balance between these aspects proved to be difficult but necessary for responsible reporting.

The federal government respondent described how collaboration with experts from the University of Antwerp's communication sciences department allowed regular surveys to be conducted, such as the corona survey, which provided insights into the population's sentiments, beliefs, trust in vaccination, and raised questions. Monitoring mental health through a team from the University of Ghent also helped assess the impact of restrictive measures on the population's well-being. (The Motivation Barometer, 2023).

Concrete public health information campaigns played a crucial role in influencing behaviour change. For instance, measures like wearing masks and the lockdown were initially met with criticism due to concerns about mental health and the balance between mental well-being and the risk of infection. Finding a middle ground and addressing these concerns was a challenge. With vaccination, it was important to continuously communicate the effectiveness of the vaccines, side effects, and updates from vaccinologists and virologists since the vaccination process started while scientific research was still ongoing.

3.2.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the crisis communication

During the corona pandemic in Belgium, one of the key government messages was - next to preserving sufficient hospital beds for those in need of healthcare and aiming to increase the survival rates at the population level - to show solidarity with the most vulnerable ones in the system. Once vaccination against COVID-19 became a possibility, similar communication rationales were used for the vaccination campaigns. During the interview, a government communicator at the federal level indeed highlighted how they tried to capitalize on this feeling of solidarity in their official communication:

"... of course young people usually didn't get that sick from corona but still it was important for us that they respected the measures and got vaccinated to protect the elderly, vulnerable people. (...) Of course, people also got vaccinated because it meant they could travel, because it meant they could go to the pub, but still they were also concerned about their grandparents. (...) So we based our communication on that. So "Don't only take care of yourself but also your loved ones" and yes that did have an impact." (Communication expert_7, Belgium)

However, due to the long duration of the pandemic and the enduring impact on people's lives, the call for solidarity did not resonate as much anymore as it did in the beginning of the pandemic. Moreover, it had become clear that government messages not always reached or were well received by all groups in society. Indeed, the failure to develop an inclusive and accessible communication strategy was a recurrent criticism. In this context, a multi-disciplinary study on the COVID-19 government communication in Belgium highlights problems with the flow of information and reception of messages by particular hard-to-reach and vulnerable groups in society (Vandenbroucke et al., 2022). According to this study, these groups include primarily foreign-language speakers, vulnerable groups with low socio-economic status and/or with low literacy and people with sensory impairments (ibid).

While the COVID-19 pandemic revealed the need for a more inclusive communication strategy, it also made visible the challenges to achieve this. *"There is a lot of diversity among citizens and differences in social vulnerability, but also in their knowledge of Dutch"*, a government communicator at the city level stated, *"(...) There was also a difference in literacy and language skills, so it was quite a challenge*

to look at ‘How can we best reach these citizens and what form of communication or via what communication channel?’ (Communication expert_6, Belgium). Attempts, both at the more local and regional/national level, to reach vulnerable groups or create messages that resonate with particular groups were often made through cooperation with organizations concerned with inclusive communication and informing vulnerable groups. These attempts included for instance translating key information into multiple languages, focusing on using clear and simple language and using sign language interpreters in video messages. At the same time, to make sure that official communication also reaches specific vulnerable groups, the need to be proactive and make continuous efforts to have contacts and build trust in the communities-at-stake was also recognized. Indeed, one of the experts saw this as a “*lesson learned*”, noticing that “*it's too late if you only start doing it when the crisis is already happening, you need to already have those contacts*” (Communication expert_7, Belgium).

3.3 England

3.3.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

The United Kingdom consists of four countries: England, Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Wales. As the COVINFORM project has partners in England (TRI) and Wales (SU), these countries are the focus of the UK analysis. This report relates directly to England. For the pre-COVID-19 time period (T0), D7.1, “*Baseline report: communication and information*” and D7.5, “*Baseline report: communication and information – update*” deliverables, identified the following bodies responsible for (health) crisis communication prior to the pandemic:

- 1) Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS) – executive department of the Cabinet Office responsible for emergency planning and response. As stated in D7.1, the Civil Contingencies Act (CCA) and accompanying measures provide the framework for civil protection in the UK. The act includes duties for Category 1² responders to maintain plans to prevent emergencies and reduce, control, and mitigate the effects of emergencies. It also includes duties for them to communicate with the public;
- 2) Government Communication Service;
- 3) National Health Service (NHS) – public health care system in the UK;
- 4) The Health and Social Services Directorate;
- 5) Public Health England (PHE);
- 6) Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC);
- 7) Government News Coordination Centre (NCC);
- 8) NGOs (e.g., British Red Cross)

As mentioned in D7.1, in 2008, the UK Government published its first National Risk Register (NRR) outlining the key risks that could considerably disrupt the UK (*National Risk Register*, 2008). Pandemic Influenza was included in the Risk Register as a risk with a high relative likelihood and the highest relative impact related to the other risks included (*ibid*). In the 2017 NRR, there are links to influenza related resources, and they include: 1) the UK pandemic influenza strategy (DH Pandemic Influenza

² A category 1 responder includes organisations that are key to the response such as the Police, Fire and NHS

Preparedness Team, 2011), 2) the pandemic influenza evidence base (*UK Influenza Pandemic Preparedness Strategy*, 2014), and 3) the UK pandemic influenza guidance (*Pandemic Flu*, 2017).

3.3.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic

As stated in D7.1, the four nations forming the United Kingdom worked together to respond to the COVID-19 pandemic.

England announced its initial measures to control the virus on 22 January 2020. This was followed by the publication of an action plan on 3 March 2020 (Atchinson et al., 2021). A government-funded UK-wide information campaign was launched in the beginning of February 2020 that included advice on how to slow the spread of COVID-19 and reduce the virus's impact on the NHS (*Coronavirus Public Information Campaign Launched across the UK*, 2020). On 15 March 2020, the UK government started the three-part "Stay home, protect the NHS, save lives" campaign, followed on 24 March 2020 by the national 'Stay at Home' text message distribution by mobile phone operations "you must stay at home" (Independent SAGE, 2020). Referring back to D7.1, the former British Health Secretary Matt Hancock and Boris Johnson urged the public to avoid all non-essential contacts on 16 March 2020, and insisted, on 23 March 2020, that people must stay at home, with UK-wide legislation enforcing this decision on 26 March. On 29 March, a letter was sent to 30 million households that included one clear instruction: "you must stay at home".

The 2020 NRR addressed new risk summaries. Besides addressing serious and organised crime risks and hostile state activity, disinformation was also included (*National Risk Register 2020 Edition*, 2020). Tackling disinformation was identified as a key priority for the Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS). As of March 2023, it was reported that the refreshed NRR will be published in mid-2023 (Levin, 2023).

Additional changes in crisis response during the T1 phase include communications that focused on vaccinations. As reported in D7.5, in 2021/22, Public Health England prioritised communications relating to COVID-19 vaccinations (*First Mandated Health Campaign of 2021/22*, 2021). Furthermore, in March 2021, new priorities in terms of COVID-19 communication included how to recover from the COVID-19 pandemic and build back better (*UK Government Communication Plan 2021/2022*, 2021, p. 5).

Another change to crisis response included communicating the country's roadmap out of lockdown. Communications commenced in April 2021 and included a four-step plan to re-open the country (Walker & Belam, 2021).

During the T2 phase, changes in crisis response concerned communications focusing on living with the COVID-19 pandemic (*COVID-19 Response*, 2022).

In terms of changes to bodies responsible for crisis communication, there were no significant changes. However, D7.5 reported that the DCMS played a role in fighting misinformation and disinformation within the context of COVID-19. As reported in D7.5, on 9 March 2020, a press release announced that the UK government established a cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit to combat lies, conspiracy theories and cyber security threats associated with the COVID-19 virus (Scroxtton, 2020).

Regarding changes to UK response, particularly during the T1 phase, the UK government did not use the Civil Contingencies Act. As mentioned in D4.5, the government drafted the 2020 Coronavirus Bill

and hurried it through parliament. When asked why the CCA was not being invoked, former Minister for Brexit Opportunities and Government Efficiency of the United Kingdom Jacob Rees-Mogg said that the CCA is for “*emergencies of which the government has had no warning*” (Lent, 2020).

For WP7 interviews with Government Communicators, TRI was unable to recruit interviews with relevant stakeholders because officials outlined how they are currently responding to a Public Enquiry on COVID-19 and must be careful not to compromise that activity. Thus, all interview commentary provided below relates to interviews conducted with Journalists who communicated COVID-19 communication during the pandemic.

On the topic of measures to fight mal-/dis-/misinformation, one of the interviewees took advantage of their radio programme to address such issues. The interviewee commented:

“Again, we would – it would be more probably the programmes that went out Monday to Friday, the main [six till six] programming that went on. On my show, I think we would just report – we would say that so and so is being said. If we had a guest to counteract that, that would be fine, but I think that’s what we would do to find somebody who we felt was – that would come through our sources, so they’re valid, to counteract that misinformation and say whether it’s true or not true” [Journalist 1].

The other interviewee interviewed did not necessarily shed light on special measures put in place, but explained that:

“Again, it’s the same as ever, which is if there is something that is going round, that is misinformation and you can factually – you can source that, then we’re reporting it whether that was stuff that was online, or social media. Whilst you are taking people’s opinions, you are also making very clear what has been absolutely given as a fact – factual information. You were going to – as we always do, hear people, hear them. Not shut them down, hear their voices, but also be very clear when something is a fact. So I think that again feeds into what we do every single day, it’s just that it was all based around Covid and the response to Covid” [Journalist 2].

Primary Data

Reflecting on interviews conducted with Journalists, some **communication recommendations were observed**, specifically, the need for a more personalised approach. When commenting on the effectiveness of the Journalist’s COVID-19 communication, in comparison to the government’s COVID-19 communication, the interviewee explained:

“I think the only difference is it’s I’m a local person who’s living in the area and heard the stories from friends and families. So you could – then, I suppose, you’ve got a personal touch and personal investment in how that comes across, if that makes sense, to say to people, this is real. This is happening. I know, because I’ve lost a family member or a friend, if that makes sense” [Journalist 1].

Another journalist interviewed was asked to reflect on the following:

- 1) Overall perceptions of COVID-19 communication by the government;
- 2) How Journalists bridged the gap between government communication and the public;
- 3) How transparent COVID-19 communication by Government Communicators were.

In response to these reflections, the interviewee explained that when they were communicating COVID-19 information, they did not protest or fill in any gaps. Their only responsibility was to reflect what the government was saying. In addition, the Journalist explained that their organisation tried to explain the context around the information being disclosed. In their own words, the interviewee said:

“We were doing that regularly, every night we have the press briefings et cetera, but we were also reflecting the questions in terms of that transparency. We’re also reflecting the questions raised, the questions people had about the strategy, about its effectiveness, about how it was being implemented locally. We were doing that more and more as it went on, because it was obvious it was going to be a long-term thing and it actually became more and more complex. We were – for instance we often would take live on the radio the briefings, and then we’d try and reflect or explain some of what the government were saying in context, and we’d then get experts on as well. We’d also reflect the questions that were being asked of that, whatever the strategy was, whether it was lockdown, whether it was not lockdown, whether it was different things for different areas. We were just questioning again it was all that we do anyway it was just very focused on Covid” [Journalist 2].

Besides these examples of communication reflections, good practices in terms of COVID-19 reporting were also identified. According to one of the Journalists interviewed, reporting on the reality of the COVID-19 pandemic was impactful. For example, reporting on the devastating reality for those who were unable to comfort or grieve loved ones:

“I think there was lots of reporting of the real pain of families that stood out and the isolation of people who had lost someone who couldn’t be with their loved ones when they were very ill. I’m never going to forget some of those stories because they’re so incredibly powerful. People who couldn’t be with – people who couldn’t be at funerals and that will never change. They lost that person during that time which meant that they couldn’t experience what most people have a right to experience” [Journalist 2].

The Journalist further added that a lot of their coverage came from trusted sources, which reflected on the horror of such situations *“as it should.”* In their own words, the Journalist commented:

“I think a lot of our coverage really did reflect the horror of some of that situation as it should, and the audience – I think the other thing was the hospital reporting we did was very stark. The pressure on hospitals and the way that hospital staff and frontline workers were dealing with some really difficult times. That really stood out to me as well, because I think we did a really good job on that. We had very thankful audiences and I think it was really interesting because people had – there was quite a lot of political turmoil leading up to Covid anyway and there was quite a lot of – you’d have some difficult conversations with people out and about but to feel the sort of appreciation, or not even appreciation just that people were relieved that there was somewhere that they could go to listen or watch, or read trusted information and trusted stories and proper questioning. I really felt that as a journalist in a way that I had never experienced before” [Journalist 2].

Secondary Data

As stated in D7.5, some **lessons learned** include the following:

- 1) Communication actors are community leaders or trusted information providers for Black, Asian, minority ethnic (BAME) communities in the UK (*Factors influencing COVID-19 vaccine uptake among minority ethnic groups*, 2021)
- 2) More work is required to strengthen honesty, credibility, and empathy of COVID-19 communications by the UK government (Abrams et al., 2021)
- 3) Gamification was used during the COVID-19 pandemic to address COVID-19 misinformation (Lewsey, 2020)

As reported in D7.5, an August 2021 report titled ‘Public Perceptions of UK and Local Government about COVID-19’ was released (Abrams et al., 2021). Overall, the findings revealed that both UK and local government communications were perceived as reasonably clear and used comprehensible language. At the same time, however, notable differences appeared on other measures:

- 1) Just over half of respondents viewed the UK government communications as being low in honesty and credibility (51.6%) and as low in empathy (50.2%).
- 2) Less respondents viewed local government communication as being low in honesty and credibility (35.5%) and low in empathy (38.7%).
- 3) Approximately half of respondents (47.9%) believed the UK governments communication did not meet their community’s needs, with a lower proportion of respondents (35.9%) reporting the same for local government communication.
- 4) UK government communications outdid local government in only one area: 44.8% considered government information as highly attainable and easy to find, whereas 23.7% interpreted local government information as highly attainable and easy to find
- 5) Maybe unsurprisingly, people who firmly associate with Britain or their local area are more likely to consider both UK government and local communications more positively (Abrams et al., 2021).

In terms of public health information campaigns, the ‘Better Health’ campaign launched by the UK government on 27 July 2020 is relevant. Launched during the COVID-19 pandemic, the campaign motivated individuals to make healthier lifestyle choices, by losing weight, getting active and quitting smoking. Responses in terms of behaviour change resulting from the campaign have been mixed (Talbot & Branley-Bell, 2022). In terms of critique, this has included the lack of consideration for mental health by the campaign, with one person tweeting: “*there is no #BetterHealth without mental health*” (ibid). According to researchers, this was seen as problematic, especially since the campaign was launched during the COVID-19 pandemic, a time where mental health was known to be deteriorating across the world (ibid).

3.3.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

As can be seen in the SES framework for England, during the T0 phase, groups recognised as vulnerable included non-native speakers, blind or deaf people, people with disabilities, foreign nationals, asylum seekers, and refugees. During the T1 phase, vulnerabilities included those with special conditions (e.g., chronic diseases), ethnic minorities, non-native speakers, youth and children, the elderly, those who fell under the autism spectrum, disabled people, and migrants. T2 vulnerabilities included pregnant women, people with learning disabilities, serious mental illnesses, or other health conditions.

With a focus on vulnerabilities among ethnic minorities residing in England, it was reported, in D7.5, that after more than a year into the pandemic, ethnic minority communities in the UK and elsewhere, were still affected by COVID-19 morbidity and mortality (Ala et al., 2021).

During the T1 phase, the government released advice on shielding and safeguarding people who, on medical grounds, are seen as extremely vulnerable to COVID-19 (Smith, 2020). A small group working across national organisations – from NHSX, NHS Digital, NHS Business Services Authority and the Behavioural Insights Team (BIT) – were asked to develop the new text messaging service that would provide this data (ibid). This service formed part of a Vulnerable, Isolated and Social Care team, which assessed how we utilise technology to assist vulnerable people (ibid).

During this time period, digital innovations were also being tested to assist vulnerable people during the COVID-19 outbreak (*Digital Innovations Tested to Support Vulnerable People during COVID-19 Outbreak*, 2020). Besides these digital innovations, D7.5 also states that the government recognised the significance of endorsing effective communication with people with learning disabilities and autism (*The Government's Response to the Health and Social Care Committee and Science and Technology Committee Joint Report: Coronavirus: Lessons Learned to Date*, 2022).

T2 phase

Communications and cross-government COVID-19 campaign activities made sure to focus on encouraging vaccine uptake as the rollout expanded (*Third Quarterly Report on Progress to Address COVID-19 Health Inequalities*, 2021). This has included using efficient media channels and building on relationships formed with influencers and local communities to reach ethnic minority groups with data about vaccines in multiple languages (ibid).

3.4 Germany

3.4.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

Germany is a federal parliamentary democracy with legislative, executive, and judicial branches. On a federal level, a Chancellor, elected by the national parliament (Bundestag) sets the top-level policy agenda, while cabinet ministers set policy agendas for their respective ministries. In the event of a crisis, the relevant ministries have the responsibility of forming a crisis task force (Krisenstab) that coordinates action on a federal level. The National Pandemic Plan specifies that in a health crisis, protocol is to call up a joint Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) and Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG) responsible for advising the Federal Government and implementing its policy decisions. Every ministry is represented by a liaison officer, as are the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response (BBK) and the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW). The federally-funded Robert Koch Institute (RKI) plays the central medical and bioscientific advisory role. Governmental health, risk, and crisis communications planning in Germany on the federal level is centralised, with the key actors the BMG, the RKI, and the Federal Centre for Health Communication (BZgA). During the COVID-19 pandemic, a steering committee including representatives of these institutions met regularly to monitor and evaluate communications strategies and campaigns (cf. Drucksache 19/32553).

Germany is comprised of 16 states, which enjoy significant administrative autonomy, and are generally responsible for internal security, education policy, cultural policy, infrastructure, and the day-to-day

implementation of federal policies. As the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated, the states also enjoy significant autonomy with regard to crisis management, within the strictures of federally established laws and guidelines. Governmental communications officers working on the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels interviewed during the COVINFORM project indicated that during the pandemic, multiple lines of communication and cooperation were established between institutions at different levels of government in Germany, and that this ultimately increased public authorities' capacity to communicate to and protect members of vulnerable groups:

“There were the Ministerial Conferences, the MPK, the Conference of Minister Presidents, which we all still know. There were the Minister Presidents with the Federal Chancellor. And there was the level of the health ministries, i.e. the health ministries of the federal states all joined together. And then, of course, there was coordination with the municipalities, i.e. with the urban and rural districts, within the states. We had all kind of task forces, especially when it comes to vulnerable groups or the old people's and nursing homes from the care sector, because this is also a part of health communication... Ultimately, all the measures that have been taken lead to the protection of vulnerable groups.” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

A communications officer working on the state level also indicated that the public sometimes appeared confused about the federalised nature of German public health governance; for instance, one state resident confused the state health minister with the federal health minister in a comment on his institution's Facebook page:

“[...] We had a Facebook comment 'Health Minister Lucha? Has Mr. Span been deposed?' Where you then noticed that this person doesn't even know that there is a state ministry of health and that the Infection Protection Act is a law for which the states are responsible. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

This stakeholder observation validates the assertion in the federal government's *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy: Report of the Expert Committee Pursuant to § 5 para. 9 IfSG* (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022) that in order to minimize the risk of confusion and enhance the political legitimacy of public health measures, different roles and responsibilities – including in health, risk, and crisis communications – must be clearly distributed, understandable, and transparent, and should be presented to the public in an understandable manner (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022, pp. 50-52).

On a federal level, the key legal instruments in epidemic/pandemic planning in Germany prior to COVID-19 were the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG) and the two-part National Pandemic Plan (Robert Koch-Institut 2016; 2017). The National Pandemic Plan is itself a successor to an earlier pandemic plan launched in 2005, which was modified in part to integrate lessons learned during the 2009 influenza (H1N1) pandemic (Robert Koch-Institut, 2017, pp. 5–6). The National Pandemic Plan identifies three stages in pandemic governance that follow the progression of a pandemic:

- “Containment”: focus on preventing the introduction and spread of the virus.
- “Protection”: focus on protecting the health care system and at-risk-groups.

- “Mitigation”: focus on improving the knowledge of at-risk groups, developing targeted interventions, ensuring the resilience of the health care system, improving means of surveillance, communications measures, and community engagement

With regard to health, risk, and crisis communication, the plan emphasises transparency and evidence-based messaging, with a grounding in communications science (Robert Koch-Institut, 2016). It specifies that, in addition to basic information on protective measures, in-depth information should be tailored to reach as many (vulnerable) population groups as possible (Robert Koch-Institut, 2017). Written materials should be offered in German and in other languages, and target-group-specific material should be pre-tested during interpandemic phases. The plan also reflects on different population groups’ affinities for internet-based communication, suggesting that in order to reach certain groups, central hotlines as well as online portals should be established during crises.

On a sub-federal level, the state of Baden-Württemberg and the city-state of Berlin both published formal pandemic strategies/plans, which include at least some material on communications. The Baden-Württemberg plan focuses on pandemic influenza, and was released on March 2, 2020 as an iteratively-edited “living document” available on the website of the state Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, and Integration, and linked to by the RKI index of state-level pandemic plans (*Baden-Influenzapandemieplan Baden-Württemberg*, 2020). This plan does not provide detailed guidelines for health, risk, and crisis communication, but indicates that its central aim should be to “ensure that the population is informed quickly, factually, and comprehensively in order to avoid unrest and anxiety”; that communications should be planned and implemented in cooperation with federal authorities; that communicators should prioritise media that can be updated quickly, have high market penetration, and can respond to public questions and requests; that active measures should be taken against misinformation on social media; and that physicians and other local “multipliers” should be leveraged to increase communications penetration. It also suggests that interpandemic periods should be used to raise awareness of behavioural measures for future pandemics. These recommendations largely echo federal-level guidelines.

The target municipality on which the German COVINFORM research focused, Mannheim, did not publish a formal strategy/plan. However, individual communications practices appear to have been shaped on both the state and municipal levels in accordance with federal and state guidelines and precedents. Governmental communications officers working at the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels interviewed during the COVINFORM project confirmed that they were well-acquainted with national and state communications plans at the time the COVID-19 pandemic hit, had experience from prior crises, and had participated in various trainings and exercises to prepare for crises (including on the cross-national level), however, that the unprecedented characteristics of the COVID-19 pandemic (such as its length) required these plans to be adapted in unforeseen ways:

“[...] What we have is called, well, not only us, it's called LÜKEX. These are exercises. [...] Cross-national crisis communication exercises or something similar, which take place, I think, every 2 to 3 years.” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“Well, there are communication plans for disasters and so on. [...] Well, we have used our plans and they have also proved successful. Of course, you always have to adjust them a bit. For example, these plans were often not designed for two years. It's also the case that

the personnel deployment is not designed for two years." (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

On 4 March, the Robert Koch Institute officially updated the National Pandemic Plan in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (Robert Koch-Institut, 2020a, b). Further official extensions, modifications, or updates to account for aspects such as those mentioned by the interviewed stakeholders have not yet been implemented; however, judging from the assessment in the *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy*, it is conceivable that such updates may be forthcoming (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022).

3.4.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

With regard to both the pandemic itself and the German authorities' response to it, the first quarter of 2020 was marked by rapid escalation. The first case of COVID-19 in Germany was recorded on January 27, 2020. In accordance with the National Pandemic Plan and IfSG, a joint BMG/BMI task force was established in February 2020. On 16 March, a lockdown was announced, extending until 16 April. On 28 March, the Federal Government passed the First Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance.

With regard to health, risk, and crisis communication, early 2020 was characterized by messages designed to promote voluntary health-protective behaviour, while also maximising compliance with regulations. This is logical, as during this phase, non-pharmaceutical interventions were the only real tools available to authorities to attempt to control the pandemic. In February 2021, the Federal Ministry of Health debuted the basic risk mitigation slogan "Through the year with AHA" ("Mit AHA durchs Jahr"):

1. „Abstand halten“ – “keep a safe distance”
2. „Hygiene-Maßnahmen beachten“ – “pay attention to hygiene measures”
3. „Alltagsmaske tragen“ – “wear a mask on an everyday basis”

The AHA formula remained at the core of health, risk, and crisis communication throughout the pandemic. However, the more detailed communication strategies and measures that took shape around this core shifted over the course of the period. In Winter 2020, the federal government announced (first to the press, then, after a leak, publicly) a communique entitled *How We Will Bring COVID-19 Under Control (Wie wir COVID-19 unter Kontrolle bekommen)* with three pillars: 1. promoting health-protection behaviours and emphasising the moral obligation to protect others; 2. promoting solidarity; and 3. encouraging and supporting people in bearing with restrictions and deprivations for an unknown, but perhaps long, stretch of time. The communique emphasised the importance of consistency across sources and channels, and approved shock and even fear-based messages as a potential means of getting across the fact that the virus was not only a danger to “at-risk” groups, but the population as a whole. An example is the #ichhatteCorona (I had Corona) campaign, which focused on risks to multiple generations, featuring individual COVID-19 patients of multiple ages, genders, and sociodemographic backgrounds – including young people – discussing their personal experience of the virus' psychological and physical dangers and impacts (Presse- und Informationsamt der Bundesregierung, 2020a).

Governmental communications officers working on the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels interviewed during the COVINFORM project confirmed that the early days

of the pandemic were marked by uncertainty and rapid escalation, and that this resulted in unforeseen demands and an unprecedented amount of stress:

“If you look at the literature on crisis communication, there are always these 4 phases. The initial phase, the acute phase and then at some point the phase where it drifts out again. [...] And I remember our boss had somehow.... At the end of the year there was the first article 'mysterious lung disease broke out in China'. [...] And he had bought it for our press review and then we said: 'Why are you buying this? This is something in China and, of course, has little to do with the state level in Baden-Württemberg'. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“[...] I can remember the first day that cases appeared in Mannheim, so to speak, and from then on, of course, communication had to be set up in a completely different way. Especially on a daily basis, that was important for us, and that was also the stressful part of the whole thing. (...) So first of all, of course, it was the communication, how can I protect myself from infection, so the very normal hygiene rules.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

During the second through fourth quarters of 2020, both the pandemic and response measures were characterized by “waves”: oscillation between severe and comparatively less severe phases, and difficulty in predicting what might come next and what an appropriate path forward might look like. A governmental communications officer working at the City of Mannheim level confirms that rapidly-changing regulatory and information situations imposed significant stress during this period:

“it sort of broke in on us from one day to the next. We had heard for some time that something was happening, and I can remember the first day that cases appeared in Mannheim, and from then on, communication had to be set up in a completely different way. Especially on a daily basis, that was important for us, and that was also the stressful part of the whole thing [...] well, first of all, it was, of course, communication on how can I protect myself from infection, so the quite normal hygiene rules. Especially in the case of Mannheim, it was, of course, multilingual. That was our goal. Then came the second phase of communicating state ordinances, which often came at very short notice, to the population. The third phase was the vaccination phase, so to speak, to set up the vaccination campaign for the whole thing. These are roughly the three phases that took place.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

By April 2020, case rates began to decrease, and the national-level hard lockdown was phased out. On 14 May, the Federal Government adopted the Second Act for the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance. Throughout Summer 2020, a focus on testing and tracing was maintained, with the introduction of the Corona-Warn-App as a highlight. In October 2020, another severe wave hit Germany, leading to a second national-level hard lockdown on 2 November, originally planned until 19 December, but in most sites extending through early 2021. With regard to health, risk, and crisis communication, a shift can be observed during Q2-Q4 2020 from a tone of shock and fear to a tone of solidarity and resilience. An example is the #besondereHelden campaign, which focused on the efforts of the younger generations to demonstrate solidarity with vulnerable older generations by adhering to regulations (Hanfeld, 2020).

Target group-specific campaigns also increased in prominence during Q2-Q4 2020, e.g., campaigns designed to address and resonate with young people, older people, people with a migration background, etc., rather than the population as a whole. Two more examples, both targeted toward young people, are #WirBleibenZuhause (we stay at home) and #FürMichFürUns (for me, for us), both of which were designed to mitigate growing frustration at extended social distancing regulations and their impact on activities central to young people's lives (note that tracking studies such as the University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring Project, discussed below, provided policymakers with real-time data on public perceptions of COVID-19 measures, though it cannot be confirmed whether specific data motivated the design of specific campaigns). The main modes of distribution for these campaigns were the distribution of videos via websites and YouTube and the sharing of the hashtags on Twitter, Instagram and Facebook. Slogans used included "I want to go to my favourite restaurant again. That's why I think of AHA" and "I want to travel again – that's why I keep my social contact down." Furthermore, enhanced measures were planned and taken against misinformation, as evidenced by a May 2020 federal government press release on "Recognising Fake News" (Presse- und Informationsamt der Bundesregierung, 2020b).

Between T1 and T2, governmental institutions responsible for crisis management and communication did not significantly change, with the exception of the creation of some new entities, such as the federal government's Coronavirus Expert Council, and the appointment of a further panel of experts empowered under the IfSG to evaluate all pandemic management efforts, including health, risk, and crisis communication (for more details on both, see below).

In Germany, as in Europe and most of the world, the transition from 2020 to 2021 was dominated by the introduction of vaccines. On 21 December 2020, the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine was approved, and on 27 December, the Moderna vaccine was approved. Vaccines were rolled out in a staged plan (*Stufenplan*), following six levels of risk of a severe progression and/or heightened exposure (Robert Koch-Institut, 2021a). Rollout to the first risk group started in December 2020 and progressed through the risk groups until rollout to the general population (risk group 6) in early June 2021. In tandem with vaccination, the federal government pursued a strategy of more targeted testing, tracing, and containment, including through the imposition of so-called "2G/2G+/3G" regulations, i.e., exemptions from social distancing rules for the vaccinated (*Geimpfte*), recovered (*Genesene*), and tested (*Getestete*). Such measures were primarily implemented on a state-by-state level in response to changing local conditions.

With regard to health, risk, and crisis communication, pro-vaccination messaging took centre stage during this phase, including proactive campaigns to debunk misinformation about vaccines. The general tone remained one of solidarity rather than fear. An example is "Deutschland krempelt die #ÄrmelHoch" (Germany rolls up the sleeves), a nationwide vaccination promotion campaign, conducted under the federal government's "Zusammen Gegen Corona" (together against Corona) umbrella campaign (Drucksache 19/29272, p. 3). According to a response to a Section 9 (3) IFG information request submitted on the transparency website FragDenStaat, the campaign has been implemented by the respective communications agencies with which the BMG has had framework contracts (*Deutschland krempelt die #ÄrmelHoch*, 2021). Another example is "#HelloAgain", intended to sway the unconvinced that a second vaccination was necessary, using the emotional appeal "Holen wir uns das volle Leben zurück – Hello Again, Normalität" (Let's Get a Full Life Back – Hello Again, Normality) and a series of spots that "communicate in a lively way the reminder of what has been

missing in the past year and a half of the pandemic, which will be possible again when community protection is achieved” (Drucksache 19/32553, p. 3).

The reference period of Q2 2021 and Q3 2022 also saw increasing criticism of authorities’ strategies, and in response, a move toward increasingly comprehensive and transparent evaluations. This is exemplified by public inquiries made in the national parliament in May and September 2021 (Drucksache 19/29272 and Drucksache 19/32553). Possibly in part as a response, the 31 March 2021 Law on the Continuation of Regulations Concerning the Epidemic Situation of National Importance (EpLaFoG) added a mandate to the Infection Protection Act requiring an expert evaluation of COVID-19 policy, to be submitted by 30 June 2022. The resulting *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy* contains a comprehensive assessment of health, risk, and crisis communication (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022). Furthermore, in December 2021, the federal and state governments convened a Coronavirus Expert Council, which authored a statement about health, risk, and crisis communication (Statement 5, 2022) and provided recommendations on risk communication in several other statements. We can conclude that since 2021, a more transparent evaluation cycle has become a key attribute of German health, risk, and crisis communications planning, which authorities intend to emphasise during future crises.

It is conceivable that the planners of specific campaigns may have taken account of this critical turn. For example, the “Ich schütze mich” (I protect myself) campaign, which promoted self-protection measures, including vaccination and adherence to health-protective recommendations and regulations, in anticipation of rising case rates in Autumn/ Winter 2022/ 23, featured a very diverse set of individuals in brief videos stating their reasons for actively protecting themselves from infection (“Ich schütze mich”, 2022). In contrast to the “Deutschland krempelt die ÄrmelHoch” campaign mentioned above, the videos emphasise lifestyle diversity as well as cultural diversity: the subjects range from teachers and doctors to musicians and bikers, and are filmed in their homes or workplaces to convey a sense of authenticity. The “Ich schütze mich” website links to an online tool that provides vaccination advice based on a series of simple interactive questions – a move toward personalisation, which can be interpreted as an extension of a targeted rather than one-size-fits-all approach to the delivery of health information and health-protective behavioural recommendations (*Der Corona-Impfcheck*, 2023).

By March 2022, key indicators began to improve. In April, most federal-level restrictions were lifted, though masks remained mandatory in hospitals and public transportation. In May, 2G rules were lifted on a federal level. By Winter 2022, public-facing experts such as virologist Christian Drosten concluded that COVID-19 had evolved into an endemic.

Communications professionals working on the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels interviewed during the COVINFORM project offered reflections on health, risk, and crisis communications during the pandemic. In Germany, two journalists, two governmental communications officers, and one public relations professional were interviewed (the latter worked for a PR firm that consulted on and implemented COVID-19 communications campaigns for public authorities). Though the sample sizes were too small to be representative of the professional groups as a whole, among our interviewees, governmental communications officers generally gave more positive overall assessments of health, risk, and crisis communications during the pandemic:

“Well, I would say that in general I agree 99.9% of the time that the basic consensus in society was greater on certain measures than what was reported in the media. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“All in all, considering that it was monothematic, one can safely assume that we got through, also with the messages.” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“So I actually rate our communication success to be very high. [...] I can only say that the feedback I have received from the population, or that we have received, has been extremely good. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

It should be noted that both German governmental communications officers interviewed during the course of the COVINFORM project were highly self-reflective, and did not hesitate to criticise state institutions, including their own, with regard to specific aspects of communications workflows and outcomes. For instance, they made it clear that health, risk, and crisis communication is a job that bears psychological burdens, which were not always recognised to the same extent as the psychological burdens faced by other front-line workers, such as health care workers:

“Of course, it's clear that if you sit there in the evening and have to report the deaths every night [...] that's a psychological burden, I found it quite intense.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

“I would draw up staff schedules, I would also provide supervision or psychological support for the people, the colleagues, [...] I would have more people assigned so that you are on duty for a fortnight and then you are off for a week.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

Despite such criticisms, the German governmental communications officers interviewed within the COVINFORM project gave generally positive assessments of COVID-19 communications strategies and measures. This is in contrast to the three non-governmental communications professionals interviewed in Germany, who tended to be critical of efforts by public authorities. With regard to the timeliness, intelligibility, and professionalism of governmental dissemination efforts toward the public and communication/coordination with media stakeholders, as well as the transparency of governmental decision-making, these interviewees were ambivalent. We can conclude that communications between federal authorities and media stakeholders tended to be inadequate, especially with regard to transparency.

“Basically, it was almost catastrophic, I would say. So, yes, if you only relate it to communication, political decision-makers also make mistakes. And one shouldn't focus too much on the fact that they made a big mistake. Instead, many things should have been explained better and more clearly. But they tried to hide behind this situation [...] And that's where politics, from my point of view, made many mistakes and always avoided facing the real discussion. If they ask that as well, how regulations are made, that's another issue.” (WP7_SINUS_02, Journalist)

“Oh, and when I think about it, really the federal government level, no, there was often not enough transparency. And not enough explanation as to why one is doing one thing now and not another.” (WP7_SINUS_01, Journalist)

By contrast, the perceived adequacy of communications between state and/or municipal authorities and media stakeholders varied greatly site-by-site:

“[...] I would say that the municipality was better from the beginning than, for example, the federal and state governments [...] So there was better, closer contact, and then I think also a learning curve. So the communication performance of the city administration has also multiplied. The Corona press releases alone were increasingly closely timed, and they always reacted very quickly. If something new came from the state, then a few hours later the city's interpretation was also in our mailbox, so to speak.” (WP7_SINUS_01, Journalist)

“And the crisis communication of the authorities, well, my analysis would be that it was often too little too late, or too late and too complex. And what they have really decided and wanted to implement could often have been communicated earlier and in a more comprehensible way. [...] I still remember, very faintly, so to speak [laughs], that at the beginning I also commented on some mistakes made by ... let's say the city, but consciously with indulgence, because I thought we all had to stick together [...] Later it was different at some point, then I also commented more sharply again, because one could have expected a learning curve by then.” (WP7_SINUS_01, Journalist)

“There were municipalities that communicated very quickly and very actively. [...] However, now take a step back and go to medium-sized district towns, Schwetzingen, Mannheim, Weinheim, Wiesloch. [...] If you take a look at how they communicated, I can only shake my head. If you think about how long it took the municipalities to communicate the topic, to develop posters or whatever: a disaster. (WP7_SINUS_05, Public relations professional)

The University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring Project conducted cross-sectional surveys of the German population from March 2020 until December 2022, covering several dimensions of public reactions to COVID-19 policy – including dimensions relevant to the assessment of health, risk, and crisis communication, such as trust in institutions. A summary of variables relevant to communications follows (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022):

	14.04.2020	23.03.2021	14.04.2022	29.11.2022
Trust in health institutions (scale of 1 to 7)	4.74	3.68	4.02	3.96
Trust in federal government (scale of 1 to 7)	4.42	3.00	3.28	3.28
Frequency of mask wearing (frequency from 1 to 5)	2.25	4.63	3.89	3.35
Belief in conspiracy theories in general (scale of 1 to 7; mean of 5 items)	4.23 (17.03.20)	3.73 (26.01.21)	4.18	3.99 (02.11.22)

Since the beginning of the pandemic, a steering committee including representatives of the RKI, BZgA, and the communication section of the BMG has met regularly to monitor and evaluate communications strategies and campaigns on the basis of these and other studies (cf. Drucksache 19/32553).

Tangentially, several health care workers (HCWs) interviewed in the City of Mannheim area during the COVINFORM project asserted that the fear-based health, risk, and crisis communication, and other extreme measures could have a cascading negative impact on physical health:

"We all function in such a way that fear makes us sick more easily and progressions often more severely than confidence" (WP5_SINUS_2, health care worker)

"Please educate people better instead of driving them crazy with fear. That would be the most important thing" (WP5_SINUS_7, health care worker)

"What was most shocking was that there was no discussion at all, it was imposed. The pressure was terrible, and that's the only reason I finally did it, I would have liked to wait until everything was clearer" (WP5_SINUS_2, health care worker)

These critiques mirror the talking points of the so-called "lateral thinker" (*Querdenker*) movement, which from summer 2020 on garnered significant media attention. However, it should be noted that none of the HCWs interviewed identified as members of this movement or reported having taken part in protests. Moreover, the COSMO survey found that at no time did more than around 15% of the population indicate that they were somewhat or very ready to join a protest against governmental measures, including communications measures.

3.4.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

Governmental pandemic management frameworks existing prior to the pandemic did recognise the existence of so-called "at-risk groups" (*Risikogruppen*) or "vulnerable groups" (*vulnerable Gruppen*). Examples given in the Pandemic Plan (part II) are the elderly, those with pre-existing chronic conditions, children, and pregnant women (2016, p. 51). As emphasized in the eleventh statement of the Coronavirus Expert Council and/or the *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy*, the fundamental approach has remained unchanged, and is to run a national "umbrella campaign" (*Dachkampagne*) supplemented by "sub-campaigns" (*Teilkampagne*) targeting specific locations and (vulnerable) population groups (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022, pp. 49-60). As emphasized in the eleventh statement of the Coronavirus Expert Council and/or the *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy*, the fundamental approach has remained unchanged: it is to run a national "umbrella campaign" (*Dachkampagne*) supplemented by "sub-campaigns" (*Teilkampagne*) targeting specific locations and population groups. However, at the beginning of the pandemic and during T1, specific health communication provisions or guidelines were not given on the federal level for specific categories of vulnerability, e.g., health vulnerability, economic vulnerability, social vulnerability, etc.

The German federal government's initial definition (at T1) of "at-risk groups" focused on factors that increased the chance of a severe progression of COVID-19 (Robert Koch-Institut, 2020a). Over the course of 2020 and 2021, official definitions of vulnerability expanded to encompass factors that increased the chance of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and included people working in health care and other front-line occupations (Robert Koch-Institut, 2021, Section 11). However, it should be noted that from the beginning of the pandemic onward, the broader set of governmental measures *outside* the domain of public health explicitly targeted a wide range of economically and socially vulnerable population groups: examples are bonus payments and tax relief for parents and especially single parents; helplines for people suffering from depression and women at risk of domestic violence; raises in minimum wage for nurses; digital learning platforms for students; expanded financial support for small businesses and freelancers; etc.

With regard specifically to health communication, over the course of the pandemic, the government gradually improved the level of guidance given on a federal level regarding how to plan "sub-

campaigns” (*Teilkampagne*) targeting specific vulnerable groups: for instance, in July 2021, RKI published a “General guidance for health officials on outreach and collaboration with marginalized populations during the COVID-19 pandemic” (Robert Koch-Institut, 2021b), defined as “people who are pushed to the margins of society by economic, social, geographic, or other societal structures [e.g., through] loss of resources, influence, and status”. It focuses especially on migrant-background and minority ethnic populations (which often see higher rates of poverty, precarity, and discrimination), defining concrete steps to be taken when planning interventions targeted at these groups. The *Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy* furthermore elaborated the distinction between the “umbrella campaign” and sub-campaigns, with the aim of reducing the chance of contradiction: the umbrella campaign should feature a small number of simple messages, understandable by (nearly) anyone, transmitted “at eye level” in multiple languages and along multiple channels while targeted sub-campaigns should be more diverse and specific, and should address target-group-specific needs, concerns, culture, values, language usage, etc. (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022, pp. 49-60).

Governmental communications officers working on the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels interviewed during the COVINFORM project gave several examples of successful targeted campaigns planned at these levels:

“We had a vaccination campaign in our federal state that also targeted people who do not speak German. Particularly in the social media area, with ads directed to groups that don't [usually] follow us. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“[...] In the area of vaccination ... we also chose a special path, and that included going into areas where people live closer together [...] Where many people live in cramped quarters, and also have jobs that have a lot to do with handicrafts and the outdoors, and are in contact with others [...] And these are the districts we specifically went to with our communications.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

“Well, of course we appealed by video, we had doctors from the Medical University of Mannheim UMM who made appeals for us, in different languages [...] We also printed banners in different languages.” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

“[...] In that respect, Mannheim was always very far ahead. As far as I can remember, we were even better than Stuttgart. We always said, ok, that's interesting in a city that is not quite 'easy' from a social perspective [e.g., in which there are numerous economically and socially vulnerable groups]. And that's actually how we measured our success, by the vaccination numbers..” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

Despite the best efforts of communications planners and practitioners alike, the *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies* offers an implicit (sometimes explicit) critique of the lack of attention given to certain vulnerable groups. For instance, it identifies migrant and migration-background populations as impacted by information deficits and cultural barriers to adherence to regulations and recommendations, which were not adequately addressed (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit, 2022, p. 98).

Governmental communications officers working on the state (Baden-Württemberg) and municipal (City of Mannheim) levels confirmed that over the course of the pandemic, working definitions of

“vulnerability” were continually expanded, and the need to target a wider range of groups with specific sub-campaigns became more clearly defined:

“[...] We also keep getting... kept getting requests saying: 'This group has been forgotten. You have forgotten the students. You have forgotten the children' or 'you have forgotten the doctors' or 'you have forgotten the nursing staff'. It's always... it's always a balancing act.” (WP7_SINUS_03, Government Communicator)

“ So this issue, what do young people actually do on the streets when pubs and discos are closed? That was a huge issue in the municipalities. [...]” (WP7_SINUS_04, Government Communicator)

A similar pattern can be observed in media. One journalist working at the regional (Baden-Württemberg) level confirmed that during the first phase of the pandemic, the media’s reporting focus was on health vulnerability, whereas later in the pandemic, social vulnerability came more into view:

“[...] But I think that our reporting was actually rather narrow at the beginning. It was more about elderly people and people with pre-existing conditions, and then, for example, people living in poverty, or refugees, that came a bit later. [...] And just the whole topic of the..., yes, the social effects came up. So then again, especially concerning schools, and then concerning certain groups of pupils who don't have three iPads and two academic parents sitting at home, that also came with great force in the local context. So at some point we also reported on this quite a lot.” (WP7_SINUS_01, Journalist)

3.5 Greece

The governmental crisis communication response of Greece has been structured on a top-down approach, similarly to the overall crisis management mechanism. The main actors of the communication activities were high level decision and policy makers such as the Prime Minister, Ministers (i.e., Minister of Health), General Secretary of Civil Protection and the main figure of the scientific committee, epidemiologist Sotiris Tsiodras, which overall is identified to be a good practice. In addition, the Greek response utilized both traditional and contemporary communication means and methods, albeit, emphasized strongly on daily press conferences. The main lessons learned include: disseminating clear, detailed information in easy-to-understand format and non-highly scientific language. The importance of acquiring and disseminating information in a transparent, constant and timely manner. Dissemination actors should be able to achieve trust-building with the message recipient (i.e., general public, vulnerable groups) in multiple languages utilizing both traditional and contemporary means of communication, whilst conduct frequent evaluation of effectiveness in order to allow for adjustments in dissemination and communication strategies. Measures ought to be coherent and communicated with simplicity and clarity, whereas, civil society actors and journalists should be engaged in the crisis management and risk communication process.

3.5.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

The socio-governmental system in Greece is a Presidential Parliamentary Republic. Prior to COVID-19 and until the outbreak of the pandemic, in terms of crisis management, key administrative figures of the Greek governance system are hierarchically presented, in accordance with their socio-political

status quo: The president of the Republic, the Prime Minister, Ministers in relevant to the crisis management system Ministries such as the Minister of Health, Ministry of Climate Crisis and Civil Protection and the General Secretariat for Civil Protection, and the Ministry of Citizen Protection. The overall crisis management in Greece, subsequently and in terms of risk communication, is identified as a centralized – top-down approach. The information dissemination was mainly conducted by the National Public Health Organization (EODY), which is part of the Ministry of Health, in cooperation with the Ministry of Citizen Protection and General Secretary of Civil Protection, supported by the Head of the Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases who acted as the main spokesperson and representative of the Greek Ministry of Health.

In addition, the Greek government established cooperation with national and international organizations such as Stavros Niarchos Foundation, IOM, Médecins Sans Frontière, WHO and UNHCR, in order to outsource the dissemination of COVID-19 related information, tailored within the framework of each beneficiary group such as vulnerable groups, which also include migrants and refugees.

Overall, the Greek crisis management and communication plan, was based on the influenza pandemic preparedness plan, created in 2005. This preparedness plan was subjected to immense revisions particularly due to evolving threats that emerged from influenza strains and was utilised as the foundation of the crisis management response in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic (Economou, Kaitelidou, Konstantakopoulou, & Vildiridi, 2021). Decision makers, policy and communication experts, would also incorporate successful mechanisms that stem from previous communication and dissemination efforts, particularly related to awareness and information campaigns regarding natural disasters such as earthquakes, wildfires and communicable infectious diseases such as Ebola, West Nile virus and Malaria. Concluding, similarly to most European countries, the Greek information dissemination campaign utilised both traditional and contemporary means of communication.

3.5.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The Greek crisis management response system in terms of risk communication, adopted a centralised top-down approach which included daily briefs via press conferences. These dissemination activities were mainly led by the former Secretary General for Civil Protection, then Deputy Minister for Civil Protection and Crisis Management and current Deputy Minister of National Defence, Nikos Hardalias and the Head of the Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases, Dr. Sotiris Tsiodras. During statistical press conferences COVID-19 related data would be communicated, particularly emphasizing the infection rates on a nationwide scope, based on the 5-scale colour system. In certain cases, these press conferences would also be supported by the Prime Minister of Greece, Kyriakos Mitsotakis (To Vima, 2020)³. At later phases, key officials such as the current Minister of Health (Athanasios Plevis), member of healthcare experts Gkikas Magiorkinis and Deputy Minister of Health, Mina Gaga, would also support governmental dissemination and communication efforts. On a regional and local level, governmental authorities would also participate in dissemination efforts, aiming to raise awareness in

³ <https://www.tovima.gr/2020/11/05/politics/koronoios-live-oi-anakoinoseis-mitsotaki-tsiodra-gia-nea-metra/>.

relation to hygiene practices, implemented measures and underlining the importance of vaccinations (Lampropoulou, 2021).

The Greek dissemination campaign was mainly led by the Ministry of Health and similarly to the majority of European healthcare information campaigns, in Greece, decision makers and communication experts aimed towards disseminating simplistic, bright, colourful infographics which raised awareness to important guidelines and personal hygiene practices such as social distancing, wearing masks and washing hands frequently and thoroughly. These communication activities predominantly targeted the general public as well as specific audiences such as students. At a later phase, the information dissemination campaign was also tailored to raise awareness in relation to COVID-19 vaccinations, thus, it would include information for both good hygiene practices and the vaccination campaign. These communication activities would also emphasize on both social and individual responsibility in relation to combating COVID-19, whereas, once vaccines were publicly available, communication would underline the importance of being vaccinated which would lead to a return to normality. The characteristics of the visual infographics can be identified in all COVID-19 pandemic phases.

As the pandemic progressed, communication efforts would be more targeted, even though the main dissemination officials would not radically change. The Ministry of Health, particularly at the third pandemic phase, emphasized on raising awareness on the vaccination mechanism which was conducted within the context of the National Vaccination Plan for COVID-19 (Emvolio.gov.gr, n.d.). The governmental communication strategy was also tailored in accordance with nationwide vaccination rates, epidemiological status quo and the relevant measures in place. Due to the rapidly changing information which related to COVID-19, some scientific experts would express differentiated or contradictory views in contrast to governmental policies, which would lead to confusion within the general public, negatively influencing citizen's attitudes towards COVID-19 measures and vaccines (To Vima, 2021).

The third pandemic phase observed the emergence of new COVID-19 messages which predominantly related to the benefits and procedure of vaccination, and information which clarified misinformation that revolved around vaccines. The dissemination activities mainly aimed at encouraging citizens to be vaccinated. The main actors involved in the COVID-19 and vaccination information campaign utilized both contemporary means such as social media, including hashtags such as #MenoumeSpiti, #MenoumeAsfaleis (We stay Home, We stay Safe) (Ladi, Angelou & Panagiotatou, 2021) and traditional means of information. The aforementioned governmental actors would assess the effectiveness of communication messages via analysis of public responses and raw data, which would also allow to tailor their responses (Naftemporiki, 2020). During the third phase, the Greek government would initiate "operation freedom" and also incorporate a holistic communication campaign utilizing traditional and contemporary means, create a dedicated website which included information about vaccination (www.emvolio.gov.gr). At this phase, the Prime Minister would also be highly engaged in the dissemination and communication efforts via press conferences and social media, highlighting the importance of vaccinations, measure compliance and individual responsibility (Poulakidakos, 2021), Tziouvas, 2021), (Papandoniou, 2021), (Ethnos, 2021).

The pandemic risk communication, according to our expert interviews, similarly to healthcare experts, was significantly challenging due to misinformation, constant tension and long working hours. Experts would cross-reference and examine carefully COVID-19 information prior to public dissemination,

while utilize official sources of information. Non-governmental dissemination experts would also present accessibility challenges:

“Distribution of news was very difficult. We didn’t always have access to the decision-making centres of the government. It wasn’t easy for us to learn in time and in a precise way the relevant information... The access to the decision-Making centres was problematic, because during the first months of the confinement, the ability to ask direct questions wasn’t available. Our questions were submitted in writing, which in my view, was the worse way in tackling the pandemic, in the level of communication policy. Skype sessions, etc., should have taken place, in order for everyone to ask questions. Technology offers many solutions.” (WP7_KEMEA_1).

“The amount of work that we had to face was huge because we had to follow all the developments and announcements coming from the official authorities such as the Ministry of Health, National Public Health Organization (EODY), World Health Organization, the ECDC and the official European authorities...We had to cross-check and document any other information that came to us from the special scientific committee established ad hoc by the government for the management of the pandemic, but also from the scientific community in general and the scientists in general who went public and expressed their opinion.” (WP7_KEMEA_2)

“I knew my sources were reliable and I was confident about it because I always talked to key officials such as high-ranking governmental officers, academics and people employed in the health sector for many years with significant experience and publicly acknowledged reliability.” (WP7_KEMEA_4)

In addition, according to experts, news ought to be interpreted in easier to understand terms for the general public: “The broadcasted news had to be explained to the public, because the sources were official channels, from specialized scientists, that needed some interpretation” (WP7_KEMEA_1).

Moreover, experts highlight the importance of providing detailed official information to combat misinformation and disinformation: “I believe that the authorities could have done a better job. If there was a more detailed official information regarding the pandemic, there wouldn’t have been any fake news.” (WP7_KEMEA_1). Communication experts also highlight how important was to address questions from the general public in relation to COVID-19 measures and guidelines:

“The people “bombaraded” us daily with hundreds of messages and questions relevant with the pandemic as for example regarding the imposed health protection measures usually asking for more information or clarifications. The volume of questions was huge every day which I think it was natural in this context of uncertainty that existed, especially at the beginning of the pandemic, during the first months when we didn't know much about this virus. This communication from the public was also intense later on, when the vaccination campaign was conveyed. People had many questions about the vaccines, possible side effects, etc. People needed constant information, there was widespread anxiety and concern. We constantly tried with great effort to answer as many issues as we could, through our daily responses and reports, posing people’s concerns to the scientists and the authorities and tried our best to provide answers wherever that was possible based upon

the official information and data sources and guidelines of international public health organizations” (WP7_KEMEA_2)

“With COVID-19, people were communicating with us daily with hundreds of messages mainly expressing their concern about the situation, they were asking for more information, there was a lot of confusion in the public about what they should do, what measures they should apply. (WP7_KEMEA_3)

According to Governmental dissemination experts, Greece similarly to other EU nations, was not prepared to handle COVID-19, nevertheless reacted swiftly and decisively, highlighting the positive impact of placing recognized key officials at the dissemination campaign:

“The truth is that we were not prepared for such an event of this large extent. I think that all countries and not only Greece were in a way caught by surprise with the pandemic outbreak and the very fast spread of COVID 19. Unfortunately, we have didn’t learn from the recent past and I am referring to the H1N1 influenza crisis in 2009-2011. Of course, I have to acknowledge that we recovered very quickly from the shock of the first weeks and the Greek government; it is true, reacted very quickly and promptly by immediately organizing its first moves. Decisions were made remarkably quickly...The daily public information routine provided by the government using broadly recognized scientific prestige personalities such as Professor Tsiodras as well as operational officials such as the Deputy Minister of Civil Protection Mr Hardalias, had a great impact on the public especially in the first months of the pandemic and until the first vaccines arrived in Greece. The informational campaign for the restriction of movement and the imposition of quarantine measures, the well-known “Stay at Home” campaign (Menoume Spiti), also had a great impact. All these worked very well in terms of communication in the sense that gave people a steady guideline of what to do and how to behave in the context of fear and uncertainty that prevailed in all of us.” (WP7_KEMEA_2)

Most, if not all, communication experts assess that governmental responses were effective, in which dissemination activities had an immense impact on the course of the pandemic management, whereas attribute confusion partially to some diverse views expressed publicly by scientists:

“There was a quick response from the authorities especially in the first phase of the pandemic. The campaigns worked satisfactorily, and convinced a large percentage of people to keep the measures and get vaccinated. In this, however, we journalists also played a very big role, all the media showed the messages and campaigns, all TV shows, sites, newspapers broadcasted daily all the messages of the authorities relevant to the protection of public health. A lot of space was given to the scientists to express their opinions, without political or partisan connotations. Our purpose was to inform the public correctly, what was happening in the rest of the countries in Europe and generally abroad, what the international organizations were saying, what were the directives that were in force. Greece followed the international standards and did not deviate from the guidelines of the World Health Organization. The measures that were applied abroad and mainly in the countries of Europe were also applied by Greece and in my opinion it was very correct.” (WP7_KEMEA_3)
“Once terrifying pressure on the health system began, where we had too many deaths every wee

k and admissions to the ICU, it was then when the decisions of the government started to be questioned and especially for the part of the prolonged lockdowns, how effective they were in the health protection and the terrible effect they had on people's lives, on the economy, on their psychology. The criticism was not so misplaced, but I don't think that at that stage anything else could have been done. Of course, this polyphony that was observed at that time between the scientists who appeared on TV channels and television shows, expressing their views that were often contradictory, created great confusion to the public" (WP7_KEMEA_3).

"The attitude of the government towards the pandemic was in a broad sense correct and effective. Health experts and the scientific community in general were given a lot of opportunities to share their opinions and contribute to the public dialogue and discussion about all relevant issues. And since I systematically followed what all international organizations like the ECDC and the EMA decided, as a country we were always on the same page. And I can tell you that this observed co-ordination with the rest of the European countries offered a strong sense of security." (WP7_KEMEA_4).

In relation to challenges and lessons learned, communication experts suggested that a mainstream source of information would be beneficial for dissemination experts whereas, misinformation was potentially the most important challenge:

"I would like to have a better update and information flow regarding actual numbers, statistics and data for example on cases and hospitalizations on a daily basis in all hospitals of the country. It was very tiring especially at the beginning to search and collect data from so many sources. I understand that now the National Health Organization (EODY) reports on these issues on a weekly basis according to the international guidelines but it would be easier for the health reporters and editors to have more data and information in relation to the pandemic publicly available from all relevant stakeholders like the Hellenic Medicines Organization (EOF) the National Health Organization (EODY), the Ministry of Health, Hospitals etc." (WP7_KEMEA_4).

"One of the biggest challenges in our line of work in relation to COVID-19, besides misinformation was to encounter how many silly things people actually believe in on 21st century, which are similar to medieval era way of thinking, even from educated people. At some point I tried to have a conversation with these people but observed that they won't accept other ideas so I merely gave up on them. They just don't want to listen. Most vaccine scepticists and deniers just claim that back "in the day" they didn't have so many vaccines or didn't get easily ill, bad pharma corporations that are after our money and similar claims, while "back in the day" one of two children would die before turning five years old and people would definitely die much easier. People continue to believe in conspiracy theories, which is a whole topic and even taught in universities." (WP7_KEMEA_5).

In terms of public reactions to the crisis management and its changes during the first pandemic phase, widespread fear dominated and influenced the general public, hence limited reactions can be observed, even though non-pharmaceutical interventions such as social isolation were an unprecedented phenomenon for the Greek society. At later phases, particularly as of the second

lockdown, the general public had elevated awareness in relation to COVID-19 and governmental responses, thus, as a coping mechanism the public would generate and disseminate memes through social media. Memes, similarly to most European States, would function as a coping mechanism to express satire, humour and in certain cases anger as well as frustration towards contemporary phenomena of the daily life. The general public in Greece would mainly disseminate memes that related to criticizing the cost and effectiveness of masks, social behaviour during the pandemic and phenomena such as essential item hoarding (i.e. toilet paper), daily product price increase and criticism towards governmental measures which would address vaccinated and unvaccinated citizens.

3.5.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The Information campaign within the context of the Greek crisis communication would emphasize on vulnerable populations, particularly during the second and third phase, as the interpretation of vulnerability evolved accordingly to the knowledge of COVID-19 and the subsequent negative health, socio-economic, cultural and legal impact. The COVID-19 dissemination governmental mechanism would tailor and shape messages for vaccination and vulnerable groups such as elderly, pregnant women and children. Communication activities conducted by the General Secretariat of Civil Protection would also include guidelines in multiple languages such as French, English, Albanian, Arabic, Farsi and Russian among other languages, as well as establish a helpline (1135) and share informational TV spots and videos (General Secretariat of Civil Protection, n.d.). Press briefings of governmental officials would also be broadcasted in sign language, whereas the Ministry of Health launched a COVID-19 campaign, dedicated to the Long COVID-19 syndrome and subsequent consequences (Ministry of Health, 2022). This campaign mainly targeted vulnerable groups such as children, pregnant women and the general public, elaborating on long-term effects on the public health of citizens.

In addition, a collaborative campaign between Stanford University School of Medicine and the Institute of Preventive Medicine, Environmental and Occupational Health (Prolepsis) would disseminate short messages and videos via Facebook, focusing on Roma communities, Western communities with Muslim populations, teenagers, young individuals. This campaign included journalists, pharmacists, actors, athletes, nurses, doctors and university professors who disseminated information relating to COVID-19 vaccination. In addition, the United Nations Refugee Agency would also be engaged in dissemination activities on official website which informed refugees on means and methods to acquire vaccination and information relevant about vaccines (The UN Refugee Agency, 2022).

According to our communication experts, some vulnerable groups would have difficulty on following with the developments of the pandemic due to lack of faith towards authorities, which with the exception of educational and social marginalization challenges, could potentially explain lack of measure compliance and decreased vaccination rates:

“Lots of vulnerable groups, especially Roma and the lower economic layers of the society had a difficulty in following how the pandemic escalated. This has to do with the society in our country, because groups that live marginalised, like Roma, usually do not show the same faith to the authorities, so there was a genuine difficulty in letting them know what was going on, in order for them to abide the law.” (WP7_KEMEA_1).

In some cases, however, it is evident that additional emphasis should be placed upon vulnerable groups, in relation to raising awareness, while experts suggest that certain vulnerable groups face more imminent challenges which prioritize over COVID-19:

“Now specifically for vulnerable groups, no, I cannot say that there was any specific care from the media I work for. We just republished the public health authorities and the government messages mainly concerning the vaccination information campaigns and the implemented measures that were published in many languages for immigrants and also the TV spots and videos about the protection measures for the elderly and vulnerable groups. Everything that existed at a central level, was also published on the site as well. From time to time we also made some reports specifically about how important it is to vaccinate everyone, especially the elderly and those with health problems, more as an extra aid to the efforts of the authorities. In any case though, everything was published with data confirmed by scientists, but we did not develop any additional or specific strategy” (WP7_KEMEA_3).

“Authorities and news outlet entities did their best in reaching vulnerable groups but I am not certain what else could have been done to improve their approaches. For example, it is rather difficult to explain how substance addicts and homeless people might be in danger from COVID-19 when they have other, significant and more direct risks in their daily lives.” (WP7_KEMEA_5).

To conclude, crisis response mechanism from the pandemic outbreak was orientated towards the general population and vulnerable groups, whereas as more information was acquired in relation to the negative consequences and impacts of COVID-19, the Greek response mechanism conducted tailored communication activities, particularly emphasizing on the vaccination information awareness campaign. The Greek government took into account vulnerable groups such as the elderly from the beginning of the pandemic and waged the communication campaign in both contemporary and traditional communications platforms, whilst emphasized on daily press briefings due to the number of citizens who use the TV as their main source of information. During these press releases, a communication expert was employed who would utilize the sign language for citizens that have physical vulnerabilities. Communication activities would be tailored to the specific characteristics of vulnerable and marginalized groups such as the Roma community, addressing their communication needs, nevertheless, based on this report there is still room for improvement. A recommended practice would entail the active engagement of municipalities and regional administration agencies in conducting information awareness activities, while in direct communication with minority group representatives. The governmental crisis management could also utilize Law Enforcement Agents, who are skilled and trained on negotiations and have pre-established communication networks with marginalized groups. Moreover, according to our expert interviews, even though homeless citizens were included as target groups in the governmental communication activities, they would often not pay too much attention to COVID-19 related risks or subsequent communication activities, which would be an obstacle to communication experts, due to the fact that substance addicted and homeless citizens would prioritize other challenges that they face on a daily basis.

3.6 Italy

3.6.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

Italy is a democratic parliamentary Republic with a three-way division of power. Executive power is exercised by the Council of Ministers, legislative power is vested primarily by the Parliament, and the judiciary power is independent of the executive and legislative branches. The State has powers of control - subjected to constitutional limitations - over 15 ordinary regions and 4 regions and 2 provinces with special autonomy. The regional government is composed by the regional council that has the power to pass laws and issue administrative regulations, the regional committee with executive power and the president of the regional committee. The legislative powers of regions are limited by the Constitution; in particular, they cannot conflict with national interests. The regions can also enact legislation necessary in order to enforce state laws when the latter contain the necessary provisions. The state has powers of control over the regions.

Italy has a “Servizio Sanitario Nazionale” (SSN) [National Health Plan, NHS], which provides universal coverage largely free of charge according to the 32° article of the Italian Constitution. The SSN is decentralized and is based on three levels: State, region and local boards.

The Communication strategy to adopt during a crisis was included in The “Piano nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale” [National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan, 2006], drawn up according to the 2005 WHO guidelines.

The Ministry of Health is supported by several specialized government agencies, such as The National Institute of Health (ISS), The National Agency for Regional Health Services (AGENAS), National Center for Disease Prevention and Control (CCM), National Institute for Scientific Research (IRCS) and National Authority for Pharmaceutical Regulation (AIFA).

3.6.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

Communication on Covid-19 played an informative and service role in making the characteristics of the virus known and in indicating precautions to avoid contagion. In the first months, the adoption of an emergency communication aimed at protecting the health and lives of people against an imminent and poorly known danger prevailed. It was characterized by strategies aimed primarily at guiding people towards preventive behaviours by promoting shared and participated actions with the community.

The topic of the virus was in the Government's agenda for some time following the WHO declaration on January 30, 2020, of a public health emergency of international concern due to the coronavirus outbreak in China. The following day, January 31, the Italian Government, considering the particularly widespread nature of the epidemic, declared a state of emergency and implemented the first measures to contain the contagion throughout the country (Faccioli et al., 2020).

As mentioned in D7.1, in February 2020, two campaigns promoted by the Ministry of Health were implemented, with the aim of informing citizens of the basic precautions to follow to defend themselves from the virus, which are hand washing, how to contain sneezing, avoid contact of hands with face, nose and mouth. In both campaigns, there was also an explicit call to consult the website of the Ministry of Health to get more detailed information.

In February 2020, the Ministry of Health Published the “Piano Nazionale in risposta a un’eventuale emergenza pandemica da COVID-19” [National Health Plan in response to a possible COVID-19

pandemic emergency] without specifically mentioning communication. Later on, other two documents have been published and have replaced the previous influenza pandemic plans: “Prevenzione e risposta a COVID-19: evoluzione della strategia e pianificazione nella fase di transizione per il periodo autunno-invernale” [Prevention and response to COVID-19: evolving strategy and planning in the transition phase for the autumn-winter period] and “Piano strategico-operativo nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale (PanFlu) 2021-2023” [National Strategic-Operational Plan for Pandemic Influenza Preparedness and Response (PanFlu) 2021-2023]. The first one refers to the second pandemic phase, while the last is valid from the end of the state of emergency (31st of March 2022).

The Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) [National Institute of Health] was among the first to establish relations with international organisations, driven by the intention to develop a communication plan focused on prevention and management of health emergencies, which was then referred to by media, newspapers and public health stakeholders.

ISS provides research results, surveillance data and technical advice in the field of public health to the Ministry of Health, the National Health Service and Regional Councils, as well as to Italian citizens and residents. Its work focuses on disease prevention, promotion of healthy behaviours, treatment of chronic diseases and quality and safety control of health technologies. In terms of information dissemination, ISS has a website and social media accounts on YouTube and Twitter. It also provides information through a knowledge management platform (ISS Salute) and an online magazine (Epicentro).

Since 28 February 2020, ISS coordinated a surveillance system that integrated at individual level the microbiological and epidemiological data provided by the Regions and Autonomous Provinces (PAs) and the ISS National Reference Laboratory for SARS-CoV-2. On a daily basis, a dedicated infographic was provided, with graphs, maps and tables, a description of the spread in time and space of the Covid-19 epidemic in Italy and a description of the characteristics of the people affected. Its press office provided daily support to ISS researchers and staff in their interactions with the media. Its web page and social channels were constantly updated with close-ups, focuses, news, events and videos. A special Covid-19 section was also created with up-to-date information on virus variants, vaccines, general information, and relevant documents, with special attention to FAQs and the fight against fake news.

The information produced by ISS was followed and amplified by the main health organisations and the newspapers they referred to, which in turn promoted information, recommendations and guidelines. The *Quotidiano Sanità* (Health Newspaper), for instance, in agreement with the ISS, collected the indications in daily newsletters sent every evening to the mailing list of about five hundred thousand health workers, in order to promote a maximum and constant dissemination.

According to Faccioli et al. (2020), during the early months of pandemic, the communication campaigns, carried out by the Ministry of Health in collaboration with several institutions, were shared with an orientation towards effectiveness, rather than promotion of the image of individual ministries. The first campaign started in March 11, at the beginning of the lockdown, and was promoted by the Council of Ministers – Department of Sport. The message focused on the need to stay at home, to respect the rules, but also to feel united in playing the same game. The call to action was addressed to different audiences (young people, students, workers, vulnerable categories including the sick and

elderly) through communication strategies designed to ensure that all citizens could feel adequately involved.

In this phase, the administrations tried to adapt to the new scenario by introducing a mix of languages and styles of communication in their releases, at times innovative with respect to the usual top-down and paternalistic clichés. In this process, the use of social platforms became central as a channel of integration and support to other means of communication to "reconnect" institutions with citizens.

As mentioned in D7.1, in Italy there was a formal communication strategy adopted to communicate about the pandemic, however it was not made explicit in an official document by the Italian Government during the period of the first wave (February-May 2020).

In this phase, the communication strategy was based on several elements:

- Communication about the content of the government's measures regarding the containment of the epidemic (state of emergency, lockdown, controls at borders, etc.) was provided directly by the Italian Prime Minister to citizens, businesses and institutions through press conferences widely attended by the media and broadcasted live to the population (via traditional and social media);
- A series of communication campaigns by the Presidency of the Council of Ministers (PCM) included, in addition to television and radio spots, a plurality of initiatives: Apps, dossiers and information materials diversified according to the public, they offered telephone numbers, infographics and pages of institutional websites dedicated to Covid-19 and constantly updated;
- The evolution of the epidemic through the main data was communicated via a daily press conference (since May it became weekly) by the Civil Protection together with the most important national health authorities: the Ministry of Health (MOH), the ISS and the Technical Scientific Committee (CTS). Since the beginning of the health emergency, data on the evolution of the pandemic were also made available by the Ministry of Health and the Civil Protection in a dedicated website that was realized with a layout very similar to the one provided by John Hopkins University for the Global Pandemic data. The website was updated daily, and data were publicly available.

The ISS - weekly provided detailed information on the evolution of the epidemic (Weekly Surveillance Bulletin- Epidemic Covid-19). In particular, the surveillance Bulletin provided the communication and commentary of the following data: the number of infections according to gender, age, region of residence, clinical status at the time of diagnosis; the number of infections among health workers; the transmission index R_t (daily punctual and interval estimation); the number of diagnostic tests; the number of deaths according to the main demographic characteristics; the number of hospitalizations and recoveries. Data assumed a central role in communication, both in informing citizens about the evolution of the epidemic and in explaining government measures and their effects in dealing with it.

As mentioned in D7.1, during the transition phase a specific communication strategy was developed. It is explained in the document *"Prevention and response to COVID-19: evolution of strategy and planning in the transition phase for the autumn-winter season"* published by the MOH and ISS, in which the 8 strategic pillars identified by the WHO for the response to COVID-19 in the second phase for the autumn-winter (2020-2021) season were taken as reference. The second of these pillars related to the risk communication plan and the involvement of the population.

According to the document, it was crucial to conduct constant, coherent and coordinated communication with the other institutions, in order to develop trust in the public and represent a constant, authoritative and reliable reference. In ISS, in particular, the Risk Communication and Community Engagement (RCCE) coordination mechanism started in the first emergency phase with the establishment of the Communication Group (Press Office, Scientific Communication Unit with the integration of some reference experts) and continued to be active during the pandemic.

The plan designed a series of initiatives:

- constant production of content aimed at increasing population awareness and at contrasting fake news through the main institutional channels (press releases, web sites and social media, infographics and videos);
- support for the dissemination of surveillance data and of information on the epidemiological situation through social channels and the web;
- management of interviews and the identification of institutional spokes-people;
- communication actions aimed at prevention for vulnerable population groups;
- activation of inter-institutional synergies to promote stakeholder training;
- dissemination of technical content and related updates on the management of this phase of the emergency to stakeholders (school, supermarkets, etc.);
- adaptation of the strategy and possible enhancement of activities on social channels;

Several campaigns were developed dealing with very different topics: the campaign promoted by the Ministry of Health and National Statistical Institute (ISTAT) to inform citizens about the serological survey and its importance; the campaign promoted by the Department for Technological Innovation and Digitization to inform about the usefulness of the *Immuni app* for tracking contacts of positive cases and promote its use; the campaign on child mistreatment, which increased significantly during lockdown, to raise awareness and inform the public about everyday violence. The campaign for the return to school, promoted by the Ministry of Education, reassured students and families about the security measures adopted.

As mentioned in D7.1, an important campaign was established on April 4, 2020 by the decree of the Undersecretary of State with responsibility for Information and Publishing: the "Monitoring Unit for countering the spread of fake news related to Covid-19 on the web and social networks".

It planned actions to check the contents scattered in different institutional sites, to realize distance-training courses for public communicators, to appoint a task force on data science and online disinformation.

As mentioned in D7.1, the evolution of the communication strategy, defined by the Italian government to cope with the spread of COVID-19 followed the pandemic trend and also the changes in the national and international political context. During the period from March 2021 to September 2022, the major break with the past waves was the appointment of Mario Draghi as President of the Council of Ministers. This change in the Italian government structure led to a series of modifications both in the people responsible for developing the communication strategies, plans, practices and in the communication organization itself, with different communication approaches adopted by the two Presidents of the Council of Ministers over the COVID-19 pandemic: "Conte's emotional and massive communication" versus "Draghi's informative and discreet style of communication" (Amoretti, Fittipaldi, and Santaniello, 2021).

As noted in Ventura (2022), Giuseppe Conte organised thirty press conferences from late January to December 2020 to manage the pandemic, he gave fifty-one interviews for the main national newspapers, while using Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to officially communicate the new measures; Mario Draghi, instead, did not have any social media account, held ten press conferences from March to November 2021 and did not release any press interviews over 2021.

As mentioned in D7.1, the most important message transmitted by the government from March 2021 concerned the importance of vaccination of the population as a whole to defeat the pandemic. On 13th March 2021, The Extraordinary Commissioner Plan was launched in order to perform the national vaccination campaign through three main operational tracks, i.e., provision and supply, continuing monitoring, and widespread distribution. Also, as done before by the Ministry of Health for data on the pandemic trend (i.e., about new contagions, recoveries, and deaths), that were weekly updated, information on vaccination were made available online by the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, the Unit for the Completion of the Vaccination Campaign, and the Ministry of Health.

The journalists interviewed as experts lamented that at the beginning of the pandemic there was a lack of transparency on the data provided by the Government: *“So, certainly during the first phase...there was a lack of transparency.”* Therefore, several Journalists from the major national newspaper put the Government under pressure to publish more data, for example

“[...] Italians needed information, they wanted to know how things were going. The first few days and weeks there was the famous bulletin, then a fairly effective monitoring was born. However, the National Institute of Health, which did not publish, did not publish the report, published a summary of about fifteen lines. [...] And I have to say that eventually the government, the ministry decided to publish the whole report and it started coming out every week. Now it's always published, which in my opinion is in emergency, institutions have to give transparency, also because if you give less transparency, first the newspapers can't do information well, but it's the users themselves, the end citizens who don't believe it, they don't trust” [J_UCSC SAPIENZA_01].

Another journalist during the expert interviews stressed that although in the first period of the pandemic the governmental communication was transparent, it lacked to clearly explain to the citizens the rules that they had to respect during the lockdown, for instance

“[the communication]It was very poor in terms of explanations [...]. I must say that you couldn't really understand anything. That is, they made very intricate rules, very conditioned by the fact that the government was, let's say, composed of various political forces, by the need to have to go to the (regional) governors.” [J_UCSC SAPIENZA_02].

“I think the mistake was not creating exactly what, for example, in the United States is the crisis committee. That is, at one point too many people were talking and too many people were showing that they were making decisions.” [J_UCSC SAPIENZA_02].

Interestingly, during the expert interviews all the journalist affirmed that to prevent disinformation they always referred to the primary source (e.g. the Ministry of Health, the Government, the PM, the ISS, the CTS), without using secondary sources e.g.

“The first thing is to verify the sources. The second thing is to try to clarify the things you say, and whether the things you say are in any way reliable. That is the only sense. That is what mediation is all about.” [J_UCSC SAPIENZA_03]

From the expert interviews it emerged that more efforts could have been made to fight disinformation. A Governmental communicator stated that

“Here, we would need less anxiety and more control. I think the first thing about greater control is to eliminate fake news. Fake news has raised, has created a lot of problems, especially in people who are not able to judge. But they have been deliberately spread. There are some people who also work to destabilize.”

The expert additionally stressed that the institutions need to vigilate to have an “ethic” communication: *“So I think institutions have to work so that there is ethics in communication as well and the citizen is properly informed”* [GC_UCSC SAPIENZA_01]. At the Governmental level there was a continuous effort to prevent the circulation of fake news. One of the Expert stressed that in order to prevent disinformation the Government (headed by Draghi) based its communication strategy on certified information (scientifically certified) and in providing the maximum amount of data to the population.

“The relevant point is that all government communication aimed to release information as certified as possible, that is, with the characteristic of reliability. And in a very noisy environment, with a lot of rumours, in some cases the fake news was clearly detectable, the ones that especially were proposed on the web, in some cases these were quite disguised, because in short you have maybe professors, even university professors, who suddenly become crowd draggers, there is a problem, this is a criticality. Then one solution, [...] was to give regular news on the progress of the pandemic, on the progress of vaccination with reference to the various territories, so, for example, every Friday, there was an appointment in the form of the press conference held by Brusaferrò, by Rezza, and then, when a certain amount of progress was made, Locatelli and Magrini also joined in. These four figures have become familiar figures in the homes of Italians.” [GC_UCSC SAPIENZA_02]

To identify the right communication approach is not an easy task, at least for two reasons: the present comparison concerns two different stages of the pandemic and two different aims of the government strategy and practice.

Firstly, the different register used by Draghi’s government directly depended on the progressive improvement in the health emergency thanks to the very positive results of the vaccination campaign and the consequent gradual weakening of the virus itself. This led to a difference in governments’ aims. Indeed, as mentioned in D7.1, over the first phases, Conte’s major purpose was to inform citizens about a new virus widespread while reducing the contagion risk and starting promoting the vaccine as the best solution for everybody. In the following phases, instead, when citizens were exhausted because of the past lockdowns and worried about new closures, Draghi essentially pointed at the vaccination campaign as a prompt and secure reply. This probably required different approaches and different communication channels. Also, just during the improvement in the COVID-19 emergency (with a strong reduction in deaths as well as in infected people requiring health assistance), other

political issues emerged over the 2022, with the war erupted between Russia and Ukraine in February as the main one, so that the attention of the media shifted from health to economic and social issues.

This may explain why many studies investigating communication about the first phase of the pandemic have been proliferating, while there is a shortage of works on the following stages' communication trend, at least among those published so far.

The study of Sfardini (2020) has identified some shortcoming in the management of the communication of the Italian emergency. Firstly, because there were multiple actors representing institutional sources, giving contrasting messages to the citizens. Secondly, the institutional body witnessed a crisis of credibility especially during phase 1. This loss of trust could be assessed by the trend of the television audience of the Civil Protection bulletin. The daily bulletin of the Civil Protection became the daily appointment with the tragic account of the contagions and deaths in the first two months of the pandemic. At the end of the first phase, the bulletin lost audience, because citizens were discouraged by the lack of understanding of data collected.

A survey by *Observe Science in Society*, shows that Italians' opinion of emergency communication was not positive. Nearly one Italian out of three judges the government's communication to be barely sufficient, while 17% judges it to be poor. According to the *Observe* sample, the communication of municipalities is unclear and ineffective, while the opinion is more positive for the Italian National Institute of Health and the Civil Protection. On the other hand, public opinion seems rather divided on the evaluation of the communication activities of "scientists" and "experts". In fact, almost one Italian out of two believes that the diversity of opinions given by experts in their interventions has generated confusion (48%) (Castellin & Palano, 2020). The opinion that experts' interventions have created confusion increases further in the second wave of the survey realized by *Observe Science in Society* during the second wave: 62% of citizens believe that experts' interventions have created confusion, while the quota of those who consider their interventions in the media effective has dropped below 20% (*Observe Science in Society* 2021).

Finally, using the data of the survey of *Observe Science in Society* collected during the first wave, Saracino (2020), adopted a two-step cluster analysis to summarize in three types of profiles the relationship of Italian citizens with information and their trust in the sources, the judgment on the work and role of science and scientific experts at the beginning of April 2020. 43% of Italians fall into the first group: they get their information primarily through television news and institutional web channels and trust mostly the indications coming from these sources. They judge positively both the work and the communication of major institutions and the communicative role of scientific experts convinced that effective solutions will come from science in a short time. This group includes mainly young people. 35% of Italians appear substantially disoriented: they follow a mix of information sources (media, relatives and friends), but tend to uncertain on how to judge either the work or the quality of communication by scientists. The multiplicity of opinions given by experts in public confuse them. This group includes citizens with low educational qualifications.

Finally, 22% of the interviewed fall into a group with predominantly negative judgements about both the work and the communication of scientists. They are people more inclined to use social networks and relatives or friends as a privileged source of information and to rely on them also for practical indications to reduce the risk of infection. This group is sceptical about the ability of experts to communicate effectively and about the possibility that solutions against Coronavirus will come from science.

3.6.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

As mentioned in D7.1, the Ministry of Health's webpage dedicated to Covid-19 devotes specific sections to three population groups: the elderly and frail, women, and children.

Elderly and their caregivers. The ISS in collaboration with the National Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work (Inail) and the Center for Promotion and Development of Geriatric Care (Cepsag) created and published the booklet "Practical Guide for Caregivers of the Elderly". The booklet was published in several languages to facilitate understanding by caregivers often of foreign origin, it aimed to help all those in charge of daily care for the elderly, deepening the knowledge on Covid-19 and behaviours to be followed at home and outside to protect their own health and that of the person assisted. The Ministry of Health edited a web page to inform about Covid-19 with particular relevance to frail older people. The page of the Ministry advertised a toll-free number for over 65 promoted by Senior Italia FederAnziani, WINDTRE and SIPEM SoS Federazione.

Women victims of domestic violence. The call to stay at home turned into a danger for women living in a condition of oppression and lack of freedom since their home, far from being a place of safety and protection, became a risk for violence and fear. For that, they were given anti-violence centre phone numbers they could refer to when in need. Moreover, women were offered housing solutions and opportunities thanks to the Department for Equal Opportunities which promoted the campaign *Libera puoi* [Free You Can].

In order to strengthen the information and to provide further guidance on how to ask for help and report domestic violence safely, a memorandum of understanding was signed between the Minister for Equal Opportunities and the Family and the Federation of Pharmacists Orders, Federfarma and Assofarm. For this purpose, informative guidelines were prepared and made available in pharmacies. In addition, the dissemination of the anti-violence hotline 1522, active 24 hours a day, was strengthened. The information in the pharmacies supported the anti-violence centres, the number and the App 1522.

Children and Teenagers. At the Department for Equal Opportunities and the Family of the Presidency of Council of Ministers there is a National Observatory for Childhood and Adolescence that established a Covid-19 Emergency Group. This group produced a report: Contrasting the impact of pandemic on children and adolescents. The Agency for Childhood and Adolescence (AGIA), tailored the decalogue of rules to be followed by the general population to avoid the spread of the contagion with a language suitable for children, both in Italian and in English. In the portal of the Ministry of Education was created a site containing all the references and useful tools for students and teachers for spreading correct information and useful links.

Youth. At the local level, Regions and Municipalities promoted awareness campaigns addressed to young people. For example, Umbria region produced a short video. Communication on Covid-19 played an informative and service role in making the characteristics of the virus known and in indicating precautions to avoid contagion. In the first months, the adoption of an emergency communication aimed at protecting the health and lives of people against an imminent and poorly known danger prevailed. It was characterized by strategies aimed primarily at guiding people towards preventive behaviours by promoting shared and participated actions with the community.

As mentioned in D7.1, other public and private organisations developed a communication strategy about the COVID-19 Pandemic:

- The National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities (ANFFAS Nazionale) carried out several initiatives addressed to people with disabilities. Its Crisis Unit Covid-19 produced a document entitled "Epidemic emergencies in residential facilities for people with disabilities" with the primary objective to provide the appropriate knowledge and health regulations issued by national, regional and local authorities, able to ensure appropriate management of residential facilities in situations of epidemic emergency. The Crisis Unit published also a text on Coronavirus and intellectual disabilities with some suggestions to families and caregivers on how to manage information on the pandemic and the adoption of preventive behaviours as well as on how to reduce stress.
- Other Professional Associations and Scientific Societies dedicated pages on their websites with a Covid-19 focus, reporting guidelines shared with the ISS and the WHO. An example for that was the Italian Federation of Family Physicians (FIMMG), which divulged press releases, articles, radio and TV interviews on the Coronavirus, with a focus on both health workers (Protocol for Medical Practices for the post-emergency management, home care for patients with Covid-19 presenting with mild symptoms and management of their contacts) and a wider audience not strictly related to the health world.
- The Federazione Nazionale Ordine Professioni Infermieristiche (FNOPI) [National Federation of Nursing Professions] launched the #NOICONGLIINFERMIERI campaign in support of the families of nurses who lost their lives during the Covid-19 emergency, supported in turn by "Barilla - Mulino Bianco" which undertook to donate the proceeds from the sale of one of its products to the FNOPI Solidarity Fund until it reached 2 million euros, all sponsored through TV commercials and web platforms.
- The Federazione Nazionale degli Ordini dei Medici Chirurghi e degli Odontoiatri (FNOMCeO) [National Federation of the Orders of Surgeons and Dentists] set up a special Covid-19 page with press releases and information to raise awareness about the doctors who died during the pandemic, while Association of pharmaceutical companies (Farmindustria) set up the campaign "#Covid19: noi non ci fermiamo - Assistenza Medica" [#Covid19: we don't stop - Medical Assistance] to support doctors, health workers and researchers in the front line against Covid19.

3.7 Portugal

3.7.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

Portugal operates as a parliamentary democracy with a representative democratic republican structure. The head of the government is the Prime Minister, and the President of the Republic is the head of state. The government holds the responsibility of formulating and implementing national policies while the Directorate-General of Health (DGS) serves as Portugal's national public health agency. The main provider of healthcare services is the National Health Service (SNS). Accordingly, the government assigned the development of the plan against COVID-19 to the Health Authorities. We didn't find comprehensive or specific governmental communication plans or strategies prior to COVID-19 in a crisis context. What is worth mentioning is that, before COVID-19, DGS developed a National

Contingency Plan against the Influenza Pandemic (2007) - [“Pandemia de Gripe: Plano de Contingência Nacional do Sector da Saúde para a Pandemia de Gripe”](#). The Specific Communication Plan was part of this document and its general lines were to address the problem directly and transparently; avoid merely informative and reactive communication; disseminate transparent and accurate information at the right times to build trust; coordinate communicational approach by the various entities to minimize the anxiety and fear generated by public misperceptions of risk.

3.7.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The National Contingency Plan for SARS-CoV-2 Infection served as the primary document that guided crisis management (DGS, 2020). Despite health communication being, formally, a responsibility of the DGS, both the Government and the DGS held public and daily press conferences. In March 2020, the Government launched a [website](#) to present all relevant information to contain the virus. An app “Stayaway COVID” was also launched but failed. At the beginning of the pandemic, the Prime Minister communicated with the population mostly via press conferences aired on open television channels, with the information then summarized and provided in a written format.

Initially, the Minister of Health and the DGS communicated with the general population via daily press conferences also aired on television, and the videos were then uploaded to the [websites](#) and [YouTube channels](#). This way, the number of new COVID-19 cases, deaths and active cases were reported daily. This information was then converted into a brochure. In addition, the DGS and the Ministry of Health made available dozens of leaflets containing instructions on best practices and sanitary procedures for protection, prevention, and disinfection, customized for the various sectors of activity. Mental and occupational health was not forgotten either, with some leaflets also focused on best practices in lockdown, both for parents, children, and adults in telecommuting situations.

In the beginning, the main documents developed by the Ministry of Health and DGS were:

- [“Guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception”](#) (DGS, March 2020): a risk communication plan that was launched, but it was never pursued or applied by the responsible health authorities. These principles were to be a tool to reinforce DGS’s crisis communication strategy for the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak and customise the communicated information to people's perceptions of risk concerning the Coronavirus and hazard template. Dealing correctly with uncertainty is one of the most relevant points in this plan. However, uncertainty was dealt with poorly since the beginning of the pandemic. The document offers a checklist that summarizes the basic principles of risk communication in a crisis context.
- [National Plan of Preparation and Response for Disease of the New Coronavirus \(COVID-19\)](#) (DGS, March 2020): containing guidelines for the Covid-19 response and the introduction of a communication plan, which was not implemented successfully; “The communication plan aims to ensure an effective information flow in the context the outbreak of COVID-19, according to the level of risk and the target audience. It is structured around three strategic axes: internal communication, external communication and social mobilisation”.

Later, another document was developed:

- [Health Plan for the Autumn-Winter 2020-21](#) (DGS, September 2020): a plan containing a section that underlines the importance of the coordination and communication structure;

“The operationalization of communication will be achieved by carrying out different actions to promote health literacy, focusing on major key issues in the adequacy of prevention and control measures (...). The communication approach will have to consider and adopt strategies to understand what motivates behaviour and facilitates the adoption of healthy behaviours that protect health, thus adapting the channels, methods and means to be used”.

In November 2020, the government nominated a task force for the elaboration of the "Vaccination Plan against COVID-19 in Portugal". In March 2021, national newspapers reported that the Government had appointed a task force of behavioural scientists to advise the Government until the end of 2021, conducting studies and presenting documents (Expresso, 2021). This team was requested by António Costa after a meeting where the integration and development of scientific work were advised. The integration of the National Civil Protection Authority within the Ministry of Internal Administration in September 2021 was a change in the allocation of responsibilities for crisis management, seen as a move to strengthen the government's response (Government of Portugal, 2021). Throughout the pandemic, the country had Marta Temido as Minister of Health, and Graça Freitas as Director of the DGS. In the end, Marta Temido left their position and was replaced, and Graça Freitas left for normal retirement. Besides these alterations, there were no other significant changes in the main responsible institutions and actors for crisis response/communication. Overall, government organisations continued without developing a COVID-19 communication plan and these actions continued to be assigned to the Health Authorities. In terms of communication by the government itself, there were moments when the President of the Republic and the Prime Minister held citizens responsible for not spreading the virus and asked for discipline (Diário de Notícias, 2021). In September 2021, this view was reinforced by the Prime Minister, stating that the pandemic was not over and asking for individual accountability. In December 2021, they both praised the behaviour of non-transmissibility as a “national unity effort” (Público, 2021). Regarding the evolution of communication by the health authorities, communication began with daily conferences reporting the main numbers and then these data began to be communicated via leaflets, with conferences becoming more occasional.

Concerning the role of other organizations, there were communication plans and practices published by organizations like Ordem dos Psicólogos Portugueses - OPP (Portuguese Psychologists Association), Ordem dos Médicos (Portuguese Medical Association), and the Autoridade para as Condições de Trabalho - ACT (Working Conditions Authority).

To fight the misinformation problem, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs translated a [UNESCO document that aims to combat misinformation](#). When asked about the misinformation problem, the Minister of State and of the Presidency defended that the Government has made [“every possible effort of transparency of information, regular communication and transmission of the measures”](#) in the fight against COVID-19, stating that it is a shared responsibility with the media to combat the misinformation. Additionally, [DGS formed a partnership with Jornal O Polígrafo](#) – an online fact-checking journal. All fact-checks published by “O Polígrafo” on the pandemic have been subject to prior scientific validation by a specialist appointed by the DGS. Beyond this partnership, the Ministry of Health and the DGS created a [website](#) where they provided all the information regarding COVID-19 and Diário de Notícias, one of Portugal's oldest newspapers, returned to the daily print edition. In August 2020, the OPP had already released a report on the topic, including psychologists’ role. It seems that most of the actions aimed at curbing disinformation were taken before March 2021. Throughout

the pandemic, journalists and government communicators had an important role in the fight against fake news and misinformation:

“We spent our days confirming whether the information was true or false, and we were doing a job of almost disproving social media, false information that created social alarm. That was exhausting because we could not always get the answers from official entities and sources quickly enough, and social media networks move at a speed that we could not keep up with.” (J_2)

“Our group was careful and would appear publicly in the sense of correcting and informing properly on a certain subject where some kind of misinformation was occurring” (GC_3)

In general, leadership in health organisations in Portugal follows a very hierarchical model that does not truly favour communication and does not recognise its strategic role in supporting management. Communication professionals are often not involved from the beginning of the processes and are usually only called 'to the table' when it is necessary to communicate with the outside. Only 2 of the 68 members of the response Taskforce created by DGS were specialists in the area of communication. Despite the apparent growth in the recognition of communication, there is still a lack of knowledge about its strategic potential and a lack of actual application of the recommendations given by experts.

The heavy and bureaucratic structure of DGS and the health institutions made crisis response difficult, contributing to some of the problems in pandemic communication. What happens is that organisations usually have plans designed for crises that unfold relatively slowly; however, in the context of a compound and continued crisis with cascade effects like the COVID-19 pandemic, heavy structures are not fit, which then manifests itself in the lack of capacity for adaptation and, consequently, lack of a timely response. This means that the initial response and communication are less efficient than needed, due to the lack of preparedness of the systems, leading to cascading consequences and making it more difficult to recover later.

As mentioned before, we know that the crisis communication guidelines designed by experts ([“Guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception”](#)) were not followed by the health authorities, but still, a year after the beginning of the pandemic, in March 2021, a task force of behavioral scientists was appointed, including as members experts that were authors of the first guidelines provided in March 2020. In fact, because of the global nature of the problem, epidemiological assessments and data analysis were being conducted by several independent identities and institutions (e.g., Portuguese Medical Association, universities, etc.), leading to various models, results and evaluations, often different from the ones disclosed by DGS. As a result, this competition in terms of information ended up pushing the government to open the conversation to “outsiders”, by giving more experts a seat at the table. This way, meetings were organised, gathering the various expert analyses and opinions to get a cohesive evaluation and consequently, efficient decision-making and communication. These technical meetings (referred to as the Infarmed Meetings) were chaired by the Minister of Health and brought together epidemiologists, health experts, political leaders and economic and social partners to share information and monitor the situation. In sum, at different points during the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal, society – and more specifically, scientists – exerted pressure on the government and health authorities to create a more open space for discussion, allowing for a bigger integration of experts in the decision-making processes. However, as discussed above, the recommendations were not always efficiently applied. Still related to the previous

topic, it is important to mention that, in all media channels, there were several experts as commentators, aiming to add more elements and find alternative sources of information. Therefore, medical experts have become major media figures and opinion leaders.

Experts' interviews: The journalists and government communicators interviewed mentioned that COVID-19 was a topic difficult to escape since it dominated media coverage for several months, which led to fatigue and other relevant topics not being sufficiently discussed (J_1, J_2). On the experts' part, there was special attention given to not disseminating information that was still uncertain. In cases where it needed to be communicated, they tried to make sure that degree of uncertainty was clear to the public and that they avoided jumping to conclusions. This cautious approach was not always present in the speech of government and health representatives; there were circumstances of inconsistent communication, causing anguish to the population. The fact that information was always changing led to contradictory recommendations and poor uncertainty communication, which also contributed to creating discreditability (J_2; GC_1; GC_3). Journalists tried to keep a close connection with official sources; in this sense, it was mentioned that the DGS did not purposely hide information from journalists, but it simply could not answer all the questions that were emerging (J_2). Especially in the beginning, there was a lack of coordination between the various health institutions and the journalists had a difficult time obtaining reliable and official information. After a while, communication became more transparent and fluid. In terms of alignment between actors, although it did not always happen formally (following a plan), there were efforts made in this direction. Government communicators said what could be said, made sure not to deceive the population and tried to provide information that was useful to try to get people to adopt behaviours to avoid infection. Experts would, at times, disagree with a certain measure, but they felt an obligation to promote alignment and advise people to listen to DGS to avoid confusing the population and to give credibility to the information (GC_2). At certain points, television and news channels explored a gravity that did not exist with the aim of having audiences, instigating panic and fear unnecessarily (J_1). It was referred that they could have had a more positive role and influence on the population:

"I think that public television, in addition to daily data, did little pedagogy. They could have had a more intervening role (...) They could have 1- or 2-minute programs a day with advice. There were thousands of things that could have been done (...) All public media television and radio could have done more, a more direct and pedagogical intervention."
(GC_2)

Government communicators consider that there was no communication strategy or plan implemented, especially in terms of scientific communication; experts were simply being contacted to comment on measures, give interviews for the media and advise the government, often adapting to circumstances as requests were arising (GC_1, GC_2; GC_3). There was mention of not talking with media channels known for being more prone to sensationalist news to avoid distortions or misinformation. There was a big mobilization of health professionals and experts and there was a lot that was done by experts besides what was being shown in the media (e.g., webinars promoted by patient associations, training of diagnostic staff, etc.) (GC_2). On the other hand, there seems to exist still a very traditional and self-absorbed academic culture that doesn't do enough to communicate science to the people (GC_1). It was recognized that the government made efforts in the sense of conveying a message of immunisation awareness and vaccination promotion (J_2). The contact, even if informal, between government communicators and journalists was mentioned as a positive practice

that allowed for awareness of what the population's questions were and better preparedness to plan communications (GC_3). Lastly, efforts were made by some media channels to clarify information:

“We opened a new box, “Explainer”, which was information that allowed to explain some issues that may not be simple to the reader (...) We tried to answer the questions that were being asked on social networks with the help of people who know the issues” (J_2)

During the early stages, the government was praised for its swift and effective response. In a survey conducted in May 2020, 72% of Portuguese respondents expressed satisfaction with the government's response (Eurobarometer, 2020). However, as the pandemic continued and restrictions on daily life persisted, frustration and fatigue among the public grew. In November 2020, a protest against the government's COVID-19 measures drew thousands of people to the streets of Lisbon, with some participants expressing their belief that the government was exaggerating the threat of the virus (Reuters, 2020). In 2021, during the second lockdown, the Minister of Health communicated that the 2021 lockdown was the same as the one in March 2020, but that people's reaction was different, that people seemed less bothered by the numbers. The minister appealed to the public in the name of healthcare workers, asking for conscience and compliance (TSF, 2021). Overall, the public's reaction to crisis management and communication in Portugal has been mixed. While most people appeared to have some level of trust in media communication, some niches would discredit the information presented while manifesting their belief in conspiracy theories. However, these were minorities that ended up not having a great impact on the general population.

3.7.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

At a national level, the Government communicated that they “will remain attentive to the needs of the most vulnerable populations in the face of the pandemic, among which are some Roma communities”. There was also a statement advertising a youth volunteering initiative to help disadvantaged communities. The DGS website provided information in five languages and there was the use of Cape Verdean Creole in posters in some health centres. DGS launched videos with prevention recommendations in 11 languages, including Portuguese sign language. There was also CoronaKids – a playful-pedagogical website for informing children about COVID-19. The main form of communication of DGS with vulnerable groups was carried out through partnerships with local associations and authorities. At a local level, for instance, the Alentejo region Health Unit created a link on its website targeted to vulnerable communities, with "Information for the Roma Community" and "Information for Migrants". Namely, there were videos depicting Roma people, as an attempt at representativeness. The "CO(m)VID(a)" project was implemented in a Roma community and a Health Education session was held for clarification about the virus and vaccination (Frazão et al., 2022).

In terms of the experts' points of view, it was mentioned that it's more difficult to identify specific initiatives regarding communication compared to other support measures (GC_3). It was a challenge to produce a message that was both applicable to the general population and adequate for those in contexts of greater risk and vulnerability where a different communication is needed (J_2). Regarding the action of specific more independent work groups (e.g., university experts and journalists), there were efforts made to reach groups especially important for pandemic communication, such as direct contacts with student associations to disseminate COVID-19 recommendations (GC_3), and contacts with scientific communities linked to certain patient associations (J_2).

3.8 Spain

3.8.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

The communication response in Spain during the COVID-19 pandemic involved several key elements and strategies. Here's an overview of how the communication response was planned:

- **Coordination and governance:** The Spanish government, primarily through the Ministry of Health, took the lead in coordinating the communication response. The National Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center (CCAES) played a central role in coordinating communication efforts and disseminating information (National Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center, 2020), through the central Government spokesman.
- **National and regional Collaboration:** Close collaboration and coordination between the national government and the autonomous communities (regional governments) were crucial but not fluent. The Inter-Territorial Council of the National Health System should have served as a platform for dialogue and collaboration between the national and regional authorities, but not always because of political differences.
- **Expert involvement:** Experts in public health, epidemiology, and risk communication were involved (but not from the very beginning of the pandemic) in planning and executing the communication, giving useful advises, guidelines and measures to the public. (Instituto de Salud Carlos III, 2021)
- **Messaging and guidelines:** clear and consistent messaging was a priority. The communication response aimed to provide accurate information, explain public health measures, and address public concerns. Guidelines were developed to inform the public about preventive measures, testing protocols, vaccination campaigns, and other relevant topics.
- **Multi-channel approach:** The communication response utilized multiple channels to reach a broad audience. These included press conferences, official statements, social media platforms, websites, and traditional media outlets. Different channels were used to disseminate updates, guidelines, and important information to the public, like the webpage of the Spanish Ministry of Health (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020)
- **Media relations:** Engaging with the media was an important aspect of the communication response. Regular press conferences were held by government officials and health authorities to provide updates, answer questions, and address concerns. Media outlets were kept informed through press releases and briefings.
- **Public awareness campaigns:** Public awareness campaigns were launched to promote preventive measures, such as mask-wearing, hand hygiene, and social distancing. These campaigns utilized various media channels to reach the public and encourage responsible behavior.
- **Monitoring and response:** The communication response involved monitoring public sentiment, concerns, and misinformation. Prompt responses were provided to address public questions and counter false information through fact-checking and public messaging.

Spain had documents and plans for crisis communication that were available before the COVID-19 pandemic. These documents and plans were developed to address various emergency situations, including public health emergencies. Here are some examples:

- **National Emergency Plan:** Spain had a National Emergency Plan (Plan Nacional de Emergencias) that outlined the country's response to emergencies, including public health emergencies (Ministerio del Interior, 2018). This plan provided a framework for coordination, communication, and decision-making during crises.
- **National Pandemic Influenza Plan:** The National Pandemic Influenza Plan (Plan Nacional de Preparación y Respuesta ante una Pandemia de Gripe) served as a guide for preparedness and response to influenza pandemics (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2005). Although the COVID-19 pandemic was caused by a novel coronavirus, this plan contained relevant strategies and measures for managing a public health crisis, including elements of crisis communication.
- **Regional Emergency Plans:** Each autonomous community in Spain had its own regional emergency plan (Plan de Emergencia), which included provisions for crisis communication. These plans detailed the roles and responsibilities of different authorities, communication strategies, and channels of information dissemination within the respective regions.
- **Risk Communication Plans:** Spain had risk communication plans (Plan de Comunicación de Riesgos) in place, which aimed to inform the public about potential risks and promote preventive measures (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020). These plans encompassed communication strategies for different types of hazards, including infectious diseases.

These documents and plans provided a foundation for crisis communication in Spain. However, it's important to note that the COVID-19 pandemic presented unique challenges and required specific adjustments and adaptations to existing plans and the development of additional guidelines and protocols tailored to the circumstances of the pandemic.

3.8.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The government, led by the Prime Minister and the Ministry of Health, held the primary responsibility for crisis management and communication and regional health authorities were responsible for implementing measures at the regional level while collaborating with the national government. At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain, the crisis management and response underwent several phases. Here is an overview of the initial implementation of crisis management and the reaction of the government, authorities, and responsible entities.:

1. **Early Response Measures and legislative actions:** As the pandemic emerged, the Spanish government, guided by the Ministry of Health, took initial measures to control the spread of the virus. These measures included the establishment of a state of alarm, travel restrictions, and the implementation of basic preventive measures such as hand hygiene and social distancing. The government enacted various legislative actions and measures to address the pandemic. These included the declaration of a state of alarm, which granted exceptional powers to the government to implement restrictive measures, such as lockdowns and curfews, to contain the spread of the virus (Spanish Government Royal Decree 463/2020).
2. **Activation of National Emergency Plan:** The National Emergency Plan (Plan Nacional de Emergencias) was activated to provide a framework for crisis management. This plan outlined the coordination, communication, and decision-making processes during emergencies, including public health crises.

3. **Ministry of Health and CCAES:** The Ministry of Health, particularly the CCAES, played a central role in crisis management and communication. The CCAES provided regular updates, guidelines, and recommendations based on the evolving situation and guidance from international health organizations (National Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center, 2020)
4. **Collaboration with Regional Authorities:** The Spanish government collaborated with the regional health authorities of the autonomous communities to ensure a coordinated response. The Inter-Territorial Council of the National Health System facilitated communication, collaboration, and decision-making between the national and regional authorities.
5. **Communication Channels:** The government and health authorities utilized various communication channels to provide updates and guidance to the public. This included regular press conferences, official statements, and the use of official websites and social media platforms to disseminate information.
6. **Scientific Advice and Expert Input:** The government sought scientific advice and input from experts in epidemiology, virology, and public health. Scientific advisory committees and health professionals played a crucial role in informing decision-making and crisis management strategies.

From COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown Until Vaccination Had an Effect on Measures:

During this period, the crisis communication response in Spain evolved as the understanding of the virus and the effectiveness of measures increased. Here are some key changes that took place:

- a) **Enhanced Information Dissemination:** At the beginning of the pandemic, there was a focus on providing basic information about the virus, preventive measures, and the importance of lockdowns. As knowledge evolved, the communication response became more nuanced, providing detailed guidance on specific measures, testing protocols, and quarantine guidelines (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021a).
- b) **Increased Emphasis on Scientific Expertise:** As scientific understanding of the virus improved, there was a greater reliance on scientific experts and advisory committees. Expert input played a critical role in informing decision-making and shaping communication strategies, ensuring that the public received accurate and evidence-based information.
- c) **Adaptation to Evolving Challenges:** The communication response adapted to the evolving challenges of the pandemic. Initially, the focus was on flattening the curve and preventing overwhelming the healthcare system. As the vaccine rollout began and vaccination had an effect on reducing severe cases, the messaging shifted to promote vaccination as a key tool to control the spread of the virus and achieve herd immunity (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021).
- d) **Targeted Communication:** Over time, communication efforts became more targeted, aiming to address specific population segments and address vaccine hesitancy. Campaigns focused on providing accessible information, dispelling myths, and addressing concerns to increase vaccine acceptance and coverage.

From Omicron (November 2021) until Now:

The emergence of the Omicron variant introduced new challenges and prompted adjustments in the crisis communication response. Here are some notable changes during this period:

- a) **Rapid Response to New Variant:** The communication response adapted swiftly to address the emergence of the Omicron variant. Communication efforts focused on raising awareness about the variant, its potential impact, and the need for continued adherence to preventive measures, such as mask-wearing, testing, and vaccination.
- b) **Reinforcement of Preventive Measures:** The communication response emphasized the importance of reinforcing preventive measures, including booster doses, mask mandates, and adherence to public health guidelines. Messaging highlighted the potential increased transmissibility and the need for individual and collective responsibility to curb the spread of the variant (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2022).
- c) **Addressing Vaccine Updates and Boosters:** Communication efforts addressed updates on vaccines, including booster shots. Messaging emphasized the importance of booster doses in enhancing immunity against new variants and maintaining individual and community protection.
- d) **Managing Uncertainty and Maintaining Trust:** The communication response aimed to manage uncertainty and maintain public trust during the Omicron variant surge. Authorities provided regular updates, addressed evolving knowledge, and acknowledged uncertainties, while emphasizing the commitment to evidence-based decision-making and protection of public health (Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores, Unión Europea y Cooperación, 2021).

Barriers and problems:

- **Rapidly evolving situation:** The dynamic nature of the pandemic presented challenges in keeping up with the evolving situation and communicating accurate and timely information.
- **Infodemic:** The rapid spread of misinformation, disinformation, and rumors posed challenges in ensuring the public had access to accurate information. One of the journalists said:

"If we detected a hoax we did not refer to that disinformation or fake news, but we fought it by offering truthful information from our accounts. And we appealed to the citizen to resort only to reliable official sources." (IJ_2)

- **Language barriers:** Communicating effectively with diverse populations, including those with different languages and cultural backgrounds, presented challenges.

Structural changes and change of responsibilities:

- **Enhanced coordination:** The crisis response required close coordination between national and regional authorities which not always be achieved, leading to changes in coordination mechanisms and responsibilities.
- **Centralization of decision-making:** In some cases, decision-making authority was centralized at the national level to ensure a coordinated response. As a journalist said:

"The experts were given a voice and a technician like Fernando Simón, director of the Coordination Center for Health Alerts and Emergencies, was chosen as spokesman. In my opinion it was a success, because the technical spokesperson is more reliable, has more social prestige and always provides greater credibility than that of the politician. He was alternating with the institutional and political spokespersons of the Minister of Health, Salvador Illa, and the President of the Government, Pedro Sánchez " (IJ_1).

Occurrence of multiple crises:

- Overlapping crises: The pandemic overlapped with other crises such as economic downturns, social unrest, and mental health challenges, which posed additional communication challenges and necessitated a comprehensive approach to crisis response.

Positive developments and solutions:

- Increased use of digital communication channels: The pandemic led to an increased reliance on digital communication channels, such as social media and online platforms, to disseminate information and engage with the public:

"We use the usual channels. On the one hand, the traditional ones: news agencies, written press, radios and televisions for that population that did not use digital platforms. And, on the other hand, social networks, such as Twitter and Youtube, which were reinforced and were undoubtedly our great allies in the dissemination of information." (IJ_1).

- Public-private partnerships: Collaboration between the government, private sector, and civil society organizations contributed to the dissemination of accurate information and innovative communication strategies.

Support or lack of support of measures:

- Varying levels of support: The level of support for measures varied among different segments of the population, influenced by factors such as political affiliations, personal beliefs, and socioeconomic factors. But, generally, citizens followed the protecting measures which Government recommended.
- Challenges in compliance: Encouraging consistent adherence to public health measures posed challenges due to various factors, including fatigue, misinformation, and differing perceptions of risk.

Crisis Communication and fighting misinformation:

- Measures to combat misinformation: Efforts were made to address misinformation, disinformation, and rumors through fact-checking initiatives, public awareness campaigns, and partnerships with media organizations to promote accurate information:

"If we detected a hoax we did not refer to that disinformation or fakenews, but we fought it by offering truthful information from our accounts. And we appealed to the citizen to resort only to reliable official sources." (IJ_1)

Focus on transparent and evidence-based communication: Authorities aimed to provide clear, transparent, and science-backed information to combat misinformation and maintain public trust:

"Because the information we gave was official and was contrasted by professionals in the field (health or firefighters). In addition, as our information was accompanied by images and statements recorded by ourselves, we witnessed everything that was done. We saw it

with our own eyes and so we told it, supporting each other, to give more consistency to the message, in the statements of the professionals" (IJ_3).

Otherwise, here are some examples of key documents delivered by the Spanish government and the Ministry of Health during the COVID-19 pandemic:

- Royal Decree 463/2020: This decree declared a state of alarm in Spain and established the initial measures to address the COVID-19 pandemic, including the implementation of lockdowns and restrictions.
- CCAES Updates: The CCAES, under the Ministry of Health, provided regular updates and guidance on the COVID-19 situation in Spain. These updates contained information on case numbers, measures, testing protocols, and public health recommendations.
- National COVID-19 Vaccination Strategy: The Ministry of Health released the national vaccination strategy, outlining the prioritisation, distribution, and administration of COVID-19 vaccines in Spain.
- Health and Safety Protocols for Different Sectors: The government and the Ministry of Health issued specific health and safety protocols for various sectors, such as schools, workplaces, and public transportation, to ensure the implementation of preventive measures and mitigate the spread of the virus.
- Guidelines and Recommendations for the General Public: The Ministry of Health published guidelines and recommendations for the general public on various aspects, including hand hygiene, mask usage, social distancing, and quarantine protocols.

The vaccination plan against COVID-19 in Spain was led by the Spanish government and the Ministry of Health. The Ministry of Health, under the leadership of the Minister of Health, played a central role in coordinating and overseeing the vaccination campaign. The plan was developed in collaboration with scientific experts, healthcare professionals, regional health authorities, and other stakeholders.

The Ministry of Health, in close coordination with the Inter-Territorial Council of the National Health System, provided strategic guidance, established vaccination priorities, and formulated the overall framework for the vaccination plan. They worked on the procurement and allocation of vaccines, distribution logistics, and the establishment of vaccination centers across the country.

Regional health authorities, responsible for the implementation of healthcare policies at the regional level, played a key role in executing the vaccination plan within their respective regions. They were responsible for setting up vaccination sites, organizing appointments, and ensuring the smooth administration of vaccines.

The vaccination plan was supported by various healthcare professionals, including doctors, nurses, and pharmacists, who were involved in administering the vaccines and providing essential healthcare services.

It is important to note that the leadership and coordination of the vaccination plan in Spain involved collaboration between multiple entities at the national and regional levels, with the Ministry of Health playing a central role in driving the efforts.

In November 2020, the development of the "Vaccination Plan against COVID-19" in Spain was a comprehensive and coordinated effort by the Spanish government and the Ministry of Health to ensure the efficient and equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccines throughout the country.

(Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021). The plan aimed to protect the population, reduce the impact of the pandemic, and eventually achieve herd immunity.

The process of elaborating the vaccination plan involved multiple stages, including scientific research, international collaboration, regulatory approvals, logistical planning, and public engagement. Here is a general overview of the story behind the development of the Vaccination Plan against COVID-19 in Spain:

- **Scientific Research and Vaccine Acquisition:** The plan began with the scientific research and development of COVID-19 vaccines worldwide. Spanish health authorities closely monitored vaccine candidates and engaged in negotiations with pharmaceutical companies to secure a portfolio of vaccines for the Spanish population.
- **Vaccine Evaluation and Approval:** The Spanish Medicines Agency (AEMPS) assessed the safety and efficacy data of vaccine candidates and collaborated with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) for regulatory approvals. The approval process ensured that vaccines met rigorous standards for safety, quality, and effectiveness.
- **Priority Groups and Vaccination Strategy:** The Ministry of Health, in consultation with scientific experts, established a framework for prioritising vaccination based on risk factors, vulnerability, and public health impact. Priority groups were identified, including healthcare workers, elderly individuals, people with underlying health conditions, and essential workers.
- **Vaccination Centers and Logistics:** The plan included the establishment of vaccination centres across the country, including hospitals, primary healthcare centres, and mass vaccination sites. Detailed logistics were developed, including cold chain management, storage, transportation, and supply chain coordination.
- **Communication and Public Engagement:** The Ministry of Health launched communication campaigns to inform the public about the vaccination plan, addressing concerns, sharing accurate information, and promoting vaccine acceptance. Public engagement was a key aspect to ensure transparency, build trust, and encourage participation. Communication campaigns like: #YoMeVacunoSeguro in the webpage of the Spanish Ministry of Health and with an official video [on Youtube](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=111111111111) (<https://www.sanidad.gob.es/campannas/campanas21/YoMeVacunoSeguro.htm>).
- **Vaccination Rollout:** The vaccination plan was implemented in phases, with priority groups receiving the vaccines first. Healthcare workers and residents of long-term care facilities were among the first to be vaccinated. The Spanish Ministry of Health through its web released a page with FAQs with information about the vaccines for the population (<https://www.vacunacovid.gob.es>). The plan gradually expanded to include other priority groups and eventually the general population. During the first months of vaccination, people were summoned from their corresponding health centers, according to priority by vulnerability and age. Then, in addition to direct summonses from health centers, citizens could also call these health centers or a telephone to quote themselves the day it was available. Later, in Madrid, two mass vaccination centers were established where people could go without an appointment.

Monitoring and Evaluation: The plan included monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the progress of the vaccination campaign (<https://www.sanidad.gob.es/areas/alertasEmergenciasSanitarias/alertasActuales/nCov/pbiVacunaci>)

[on.htm](#)), identify challenges, and make adjustments if needed. Data collection and analysis were crucial for tracking vaccine coverage, safety, and effectiveness.

Throughout the process, the Spanish government and the Ministry of Health collaborated with regional health authorities, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders to ensure a coordinated and efficient vaccination campaign.

Regional health authorities were the responsible for prioritizing vaccination groups: people with risk factors or other vulnerable people and health professionals too. As an example of coordination in Madrid, between the Autonomous Community of Madrid and the City Hall of Madrid (from which SAMUR-PC depends), an agreement was reached to train a group of nurses responsible for the vaccination of all members of SAMUR-PC. From this Service, the order was made to the Counselor of Health of the Autonomous Community of Madrid about the necessary vaccines for each day, according to the professionals cited to be vaccinated. And from SAMUR-PC its members were summoned to be vaccinated at the headquarter, making shifts of nursing staff responsible for the load of vaccines (those who had received training from the Autonomous Community of Madrid on vaccines, form of preparation, dose, form of administration and information to advise and resolve doubts about the vaccine). All the process was led by a physician and a pharmacist was controlling at all times the number of vaccines and their safe storage without breaking the cold chain.

Reflections on Pandemic Management and Crisis Communication:

Good Practices:

- **Timely and Transparent Communication:** Providing timely and transparent information to the public about the virus, preventive measures, and the evolving situation helped build trust and fostered a sense of shared responsibility.
- There was an important issue that stood out, in a generalized way, in all the journalists interviewed about the "feeling of responsibility" they had and their concern to give correct information to citizens, while combating fake news or misinformation:

"In this pandemic, we have seen that communication is one more element of crisis management. It is essential to be transparent, empathetic, provide clear, truthful and updated data and, ultimately, offer trust. And all this, starting from the difficulty of communicating when fear has taken over society and when it is the population that has to get involved to help get out of the crisis situation" (IJ_3).

- **Clear and Consistent Messaging:** Clear and consistent messaging, supported by scientific evidence, helped to mitigate confusion and misinformation, enabling individuals to make informed decisions:

"Because the information we gave was official and was contrasted by professionals in the field (health or firefighters). In addition, as our information was accompanied by images and statements recorded by ourselves, we witnessed everything that was done. We saw it with our own eyes and so we told it, supporting each other, to give more consistency to the message, in the statements of the professionals" (IJ_3).

- **Multichannel Communication:** Utilizing various communication channels, including traditional media, social media, and public health websites, allowed for broad reach and ensured accessibility to different segments of the population:

"Social Networks were perfect allies. All our information was posted on Twitter and Youtube. Both the citizen and the media were able to access all the content. From our followers on Social Networks we received messages daily. Some with the intention of helping, for example, in the dissemination of messages; others to make inquiries, ask for advice or clarify doubts (for many of them we referred @SaludMadrid because we were not the appropriate interlocutors); others exposing particular cases of relatives in residences from which they did not receive news. Almost all queries and questions were answered with the utmost respect and empathy and referred to the appropriate body. Many other interactions were to send strength and encouragement to health professionals." (IJ_1).

- **Collaboration and Coordination:** Collaboration between government agencies, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders facilitated a coordinated response and a unified communication strategy:

"The direction of the crisis was in charge of the government, so we were completely auxiliary. From that point of view, we try to complement and support the general guidelines to provide our help from a purely municipal point of view" (IJ_3).

"The Madrid City Council did not have the direct management of the pandemic, it was the responsibility of the Government of Spain. But as a spokesperson for the health service of reference of the people of Madrid, it was appropriate to offer preventive information on how to avoid contagion and what to do in certain health situations during confinement" (IJ_5).

Challenges and Lessons Learned:

- **Managing Uncertainty:** The dynamic nature of the pandemic posed challenges in providing accurate information in real-time. Balancing the need to communicate promptly with ensuring accuracy requires clear communication protocols and continuous updates as new information emerges:

"The key was to try to give confidence and certainty to citizens, in a very complicated situation. Hence, we tried through social networks and the media themselves, to offer advice and show the work that the emergency services were doing, without rest. To give some examples, we informed about the different types of masks that existed, how to disinfect home and clothes, tips to heal small wounds without having to go to a hospital, etc." (IJ_2).

- **Addressing Misinformation:** The spread of misinformation on social media and other platforms was a significant challenge. Implementing strategies to combat misinformation, such as fact-checking initiatives and working with social media platforms, is crucial:

"Communication is a fundamental tool to minimize consequences in a health crisis. It is very powerful in fighting misinformation. We must follow the established guidelines of leading, avoiding the information vacuum, contrasting and being transparent without dramatizing or transmitting excessive security. And always keep in mind the maxim that information – well worked – helps save lives" (IM_4).

- Tailoring Communication: Recognizing the diversity of the population and addressing language, cultural, and accessibility barriers is essential for effective communication. Tailoring messages to specific audiences and utilizing diverse communication channels can help reach a wider range of individuals:

"In one of the messages sent, they suggested we include subtitles in Twitter and Youtube videos to reach deaf people. And also this follower offered her collaboration by handling sign language. I think it was a mistake to spread the videos without subtitles." (IJ_1)

- Empowering Communities: Encouraging community engagement, involvement, and active participation in decision-making processes fosters a sense of ownership and strengthens adherence to public health measures.

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There is not much information, nor studies related to the perceived satisfaction of citizens about the management of the covid-19 pandemic carried out by the Spanish Government.

Some data providers indicate that Spain is one of the countries with the greatest dissatisfaction of the population with respect to the management of its government. According to this study (Ipsos (2021), 35% of Spanish people are satisfied with the work done by the Government to contain the pandemic. Although 55% express satisfaction with the work done by the WHO against covid-19. Even press such as (El independiente, 2020), states that 59.9% of the Spanish population considers that the Government has mismanaged the pandemic.

According to the Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas (CIS), an official body dependent on the Government of Spain, 23.4% of Spanish people have felt afraid of dying as a result of a coronavirus infection, 41.9% admit to having suffered sleep problems for this reason and, finally, 35.1% recognize that they have cried because of this situation (Center for Sociological Research, 2021).

According to interviews with journalists, one of the categories or issues for them was transparency in the information provided by the central Government. Some of the journalists expressed a message in favour:

"I think using a technician like Dr. Simon was the right decision. Beyond the criticisms that can be made, the truth is that the figure of the technician tends to be better accepted by the population because it is understood that a person speaks of science and not someone

who comes from a political party and who may have interests on the side. In addition, he answered daily all the questions that the media had about it. (IJ_3).

"I think the provisionality of COVID knowledge did not pose a credibility issue. The experts were the first to recognize with all humility that it was a new situation, unknown to everyone and in which they were not in a position to give immediate answers. It arrived unexpectedly and the experts were learning as they went. I think it is also important to be aware of the vulnerabilities of our societies and to convey it frankly." (IJ_3).

But, among the interviews, one category emerges as one of the most important for these journalists: Errors, lack of transparency and creation of fear and distrust in the population for the information of the Central Government:

"It was reported quickly, although in the pre-crisis (it could be justified by the ignorance of what was coming) messages of control and low risk were launched that ended up being erroneous such as that Spain will not have at most beyond some diagnosed case "or"that the incidence if it had been low and controlled", both by Fernando Simón. From these messages of tranquility it was passed overnight to alert the population generating doses of fear and uneasiness by advancing negative scenarios, high risk, etc ..." (IJ_1).

"The continuous drip of data on the evolution of the pandemic was necessary and showed transparency but I think they came to "overwhelm" a frightened population more than necessary. It was very difficult to keep the balance on that balance. There was some controversy because for those appearances there was a previous and notorious filtering of questions that for some journalists was partisan and revealed a certain censorship. I believe that the reports issued by the scientific-technical committee on which politicians relied to make decisions should have been made public from the outset. It would have given more transparency to the communication strategy" (IJ_1).

"There was a lack of transparency and that generated uncertainty and doubts in the population. Communication was not effective. One thing was said and the opposite and caused a loss of confidence on the part of the citizens. In many cases, messages were adapted as appropriate (e.g. with the use of masks), and the whole truth was not told. Lying always penalizes, but in crisis situations much more. There was a lack of transparency, among other things, because they did not want to recognize the (logical) ignorance that existed in the matter. Lies were made on several issues that were later discovered. And instead of recognizing the lack of self-protection material, the measures for the population were modified." (IJ_2).

"On very specific issues there was a great lack of transparency. Example: Issue masks, at first the government spokesmen assured that the masks were not effective to avoid contagion, alleging scientific reasons, when in reality, the government knew that if they were effective, but the problem, which they did not want to say, was the lack of material, of masks, there was not for everyone, even for the health workers in the first months" (IM_4).

"At the beginning of the pandemic the only news that came was that which came from China and in droppers, more than information I would say disinformation. When the Government decided to take measures, it was mandatory to publish them to keep the citizen informed. But it is true that he was suspicious of the statistics of deaths, to this day there is still a great discrepancy between the data of the Government and other entities" (IM_4).

"In the early stages of the pandemic, the evidence was denied and, as it was later demonstrated, they did not know or did not want to alert the population of the real situation. Over the weeks, they adjusted government communiqués to their management capacity which did not correspond to reality. Knowing first-hand the health situation and knowing that the Government was not taking adequate measures had a negative influence. From the point of view of communication, the opposite was done to what was advisable in the management of a crisis: single spokesperson, single message without distortions" (IJ_5).

"The continuous drip of data on the evolution of the pandemic was necessary and showed transparency but I think they came to "overwhelm" more than necessary a frightened population. It was very difficult to maintain balance on that balance." (IJ_1).

3.8.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The central Government, through the Ministry of Health, issued a first report, which was being reviewed and updated over time entitled: Analysis and proposals to address epidemiological vulnerability linked to social inequalities (https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/C_OVID19_Equidad_en_salud_y_COVID-19.pdf), which reflected concern about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on vulnerable populations, with issues related to the social determinants of vulnerability such as employment conditions, housing, income and economic situation, residential environment, access to social and health services, stigma and discrimination, digital divide, greater exposure to infection, among others.

With regard to the aspect related to employment and working conditions, it refers to the concern that this population performs jobs that must be face-to-face, assuming a greater risk of exposure to infection. For example, essential jobs such as food, transport, health and social work, domestic and care workers (Bambra, C et al, 2020). It is these groups where the strict monitoring of prevention and safety measures must be emphasized.

The differential impact according to gender is also highlighted, due to the feminization of some essential jobs such as health, cleaning or care (Ruiz-Cantero, M. T., 2020).

With regard to improving employment conditions, the following actions have been carried out:

- Protocols on the performance of occupational risk prevention services against exposure to COVID-19 (Ministry of Health, 2020a), which contemplate the participation of companies, as

well as the measures in current legislation on the prevention of occupational risks, highlighting the protection of especially vulnerable people and the measures to be adopted.

- The legislation on the consideration, exceptionally, of the period of isolation and quarantine as a situation assimilated to an accident at work, exclusively for the economic benefit of temporary disability of the Social Security system (Spanish Government. Royal Decree 6/2020).
- Measures such as unemployment benefit, temporary employment regulation files (ERTE), extension of temporary contracts, moratoria and exemptions for self-employed workers and approval of the minimum vital income (IMV) (Heras, R. L., 2020).

Relating to housing of a part of this vulnerable population, they live in situations of overcrowding that entail difficulties in maintaining prevention and protection measures against infection, such as isolation or quartering. On the other hand, collective housing such as residences or shelters (in which a very important part of this vulnerable population lives) are potential outbreak foci when there are insufficient means to guarantee distance and hygiene measures, in addition, specific health care in these places has proven to be insufficient or inadequate in many cases. (Working positive, 2020).

Among the actions carried out to mitigate these situations of vulnerability, housing alternatives have been established for the isolation of people with infection. In some cities, non-serious patients were referred from the health system to hotels with a health team. This is an important measure to enable effective isolation and quarantine. Although this measure has not been carried out throughout the national territory and was not available, in many cases, for people with comorbidities or dependencies who needed greater support in their care (Roldán, P. G., & Carrasco, A. M., 2020).

The socio-sanitary and public health services have reinforced surveillance and control in collective housing. Shelters and other spaces (e.g. exhibition halls, municipal centres, etc.) for homeless people have also been established. Although these measures did not continue after the end of the state of alarm.

As for more general measures, moratoriums on mortgage and rental debt, suspension of evictions during the state of alarm, temporary postponement of rent payments, aid for rent payments, guarantee of electricity, gas and water supply have been regulated. These measures have not been sufficient in many cases for the most vulnerable people, and some have ended even though social need has continued.

Also, job insecurity has made it more difficult to access and follow preventive measures and rules. In some cities, preventive material, such as masks and hydroalcoholic solution, has been distributed free of charge. However, administrative barriers have been identified in some cases due to lack of health card.

In precarious economic situations, the fear of losing a source of income, as a result of confinement, or isolation or quarantine, can motivate reluctance to report symptoms and go to the health system to receive a diagnosis.

Having a low income can also mean less access to telematics tools. This leads to less access to information related to the pandemic, less social connection, inequalities related to employability and quality of employment, even less possibility of diagnosis and follow-up. In some places, electronic devices and internet access have been provided to families without connection.

There has been a very significant increase in the demand for social services and soup kitchens, above their capacity. Increased mobility and long lines of people for access to food and essential deliveries

could have led to increased exposure to infection. For this reason, some soup kitchens decided to organize home deliveries.

The measures related to unemployment benefits and sick leave, as well as the approval of the Minimum Vital Income have been important to mitigate these effects. It is important to identify the different administrative, digital, educational or language barriers to access to these benefits as they can aggravate or generate new situations of exclusion.

The role that community networks have played in mitigating the impact of the pandemic among low-income people is noteworthy. A large number of informal neighbourhood-level food distribution networks have been created and strengthened. Also, in some cities and towns, the population itself has contributed to the development and distribution of preventive material, such as masks, in a situation of global shortages, or to the reduction of the digital divide through donation of electronic devices to people with lower incomes.

Some of the most important recommendations made by the Government on factors related to communication to the population are the following:

- Consider universal accessibility in communication strategies, paying special attention to the different linguistic needs, understanding and accessibility of populations, both in the content and format of messages, and in channels.
- Adapt messages to different population groups and use the necessary languages according to each context and subtitled formats, use of sign language, audio-description, cognitive accessibility measures such as easy reading, pictograms, etc., telephone numbers accessible by instant messaging for people with hearing problems:

"The information we disseminated was intended for the general public and in some cases, the most vulnerable population in a pandemic, such as the elderly. We use very simple language for this. We did not, however, translate the contents into other languages or use sign language or subtitles, for example" (IJ_1).

- Enhance the bidirectionality of information between health authorities and the population, establishing channels to listen to citizens, which allow evaluating whether the information is arriving and being understood, and adapt communication at each time and place:

"From our followers on social networks we received messages daily. Some with the intention of helping, for example, in the dissemination of messages; others to make inquiries, ask for advice or clarify doubts (for many of them we referred @SaludMadrid because we were not the appropriate interlocutors); others exposing particular cases of relatives in residences from which they did not receive news. Almost all queries and questions were answered with the utmost respect and empathy and referred to the appropriate body. Many other interactions were to send strength and encouragement to health professionals." (IJ_2).

- Offer interpretation and intercultural mediation to improve communication between health and social professionals and the people served.
- Provide electronic devices and internet connection and support for digital literacy, to people affected by the digital divide, to improve their access to information on the pandemic and measures, and communication with social and health services and community networks.

Facilitate alternative means of communication for those groups that present more difficulties to make use of the telematic route:

"We use the usual channels. On the one hand, the traditional ones: news agencies, written press, radios and televisions for that population that did not use digital platforms. And, on the other hand, social networks, such as Twitter and Youtube, which were reinforced and were undoubtedly our great allies in the dissemination of information" (IJ_1).

3.9 Sweden

3.9.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

From the very beginning, the government made it clear that the response to the pandemic would be according to the strategies applied by the Public Health Agency (PHA). The government thus relied on the scientific expertise of the agency, and the recommendations issued by it. This strategy was widely applauded by all political parties and the media.

On an average day (2018), 64 % of all Swedes read a newspaper (online or paper), 35 % watch tv-news, 62 % listen to the radio. Internet penetration rate is 98 %.

Swedes' have high trust in news media, 65% in Public Service radio, 62% in Public Service television, 41-47% in daily newspapers.

The PHA is responsible for coordinating infection control on a national level, taking action to uphold an effective infection control, and initiate measures to protect citizens from contagious diseases and other serious health threats during crises and in situations of increased preparedness. This includes risk and crisis communication. The overall goal of the agency's communication during a crisis is to reach all target groups, both internal and external, with correct and up-to-date information as soon as possible to enable them to act and/or make rational decisions. Identified target groups were: General public/media, vulnerable groups/groups with specific needs, victims and their families, other agencies and employees, opinion leaders and networks. Identified channels to disseminate information were press-conferences, external and internal websites (a specific crisis website could be used if necessary), social media, and receptions telephone service. Guidelines for the transmitted information were that it should be accurate, clear, prompt, reliable and respectful, that the agency must be responsive and accessible, that communication should contribute to mitigating the crisis and provide security among target groups, and that confidence in the authority must remain high during and after the crisis.

Already before COVID-19, the PHA had produced a report and strategic plan for how to communicate during a pandemic.

3.9.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The government, ministries and the government agencies have mainly communicated through press conferences, interviews in news media, government agencies websites, campaigns in traditional and social media. Community contacts was also a significant channel to reach hard-to-reach groups. Even

if most information was targeted towards the general public, different target groups were identified depending on the development of the pandemic.

The communication followed three main themes: to respect and follow the restrictions being induced, to confirm and support new restrictions and recommendations to mitigate the spread of the virus and increase vaccination.

Daily (on weekdays) press conferences became the main channel to reach the general public, where chief epidemiologist Anders Tegnell at the PHA became the person who more or less personalized the Swedish crisis management. The Swedish strategy built on advice and recommendations instead of mandatory measures and communication on the press conferences, where characterized as building on rationality, ensuring the citizens that the Swedish strategy was built on scientific evidence. The Swedish “expert regime” contrasted to other Nordic countries, where politicians (prime ministers) took the lead as communicators of the pandemic strategy.

How did these (referring to question 1-2) change over time

Press conferences became throughout the pandemic a central channel for communicating the pandemic. This said, they were more central during the first waves and became less frequent and the last press conference was held in March 2022. To that date almost 200 press conferences has been held. The reason for ending them was that the government on February 8th decided to remove almost all restrictions declaring that Swedes in the future must live with COVID-19 like with the seasonal flu. Still, campaigns for increasing vaccination continued during the Spring of 2022.

From November 2021 prime minister Stefan Löfven resigned, and Magdalena Andersson took over, the director of PHA retired at the same time. From that the new prime minister and the new director of the PHA became more visible in communicating the pandemic. The new prime minister also made some organizational changes centralizing the pandemic management to the prime minister and her staff.

What changes in crisis response occurred and why?

The aim was to make the information available to as many people as possible. Therefore, a combination of broad media, i.e., media that reached many people, was combined with information channels for different groups. Information channels were combined according to factors such as gender, age, language, special needs or whether people were in a particular situation in life, for example being pregnant, or did not use digital media, did not watch TV, or did not read print media.

Reaching groups with limited knowledge in Swedish became early on acknowledged and campaigns and information of government agencies’ websites was translated to many different languages. During vaccination campaign difficulties to reach out to specific target groups, both to inform about the vaccine to hard-to-reach group but also meet vaccine hesitancy and dis-/misinformation. The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency was responsible for continuously monitoring and, where necessary, addressing misinformation, disinformation and rumour spreading about COVID-19 vaccination. The results were weighed against other studies on vaccine acceptance and used as a basis for designing and targeting information efforts. The Communication Director at a government agency explains how they worked with vaccination disinformation:

"We have produced information about myths on eight to ten languages. So, we work a lot with what is happening on social media. We are monitoring it all the time and respond with facts"

Specific campaigns were to migrant populations was addressed, but also to men younger than 50 years. Further, adolescents among which vaccination was lower and people with lower acceptance to other vaccinations was also target groups for vaccination campaigns. The introduction of vaccine-guides in migrant dense suburbs was one of these campaigns, where people living in the area with migrant background used their network to spread information about the vaccine.

In short were changes in the campaigns due to 1. Groups not reached by the main channels, 2. Groups being more severely affected by COVID-19 and 3. Groups with low trust in measures/vaccine.

Reflections on pandemic management/communication taking changes into consideration.

Criticism against the crisis communication has been centred around vagueness in language, lack of transparency and coordination of information between government agencies and other public authorities (health care, municipalities). Also, conflicting messages have been discussed as problematic during the first wave of the pandemic. In general, more criticism was directed toward the crisis communication regarding the campaigns to mitigate the spread of information than the vaccination campaign.

A general problem during the pandemic was to communicate uncertainty, as knowledge about the virus increased all the time, recommendations and advice changed and new risk groups were added or removed from the list of target groups. Another problem was to motivate citizens following the recommendations during a prolonged crisis as pandemic fatigue became a emerging problem.

Lessons learned about crisis communication has been discussed. One general is that preparedness and structures need to be present before the crisis emerges. A communication director working in migrant dense suburbs explains:

"All these structures have to be built up before, the relationships have to be built up before, the trust has to be built up before. You don't build trust during a crisis. You can build on, you can strengthen. But there must be some foundation..."

Another thing being important is to have knowledge about target groups and their media use and information seeking behaviour to manage to reach and address them with relevant information. What also is stressed in interviews was the choice not to spend resources on the anti-vaxx movement. This movement is quite small in Sweden and the large efforts were instead to reach those for different reasons doubting to take the vaccine, as commented by a vaccine coordinator:

"There are not so many "couch potatoes" anymore, but those who need to be convinced. Then there is this small percentage, I don't know, they usually say 2 or 5 percent or something who really don't want to be vaccinated. We don't put any energy on them. I said that early on, that they are not interesting to focus on - they won't do it anyway. However, they put a lot of focus on us [laughs]"

Experiences from the vaccination guides learned that effective crisis communication is not only about speaking to a target group, but also about listening to learn about socio-cultural characteristics, level

of trust, language proficiency, potential previous sensitive experiences, political context, and so forth. Civil society and interpersonal communication are central to reach out to minority communities, building on existing networks.

How did the public react to the crisis management/communication and its changes?

According to national surveys conducted with the Swedish public, the majority was well informed about what measures to take to avoid getting infected in COVID-19, and the implementation of measures increased notably during the autumn of 2020. Most Swedes kept informed about the spreading of the virus, protective measures that were imposed, consequences on citizens and society, and vaccination strategies through Swedish news media. Also, the websites of government agencies were frequently used as well as news media from other countries.

Most Swedes were satisfied with the information that news media provided, even if the tonality was seen as alarmistic when infection rates were higher. Trust in news media, especially public service, was also high and trust in health care was very high throughout the pandemic. Trust and support for politicians were the highest during the first wave, which indicate a so-called rally effect.

Our conclusion is that Swedes were well informed and that the information on a national level from government and government agencies effectively reached the public. The news media assisted government in reaching out to the public with essential information during the corona crisis, and the websites of government authorities provided frequently updated information on restrictions and recommendations, statistics on the spread of infection, and burden of infection on healthcare, in Swedish, a large over 20 other languages, sign language and easy-to-read texts.

There was almost no public outrage against the measures like we have seen in other countries. A few demonstrations were organized against the use of vaccine certificates. These were, however, margin phenomena with rather few participants. Vaccination rates were high in Sweden, where 88 percent had taken at least three doses in 2023.

3.9.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

Expert interviews with the Communications Director (CD) at the PHA stressed they already at the beginning of the pandemic had knowledge and preparation for reaching out to vulnerable groups.

And where we already know before - it's nothing new - there you have to put a lot of gunpowder to reach out, and that's what we've tried to do. Cooperation, I just want to say, is the whole watchword of it. No one does it themselves, but they do it in collaboration with other authorities and regions and so on. It's super important, it's absolutely crucial.

The PHA talks about “customized communication” which is tailored messages and channels for specific target groups and the PHA early identified groups with low socio-economic status as having need for tailored information, but migrants with low trust and non-Swedish speaking inhabitants were also early on recognized as being more vulnerable. Later, other groups were put on the list for being more vulnerable as for example disabled, chronically ill, obesity and pregnant. For some of these groups were messages tailored, for example were pregnant women addressed with vaccine communication, but obesity was not addressed any particular way and the National Board for Health and Welfare kept the level for obesity as a risk group to a BMI +40, even if studies showed the risk was significantly

higher even with a BMI +30. Apart from these were elderly people identified as being more vulnerable from the very beginning and was therefore advised to keep social distance and limit social contacts to a minimum. The call to “protect the elderly” during the first wave criticized for stigmatizing groups and being unclear about which group was targeted. Social distance recommendations targeting specifically people 70+ was during the fall of 2020 removed from public campaigns.

During the vaccination campaign low socio-economic status groups were identified as being less inclined to take the vaccine, but also migrants with low trust and limited Swedish language skills. As already mentioned, were pregnant women also an identified group with higher vaccine hesitancy and younger citizens, often men, were another such group. Targeted campaigns to these groups, using social media, podcasts and interpersonal communication campaigns helped to inform about the vaccine. Specific campaigns (Vaccination Day) and mobile vaccine teams were also used motivate vaccination and lower thresholds for taking the vaccine.

3.10 Wales

3.10.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

Wales is a devolved nation within the United Kingdom since 1998. Devolution granted the National Assembly for Wales the power to decide how the Westminster government's budget for Wales is spent and administered. In 2006, the National Assembly for Wales was given legislative powers, resulting in the creation of a Welsh Parliament and a Welsh Assembly Government, comprising of a Prime Minister for Wales (currently Mark Drakeford), Welsh ministers and deputy ministers. From May 2020 onward the National Assembly for Wales is called the Welsh Parliament in English and Senedd Cymru in Welsh. Wales has its own National Health Service (NHS Wales). NHS Wales now delivers services through seven Health Boards (HBs) and three NHS Trusts in Wales. The HBs now plan, secure and deliver healthcare services in their areas. The Wales Resilience Forum is the highest authority for crisis management and emergency planning in Wales and works in cooperation with local resilience forums and other agencies. Wales as a devolved nation follows advice from their Chief Medical Officer (Frank Atherton) and Chief Scientific Adviser (Rob Orford). The Chief Medical Officer works with the Welsh Government on policy for public health, and the Chief Scientific Adviser advises the Welsh Government on matters related to health science.

The Coronavirus Restrictions were approved by the Welsh Parliament on March 25th, giving Wales the power to manage the pandemic independently of the other British nations. As addition to the UK-wide SAGE group, Wales created a Technical Advisory Cell (TAC) and a Technical Advisory Group (TAG) to support SAGE in advising the Welsh Government and Public Health Wales. TAG-SAGE experts inform the ministers, which in turn present changes to the regulations to the Welsh Cabinet for consideration. The Cabinet makes the final decision which is communicated to the ministers. The Welsh pre-pandemic preparedness strategy is aligned to the overarching UK-wide strategy. The main Welsh document that resembles a pandemic response plan or strategy is the *Wales Framework for Managing Infectious Disease Emergencies 2005*. It “sets out national arrangements for managing major infectious disease emergencies, including national co-ordination, operational responsibilities of NHS organisations and the role of partner agencies” (Welsh Government 2007: 3). Wales has a pandemic-specific response

plan; the 2007 *Pandemic Influenza Guidance Planning* was established before the 2009 influenza pandemic. For emergencies in general, Wales has the *Pan-Wales Response Plan*.

3.10.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The Welsh Government communicated its measures and plan in updated versions of the 'Coronavirus Control Plan' with regulations formalised in 'The Health Protection (Coronavirus Restrictions) (Wales) Regulations 2020'. The (updated) plans have brief sections on communication, and focus on collective responsibility and maintaining the anti-COVID behaviours to prevent the virus spreading. TAG launched a report in March 2022 "Living safely with COVID19 in Wales: risk communication and behavioural science perspectives" that is still in place in June 2023. It shifted the emphasis to all people and organisations continuing embracing anti-COVID measures. Most emphasis is placed on individual behaviours, based on the 'Covid Code' in the TAG's August 2021 paper *Sustaining COVID-safe behaviours in Wales*⁴. A public health Wales (PHW) communication strategist and public health researcher reflects on the communication about the implementation of the measures at the start of the pandemic and what makes it powerful enough so that people adopt these new rules:

"I understand public messaging, I understand the need to be really clear. And to have something that is authentic. So people say 'it's not just, you know, Boris [Johnson] or whoever standing up saying this. There's a guy there called Chris Whitty who understands it. He's clever, he's knowledgeable and he's got something that shows that I can't do that'. At what I can do is to say, 'from the evidence and research that we've got over time, this is where we think, you know, we can place the most emphasis' and you put the two together that can be really powerful."

In their view, the message combining quantitative and qualitative data insights was pertinent, rather than only quantitative data that almost exclusively underpinned Welsh policy decisions and crisis communication at the start of the pandemic: *"I'm not a scientist, but the hard science data can be used in any which way you want to justify what you've done and why you've done it. (...) 'we are always learning, nothing is definite, we cannot say for certain that if we do this thing, then that's going to cause that to happen'"*. Their narrative beyond this quotation denotes a style of crisis communication based on 'hard' scientific assertions of clarity and certainty shifting to one that allows for more uncertainty and humbleness on knowledge creation about the virus-society interactions in Wales.

According to an interviewed member of the TAG Guidance Cell, at the start of the pandemic (Point 1), the Cell did not have the new pandemic measure information that the Welsh Government had developed to a greater detail, nor did they receive it before the general public did via the press conferences. They stated that the Cell always kept an eye on the Welsh Government webpages and social media channels, on BBC Wales that broadcasted the press conferences, and on WalesOnline; a popular media channel that was often the quickest in reporting Welsh pandemic news. At later stages (early summer 2020), the TAG was more closely included in the determination of the content of government announcements, so that they could consider and coordinate answers to the questions they anticipated the new announcements would conjure. In terms of processual change in crisis

⁴ <https://gov.wales/technical-advisory-group-sustaining-covid-safe-behaviours-wales-html>

communication, after initial non-involvement, the scientific experts worked with a comms person, which created a more robust message that was more legible for a wide audience.

For media correspondents, the early stages of the pandemic a journalist from BBC Wales with health expertise said that *“At the start, there was a lot about public information, just telling the public what they needed to know, and what the government was doing. And you know, how likely it was there would be restrictions”*. They said that further analysis, interpretation, or addition of journalistic insights and expertise would bring more confusion and possibilities to challenge the crisis messages. Therefore, they abstained from doing so at that time, which would change in summer 2020 as and when it would not interfere with the government’s message. The journalist described the difficulty of their task:

“I was trying to strike the balance between things like reassurance and accurately illustrating the scale of the threat: ‘How worried should people be anyway?’ (...) but you couldn’t really assure or advise or accurately illustrate the scale of the threat (...) at the time, it was perhaps one of the things that I was thinking most about, you know, where do I pitch what I’m saying at this stage of the story?”

In the absence of offering a very critical analysis of the Welsh Government’s interpretation of and response to the pandemic, this and other journalists suggested that the media’s task mainly involved helping the public assess their position in this crisis.

Several changes in the content of the crisis response in Wales have become apparent. A PHW communication specialist and HB crisis manager remarked on the astounding ethical stance the Welsh response held towards homeless people at the start of the pandemic. They elaborate:

“I think that, that if nothing else, that was just jaw dropping in terms of response. I think there’s some real issues around it. (...) There’s lots of unknowns for me, but in terms of a government making a statement that says ‘we will not allow homeless people to be without a home during this’, I just thought, ‘goodness, where did that come from?’ So that that is the more positive example that from my reading of that it didn’t matter who they were, it didn’t matter what their problems or issues or addictions might have been, didn’t matter if they were here illegally or not, none of that mattered, then what mattered was that they were able to access you know, a roof over their head, we were able to feed them now”

Whilst the possibilities for rapid and profound change turned out to be possible in Wales’ social policies in the context of the pandemic, the longevity of these new ethical drivers of such policy is questionable. Not only through the incessant lack of resources that Wales continues to struggle with, and which keeps its healthcare system perpetually on the edge of collapse, the interviewee quoted above identified that the foundations for structural change around those new ethical positions may not allow future policy adherence to these ethics as social policy is not devolved to Wales (Bambra et al. 2021).

In the early pandemic stages, marginalised groups had pandemic regulations imposed on them from more central, nationally organised institutions, including Welsh Government, and were addressed by PHW. Later on, local teams gained decision-making importance on appropriate pandemic measures for these marginalised groups. As the Guidance Cell member elaborated on: *“Our local teams, they know where those populations are. That’s part of their role and what they bring to our public health system is that eyes and ears, and that community level knowledge to deliver that information.”*

In terms of changes in media coverage and message formations, a BBC journalist with health expertise argued that they changed their message delivery from addressing the figure of their grandmother to the figure of a sceptical friend in a pub. They remained sensitive as they knew that different people were affected differently by the pandemic, because differences in living conditions and having lost significant others: *“So you took telling the story to others dispassionately while being involved in the story and the uncertainty.”* Restricted journalistic practices and the meaninglessness of numbers created further problems for journalists: *“Because the numbers were there each and every day, you almost have to start with the numbers and try and work back for backwards from there. And I was acutely aware that we are missing a huge amount of personal stories here but the problem was.”* From the Delta variant onward, the interviewee changed their focus into tracing circumstances of social groups that had been neglected.

The public reacted to the crisis management and communication in several ways. At the start of the pandemic, a health practitioner who worked for the TAG Guidance Cell recalled that the need for clarity about the pandemic and information on what people should do was most pertinent. They explained that after every press conference and news item, the Cell would be bombarded by phone calls. Compounding the Welsh public’s confusion was the lack of certainty about what advice to follow, as former UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson would announce new regulations, incorrectly seeming to speak to the whole of the UK. These televised press conferences by Westminster did not carry the ongoing message that only the measures announced by First Minister of Wales Mark Drakeford would be relevant to people in Wales.

Gauging the public opinion to find out what to address in news articles became very difficult in the absence of offline public debates. It was difficult to rely on online debates that were also fuelled by extremist views. A journalist who mainly publishes in Welsh-medium media outlets recalled being very conscious of their role in forming the public opinion on pandemic measures. They recall the case of a cinema owner in Swansea who flouted all pandemic rules and was forced to close indefinitely:

“There’s a real balance between doing what you know, deeming something as newsworthy, but also giving people who are sort of paddling, quite obviously in misinformation, too much oxygen.”

In the absence of people’s pre-pandemic references, this journalist was very conscious of not forming the public opinion in opposition to the pandemic regulations. Another journalist who reported mainly on local issues in Swansea recalled the increase in the uptake of the antivaxx ideology by the public and the ensuing hesitation for accepting the vaccine in early 2021: *“there was just that that very strong, anti-vaxx element of society that were very vocal, and clearly genuinely believed that they were they were right, and that this thing was bad.”* The curation of conventional media articles and social media posts that held more or less extremist views was considered to be of great importance in how the public reacted to the pandemic measures according to the communication specialists and journalists.

3.10.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

Towards the winters of 2020 and 2021 a PHW communication strategist and public health researcher explained that more qualitative effects of the pandemic policies were also becoming important. The realisation came that the first pandemic winter would take another toll on people and the need for the

vaccination programme to be effective for vulnerable groups was pivotal in considerations of the pandemic measures' effectiveness. The interviewee discussed this attention to vulnerable people:

“But suddenly, [marginalised people and violence] took on a new value and importance, because here's a bit of public health that is not just about vaccines, it's not just about medical stuff. It's not just about petri dishes, it's about people, and how they are going to be responding to this and how it might affect things like their mental health, things like adversity in childhood, because people are, you know, confined by restrictions. And the bit I was worried about more than anything else, what about those people we've never cared about, and we really don't care about now, what are we doing for them? So suddenly, I was given a platform, if you like, to start to voice some of the things that that suddenly people were listening to.”

Their work and insights into marginalisation processes became central in the communication strategy. It helped to ensure people's continued adherence to the behavioural regulations and to prevent social inequalities to exacerbate rapidly. The quotation testifies of a consideration of vulnerability beyond biology or 'medical stuff' but seem to have expanded into a fuller idea of humanity in the pandemic: one that acknowledges personal, social history, feelings, and other intangible aspects of human life.

The TAG Guidance Cell member explained how the notion of vulnerable groups consisting of certain social groups needed to be expanded further in crisis communication. In the context of care homes:

“The staff that work with [residents] are some of the lowest paid individuals in society. They have low educational standards, low health literacy, they have poor money, they're often on the poverty line, but also they're vulnerable themselves. (...) They were still going to work, even though they were susceptible to adverse risks themselves. How would you communicate to them a 74-page document over telephone, and that's what our role is, to talk them through those processes to make sure that they're safe, but also protecting the residents that they're treating or, or caring for.”

Crisis communication then highlighted how vulnerability in the pandemic cannot only be considered as attached to social groups, but as emerging from circumstances and processes that put particular people in situations that made them susceptible to more suffering in the pandemic than many others. Media focused on disproportionate effect of the pandemic on different groups and highlighted the suffering of some. Such kind of messages also served to educate more privileged groups that the pandemic ought to be taken seriously, adhere to the rules, and highlight pandemic damages outside their social circles. In terms of media communication, the health correspondent from BBC Wales explained that they ensured the pandemic measure messages as issued by the Welsh Government were understandable for a large public. They did so by using language that included little to no jargon. As such, older people and people with a lower degree of completed education would be able to better understand what was happening and what was expected at the various stages of the pandemic.

In terms of policy making and communication strategy design, vulnerable people became of more importance at a later stage in the pandemic in Wales. A PHW communication strategist and public health researcher explained the shift they saw in how the consideration for marginalised groups in Wales had suddenly garnered interest from senior management and policy makers. It became clear that the measures had fuelled the marginalisation of certain social groups in Wales (e.g. Gypsy Travellers, homeless people, and minority ethnic groups) and had suddenly been allowed to become

visible and informative of new pandemic policy. The interviewee argued that despite the authorities' historical disinterest and maintenance of policy structures that would not reduce social and health inequality, the institutions were now (more) open to be confronted with these structures, such as on housing and vaccination rates. Despite the interest in the plight of vulnerable groups in the pandemic, the interviewee remained sceptical in the durability of the health organisations' commitment to these groups. Nonetheless, the communication strategist remains hopeful towards continuing the prioritisation of vulnerable groups after the pandemic and when the funding has dried up.

4 Key findings

The COVID-19 pandemic has posed unprecedented challenges for public health authorities (PHAs) and governments around the world. One of the key aspects of managing the crisis is effective communication with the public, especially with vulnerable groups who may be more at risk of infection, complications, and social exclusion.

4.1 Good Practices for Communicating with Vulnerable Groups during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Prior Implementation of the Influenza Pandemic Plan

Some countries, such as Austria, Germany, and Sweden had already developed Influenza Pandemic Plans before the COVID-19 outbreak. Germany had conducted cross-national exercises in case of an emergency, and had established contacts with organizations working with migrants, refugees, homeless people, and people with disabilities. Moreover, Germany and Sweden also had prior knowledge in reaching out to vulnerable groups, such as ethnic minorities, elderly people, and people with chronic diseases.

Immediate Establishment of a Multi-Professional Emergency Team

A second good practice was to establish a multi-professional emergency team that could coordinate and collaborate with different actors and organizations at various levels. Each of the ten countries report collaborating with different supra-national or subnational actors and organizations. A third good practice is the formation of emergency teams that involved representatives from the government, the health care sector (nurses, pharmacists, doctors), the media, the civil society, and the scientific community. Some countries, like Belgium, also integrated communication into policy decision-making processes. Portugal created a task force of behavioural scientists to advise on communication strategies. Another good practice, observed in half of the countries (Austria, Belgium, Greece, Sweden, and Wales) was the active collaboration with group representatives or organizations working with certain vulnerable groups of people, to tailor the communication to their needs. Wales set a good example of relying on already formed public health networks that are run by highly networked people already experiences in solving crises through collaboration.

Use of Multiple Communication Channels and Style of Communication

Another good practice was to use multiple communication channels to reach different audiences and provide accurate and timely information. For example, Austria and Sweden used various channels such as websites, social media, TV, radio, newspapers, leaflets, posters, and phone lines to disseminate information about the pandemic. Some countries also collaborated with journalists to ensure that the information was clear and consistent. For example, Portugal involved journalists in the official information dissemination. In England Journalists interpreted governmental information and invited experts on their shows. Information was presented in a more popular and personal way, rather than presenting simply raw numbers, to raise awareness among the public.

The style of communication was also important to convey trust and credibility. Some countries adopted a coherent and immediate communication style that was responsive to the changing situation and the public's needs. For example, Italy and Greece assessed the effectiveness of different media

channels and tailored their responses accordingly. Belgium also monitored the population's beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours regarding the pandemic and adjusted their communication strategies accordingly. Greece assessed the vaccination achievements and implemented accordingly tailored measures. Some countries also created an internal document that served as a basis for all crisis communication institutions to keep their messages aligned. For example, Wales developed a document that outlined the key messages, target audiences, communication objectives, and evaluation methods.

Engaging the Public

Finally, some countries also recognized the importance of engaging the public and addressing their concerns and feedback. For example, in Spain public engagement was a key aspect to ensure transparency, build trust, and encourage participation. The Spanish Ministry of Health launched communication campaigns to inform the public about the vaccination plan, addressing concerns, sharing accurate information, and promoting vaccine acceptance.

4.2 Bad Practices

The COVID-19 pandemic has been a global challenge that required effective and timely crisis communication from various actors and stakeholders. However, not all countries and regions have performed well in this regard. The ten country reports identified some bad practices that hampered the communication efforts and undermined the trust and compliance of the public.

Lack of pre-existing crisis communication plans

One of the most common bad practices was the lack of a pre-existent crisis management plan or the failure to apply or adapt the existing plans to the specific situation of the pandemic. While most countries had some form of crisis preparedness plan, it did not include a clear communication strategy in the case of a pandemic. For example, Austria, Greece, Belgium, and Portugal did not have a crisis communication plan ready for such a scenario, while Greece also did not learn from previous pandemics. In Belgium there was a disbelief that there would ever be a long-term crisis, which affected their preparedness and response. While Portugal launched the plans, but they were not applied consistently or effectively. Germany had emergency plans that were implemented, but they were not designed for such a long period spanning more than two years, and they did not specify the vulnerable groups enough.

Governmental structures

Another bad practice was related to the governmental structures and their flexibility and transparency. Some countries, such as Portugal, reported that their governmental structures were quite inflexible, which made it difficult to respond timely to the pandemic. Some countries also had a too centralized approach, which hindered the communication between media representatives and government, as well as posed challenges for states with federal structures. For example, Greece reported that media professionals were not able to ask the government direct questions. Germany reported that the communication between federal authorities and media stakeholders was inadequate, and not transparent in regard to why certain measures were taken. Germany also reported that municipalities did not communicate timely or comprehensibly enough, and that the government could have explained things more clearly. Portugal also reported that governmental officials lagged behind when answering to journalists' questions. Another issue was related to the health organizations, which are

very hierarchical and did not favour communication, thus excluding communication professionals from the early stages of the processes. This was based on the lack of knowledge on the strategic potential communication experts can have, as reported by Portugal.

Political scandals, contradictory measures and sinking levels of trust

A third bad practice was associated with political scandals or sudden changes in the political structures that influenced the trust levels in politics. For example, Austria experienced political scandals and changes in the government that eroded the public confidence in the government. Moreover, Austria had inconsistent approach in some areas, for example mandatory vaccination, which was initially announced, only to be cancelled before coming into force. These contradictory steps created confusion and frustration among the citizens. Sweden and Germany also reported sudden changes in their political strategy regarding the pandemic, which affected their credibility and consistency. Some countries also promised things that they could not deliver or communicate them properly. For example, Wales promised 9000 test results per day but did not manage to achieve this. England also reported that half of the respondents thought the government communication to be low in honesty and credibility.

Multiplicity of actors in crisis communication

A fourth bad practice was related to the involvement of too many actors in crisis communication who sent contradicting messages. This created confusion and uncertainty among the public, who did not know whom to trust or follow. This was reported by Italy, Greece, Sweden, Portugal, and Wales. Some of these countries also reported a lack of coordination between the various health institutions, which affected their efficiency and effectiveness. England and Wales had a special case, as many people in Wales watched news from England which measures however did not apply for Wales. Another issue was related to the insufficient involvement of different groups of people in crisis management, such as ethnic minorities or vulnerable groups. This was reported by Austria, Wales, and Germany. For example, Wales reported ineffective messaging by ethnic minority Members of Parliament who showed scepticism, complacency and mistrust by scientists and politicians as compared to other local community members.

One-size-fits-all communication approach

A fifth bad practice was related to the one-size-fits-all communication approach that was insufficient for addressing the diverse needs of the public. Some countries reported that their communication was too complex or too focused on quantitative data that did not resonate with the citizens. For example, Austria and Italy reported that too complex data discouraged citizens from following the pandemic situation closely. Greece and Wales reported that governmental news needed to be translated into "simple language" by journalists who acted as mediators between the authorities and the public. Wales also reported that the communication was too focused on excessive quantitative data, while they were missing personal stories that could humanize the pandemic and its impact and make it more understandable and relatable. Greece also reported that there was too little information on the pandemic available, which enabled the spread of fake news and misinformation. Sweden reported that the communication language was too vague and the crisis communication was untransparent, which affected their trustworthiness and clarity. In England, it was regarded by many people that the information provided by the official channels of communication is insufficient.

Style and content of communication

Another bad practice was related to the reporting style of media outlets who sometimes reported on COVID-19 too negatively or sensationally instigating unnecessary panic and fear among the public. This was reported by Portugal and Germany who criticized some television and news channels for their coverage of the pandemic. Another issue was related to the lack of scientific journalists who could explain the scientific aspects of the pandemic in an accurate and understandable way. This was reported for Belgium, where it was also pointed out that the self-absorbed academic culture did not do enough to communicate science to lay people.

The content of the communication was also criticized. It was regarded as focusing too much on physical health and neglected other aspects, such as mental health or social well-being. This was reported for England where one health campaign that excluded mental health from its message, was openly criticized. This campaign was perceived as insensitive and ignorant of the psychological impact of the pandemic and the lockdown measures on the public.

4.3 Communication Strategies

The COVID-19 pandemic has required various communication strategies from different actors and stakeholders to inform, educate, and persuade the public about the virus, the measures, and the vaccines. The country reports highlighted the types of communication strategies and their effectiveness.

Format of official communication

One of the most common formats of communication strategies was the use of press conferences, which were held by authorities and experts in all of the ten countries. These press conferences aimed at providing regular updates on the pandemic situation (in the initial periods, daily), announcing new rules or restrictions, explaining the rationale behind the decisions, and answering questions from journalists or citizens. Another common format of communication strategies was the use of information on governmental media, such as official ministries websites and official social media channels. These were used by Austria, Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Wales, England, and Germany to disseminate official information and guidelines on the pandemic, as well as to counter misinformation and rumours. A third common format of communication strategies was the implementation of information campaigns, which were designed to raise awareness and promote behaviours related to the prevention and control of the virus. Such campaigns were launched by all ten countries and covered topics such as hygiene measures, social distancing, testing, tracing, isolation, quarantine, and vaccination. A fourth common format of communication strategies was the reactivation and establishment of new health hotlines, which were used actively in Austria, Belgium, and Wales to provide advice and support to people who had questions or concerns about the virus or their health status. Other forms of communication strategies that were reported by some countries were individual targeting by sending out letters or text messages to citizens (England), and establishing mobile phone applications for contact tracing or alerting (Austria, Italy, Germany, and Portugal). All countries also launched special vaccination information campaigns.

Approach and principles of the communication strategies

The communication strategies also varied in terms of their approaches and principles. Some countries adopted a centralized top-down approach (Italy, Greece, Belgium in the federal phase), which meant

that the communication was mainly led by the central government or a single authority that coordinated the messages and actions. Other countries used an umbrella campaign with many minor campaigns (Germany), which meant that there was a general framework for communication that was adapted. The different countries followed different principles of communication. Austria and Greece chose to not report too complex issues for the general public. Italy followed the principles of constant and coherent flow of information. Wales and Sweden focused on providing accurate, clear, prompt, reliable, and respectful information. England put an emphasis on using comprehensive language. Germany aimed to provide factual information to avoid unrest and anxiety. Another principle was to clearly communicate when information was uncertain, acknowledging the gaps in current knowledge and predictability about the virus or its impact. This was particularly emphasized for Wales and Portugal. Another technique deployed in England was to use easy to comprehend visuals that were consistent and generic to all communities, ethnic groups, and culture, which meant that the communication used images or graphics that could convey the message effectively and inclusively.

Communication strategies reach, content, and dissemination

Some countries reported changes in their communication strategies over time. One such change was related to the initial one-size-fits-all communication approach that was insufficient for addressing the diverse needs and preferences of the public. Some countries, like Austria and Italy used this approach in the beginning in order to reach the majority of the population fast. However, later the approach widened and included more languages. Some countries cooperated with civil society organizations or individual representatives of one group (Austria, Greece, Belgium, Sweden, Portugal, Wales) to reach out to different segments of the population, such as ethnic minorities or vulnerable groups. Another challenge was related to dealing with misinformation or disinformation that circulated online or offline. Some countries reported that they faced a difficulty in finding a balance between addressing these false or misleading claims without giving them too much attention or legitimacy. For example, in Wales the communication experts found it was challenging to select which points of misinformation to address as to better inform the public, without giving them too much importance and voice.

Another challenge was related to gauging the public opinion to find out what to address in news articles or campaigns. Some countries reported that this became very difficult in the absence of offline public debates or events. It was considered challenging to rely on online debates that were sometimes fuelled by extremist views or bots (Wales). Another change that was reported by some countries was related to the content of their communication. Some countries reported that in the beginning they mainly focused on providing information on the virus itself but later shifted their focus to include more information on the people affected by it, especially vulnerable groups (Wales). This was seen as a lesson learned from their previous communication strategy. Germany focused superficially on convincing the population that COVID-19 is not only a danger for the “at risk” groups but for the entire population.

Different countries chose a variety of modes to disseminate the official communication campaigns. Countries like Italy and Greece relied on establishing relations with international organizations. Almost all countries used community representatives and civil society organizations to reach and disseminate the information to different vulnerable and hard-to-reach groups. Countries like England also relied on influencers to reach a wider audience and convince more ages and segments of the population in the main messages.

4.4 Fighting Mal- and Disinformation

Fake news has been a major challenge for the public health sector, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. To counter the spread of misinformation and disinformation, various initiatives have been launched by in the ten countries.

One of these initiatives was a press release on "recognizing fake news" that was published in Germany. It emphasizes the importance of using official sources of information, instead of rumours and private sources. It also encourages the public to be critical and responsible consumers of information.

Another initiative is the establishment of units dedicated to combatting disinformation. For example, a "Monitoring Unit for countering the spread of fake news related to Covid-19 on the web and social networks" was established in Italy, Sweden, and England. The unit monitors and analyses the online discourse around Covid-19 and provides accurate and timely information to the public. Similarly, working with strategic communication experts to combat fake news was a key priority for the Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sports in England.

Some initiatives also involved establishing partnerships with media outlets, journals, and other stakeholders. For instance, in Portugal, there were collaborations with media outlets to produce and disseminate information on Covid-19 prevention measures and vaccination. A report on the impact of these collaborations was also written.

Another shared approach was to exclude or minimize the coverage of conspiracy theorists or anti-vaccination activists, in order not to give them a platform or legitimacy, and to not waste resources and time on covering them. This was done by some media outlets in different countries.

Social media campaigns were another common strategy to address fake news. Several media channels and radio shows in England tackled the issue of misinformation and disinformation in their programs. Some examples of social media campaigns are the translation of international documents into local languages (for example in Portuguese). Germany set up a transparency website 'Frag den Staat' (Ask the State), which allows the public to access official documents and data related to Covid-19.

Vaccination was a specific topic to tackle in relation to fake news and disinformation, especially in relation to the side effects and the efficiency. For example, in Greece, there was a campaign to inform the public about the benefits and safety of vaccination. In Germany, there was a proactive campaign to debunk misinformation on vaccinations. The campaign produced information materials on myths and facts about vaccinations in eight to ten languages. In Belgium, information campaigns emphasized the scientific research on which vaccination is based.

Scientific research and knowledge were a common principle that guided all these information initiatives against fake news. The information provided by these initiatives was either based on or verified by scientific research. For example, in Belgium and Portugal, there was an emphasis on communicating that the measures were based on scientific evidence. In Portugal, there was also a prior fact-checking of the published information by scientists. And in Sweden, information debunking myths was published in ten languages.

4.5 Addressing Vulnerable Groups

One of the challenges of crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic was how to reach and include various vulnerable groups in different countries. These groups faced different risks and barriers

to access information and services, and required tailored strategies to address their needs and concerns. In this section, we will summarize some of the approaches that were used by different media outlets and governments to communicate with and include vulnerable groups in the different countries analysed.

Most countries initially started their communication campaigns focusing on the mainstream population, aiming to reach as many people as possible with key messages. However, after a few months, the approach got more diversified and more inclusive. Seven out of the ten countries used key persons or influencers to target specific groups. This was done in Austria, Belgium, Greece, Sweden, Germany, England, and Wales. The key persons could be community leaders, celebrities, experts, or peers who had credibility and trust among the target groups. Coverage was adapted only in certain countries and by some media outlets.

Types of vulnerable groups acknowledged

Different countries have acknowledged and addressed various types of vulnerable groups in their communication strategies. The definition and identification of vulnerability changed over time as the pandemic evolved and new challenges emerged. Medically vulnerability expanded to a fuller idea of humanity, that acknowledges personal, social, historical vulnerabilities such as feelings or other intangible aspects of life. Nonetheless, only health vulnerabilities were officially acknowledged and received special rights and/or protection during the pandemic. Some of the common groups that have been recognized as vulnerable are:

- Migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, and ethnic minorities, who may face language barriers, discrimination, social exclusion, and lack of access to health care and social services. For example, Austria, Greece, Portugal, Germany, England, and Wales have all identified migrants as a vulnerable group.
- Care workers, seasonal workers, and low-income workers, who may be exposed to higher risks of infection due to their working conditions, lack of protective equipment, or inability to afford sick leave. For example, Austria has addressed the vulnerability of care workers and seasonal workers, while Germany and Wales have included low-income workers in their communication strategies.
- People experiencing homelessness (PEH), who may lack adequate shelter, sanitation, and health care, and may face stigma and marginalization from society. For example, Austria and Greece have both recognized PEH as a vulnerable group and addressed them specifically with separate communication approaches.
- Elderly people, who may have underlying health conditions, reduced mobility, or social isolation that make them more susceptible to severe outcomes from COVID-19. All ten countries in the list have acknowledged the vulnerability of elderly people.
- Young people, children, and students, who may experience disruptions in their education, mental health issues, or reduced opportunities for socialization and development due to the pandemic. For example, Italy, Greece, Portugal, Germany, England, and Wales have all addressed the vulnerability of young people.
- Women, especially those who are pregnant or in danger of domestic violence, who may face increased risks of physical or psychological harm due to the pandemic. For example, Italy, Greece, England, and Wales have all identified women as a vulnerable group.

- People with disabilities or special needs, who may have difficulties accessing information, health care, or social support due to the pandemic. For example, Italy, Greece, Belgium, Sweden, England, and Wales have all recognized people with disabilities or special needs as a vulnerable group.

Representation of vulnerable groups

The main approach used in most countries was to make vulnerable groups more visible by discussing their vulnerabilities publicly or prioritizing them in the communication campaigns. For example, in Wales, PEH were portrayed not as difficult but as vulnerable in need of a home. In Belgium, the key governmental message was to show solidarity with the most vulnerable of the population. In Greece, the national government communicated that they “will remain attentive to the needs of the most vulnerable populations in the face of the pandemic, among which are some Roma communities”. Another way of making vulnerable groups more visible was to include lifestyle or cultural diversity in campaigns or make them more personalized, as done in Germany.

Demonstrating solidarity with less privileged groups by reminding the privileged about their privilege was a common approach in some countries. For example, in Wales and Germany, some campaigns encouraged people to show solidarity with less privileged groups, such as those who had lost their jobs or income due to the pandemic, or those who had limited access to health care or social support.

Addressing vulnerable groups

As the pandemic evolved, government across the ten countries expressed their dedication to solidifying important COVID-19-related communications in a way that is reachable and inclusive. For example, Germany published a guideline was published by the government for how municipalities could address vulnerable groups. Along with financial and other aids for those who were economically affected by the pandemic. For example, in Germany, the government provided tax relief, raises in minimum wage, expanded financial support for small businesses and freelancers, etc. These aspects are discussed at length in D4.7. In addition to the material support, governments also set up digital learning platforms for students and helplines for women at risk of domestic violence, support lines for people suffering from depression, and special hotlines to provide information on the virus and the vaccines. These were not necessarily tailored to the special needs of the different categories of vulnerable groups.

A common approach in almost all countries was to use multi-language information campaigns or coverage to reach foreign language speakers or non-native speakers who might have difficulties understanding the official language or the technical terms related to the pandemic. This was done in many countries, such as Austria, Greece, Belgium, Sweden, Portugal, England, and Germany.

Another inclusive approach was to use sign-language in the communication campaigns or coverage to reach those with hearing impairments who might have difficulties accessing audio or verbal information. This was done in some countries, such as Austria, Greece, Belgium, England, and Germany.

Special attention was paid on also using simple language in the communication campaigns or coverage to reach those with low literacy levels or cognitive impairments who might have difficulties understanding complex or technical information. This was done in some countries, such as Belgium, Sweden, Wales, England, and Germany.

Another approach to reach vulnerable groups was to partner with civil society organizations (CSO) and local representatives who had direct contact and trust with the target groups. For example, marginalized groups in Wales were first addressed on the governmental level, then by more local teams which were also given more importance in decision-making and advice formation on what sort of measures would fit with these cultures of these marginalized groups. Similar approaches were adopted in Austria, England, and Germany.

Digital exclusion

While most of the information was shared through digital channels, all countries made efforts to ensure that official information is also shared in non-digital modes. Press conferences, daily in the beginning, were a source for media outlets to share key messages and pieces of information in printed media, public television and radio channels. This allowed digitally excluded people to be up-to-date. Printed leaflets, and other printed materials were distributed in key locations as to be accessible to people who might not have access to paid media channels, for example for homeless people, or for people of lower SES. Translated information in key languages of the main ethnic and language minorities, were also made available in most countries.

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Annex 1 D7.7 Standardised Questionnaire for Country Reports

3.1.1. Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

1. **How is your government/the public health system/the civil society ecosystem/the crisis communication structured?** *(Who are the main responsible institutions and actors for crisis communication)*
2. **How was the response in your country planned?** *(documents and plans for crisis communication already available before the pandemic)*

3.1.2. Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

3. **How was the crisis management implemented at the beginning of the pandemic?** *(What happened when the pandemic hit? How did the government/ people in charge/authorities responsible for crisis management or crisis communication react? What documents did they follow? Who held the responsibility?)*
4. **How did these (referring to question 1-2) change over time** *(2 points in time: 1.) COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures, 2.) Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022)*
5. **What changes in crisis response occurred and why?** *(We are looking for barriers, problems, structural change/change of responsibilities, occurrence of multiple crisis, positive developments, solutions that made measures obsolete, (lack of) support of measures, content with government. Focus on crisis communication and Indicate whether there were special measures to fighting mal-/dis-/misinformation. If this was not addressed or there is no information about it, please indicate this as well) (use secondary sources and Expert interviews)*
6. **Reflections on pandemic management/communication taking changes into consideration.** *(Good and bad practices and lessons learned about crisis communication, both from secondary sources and from expert interviews. When using expert interviews, please quote the position of the expert, keeping their anonymity)*
7. **How did the public react to the crisis management/communication and its changes?** *(Focus on how different forms of crisis communication were assessed, approved or disapproved and Include assessment of concrete public health information campaigns and the extent to which they contributed to behaviour change)*

3.1.3. Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

8. **What vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed by the government/the public health system/civil society organisations/in crisis communication in the beginning of the pandemic? How did this change over time (over T1 and T2), were there new vulnerable groups defined and acknowledged in the course of the pandemic?** *(Discuss specific vulnerable groups that were at risk of exclusion from mainstream communication channels and messages. What were the main barriers in reaching different categories of vulnerable people and were these barriers immediately acknowledged and addressed?)*

9. **How was the response in relation to vulnerable groups implemented at the beginning of the pandemic? How were vulnerable groups supported or included in communication? How did it change over time, especially if new vulnerable groups were acknowledged?** *(What were the concrete measures to overcome barriers to reach vulnerable groups? For example, did the government take into account from the beginning different vulnerable groups like ageing people with limited digital skills or access. How were different ethnic minorities and migrant population included? How were homeless people and other people with no internet or other medial channels access accounted for in communication measures? Was there a particular timeline in addressing these different vulnerable groups, comparing different moments in the pandemic?)*

ANNEX 2
WP7 country frames

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to in a country and communicate during a (health) crisis

Governance Systems (GS) – describes how crisis communication is structured and organized in relation to a (health) crisis

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis communication a country

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the health crisis communication and response

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. Here it describes measures taken to manage the communication during the health crisis (e.g. communication strategies, messages and content creation and distribution).

AUSTRIA

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Government-run websites
- Social media channels of government actors (e.g., chancellor) & ministries

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 90,4 % of the population has access to internet¹
- 31,3 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)

Commonly used sources of information in the Austrian population (information-seeking behaviour)

- Online: ORF News online (36 %), Kronen Zeitung online
- TV, radio & print: ORF (80 %, public broadcaster) Kronen Zeitung, Puls4, ServusTV
- Mainly online or via TV
- 40 % trust news overall²

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Baseline Outcomes (O)

Relevant country status/indicators (from WP2):

- Trust in government: 49 % or 50 % in the autumn of 2019³

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Crisis and Catastrophe Management (SKKM) located within the ministry of interior
- Ministry of Health (BMG)
- Responsibilities between the Federal Government and provincial Governments often unclear⁴

Which other actors are involved in crisis communication?

- Austrian Public Broadcaster (ORF)
- Unemployment Agency, Austrian Economic Chamber of Trade, lobby for workers and employees
- National Tourism Organisation, Austrian Integration Fund
- Austrian Civil Protection Association (ÖZSV, NGO but not only in the health sector)⁶

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- Disaster Relief Law (Katastrophenhilfegesetz)
- Epidemic Law (Epidemiegesetz)
- Austrian Epidemic Act
- Influenza Pandemic Plan (2006)

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Provincial governors are responsible for executing the regulations issued by the BMG
- SKKM supports federal states

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Office of General Director for Public Health was vacant since 2019
- Supreme Health Board lacked members since the end of 2019⁵
- Health Minister Rudolf Anschober

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)

Who are the recipients of communication?

- General public
- The elderly (National Influenza Pandemic Plan)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Press conferences; websites & dashboards; Corona Traffic Light (September 2020); Public consultation hour of health minister; Information campaigns & advertisements (e.g., "Schau auf mich, schau auf dich"); Hotlines; Social media and Hashtags (e.g., #StayAtHome, #schauaufdich); Health data provided by AGES; use of the health hotline (1450) and installation of new hotlines
- Later vaccination campaigns (e.g., "Österreich impft"), use of Hashtags (e.g., #GemeinsamGeimpft)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- rules of communication: preparation, speed, truth, certain aggressiveness, empathy, consistency, messages, language, availability, action, lookout
→ later on focus on facts to convince those not already vaccinated
- principles of government communication: openness, transparency, regularity, conveying trustworthiness and consistency, dialogue;

What strategies were applied to address vulnerable populations?

- Information is mainly available in German, however the Integration fund provides information in 17 languages, easy German and sign language
- Sign language at press conferences (since Autumn '20)
- ORF teletext for the elderly
- Since March '20 campaign against misinformation targeting people with a migration background

What was the content of the crisis communication?

- announcement of measures and the current situation (Press conferences, websites)
- overview of current situation (Corona traffic light)
- awareness raising (Campaigns, hashtags)

Which barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered?

- Language and cultural barriers
- Different information seeking behavior depending on group belonging

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- Trust in Government increased during the Covid-19 outbreak (59 % / 63 % Gallup World Pole, 2020) to then sink to 38 % in winter and increase again in Spring (45 %) (Statista)
→ Trust declined generally due to constant changes in personnel
- 45 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, 32 % stated their trust to have decreased (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
→ Austria has a general problem with trust in science (expert interview)
- migrants felt (at times) poorly informed about the vaccine and they miss easy to access information on internet channels they frequently visit

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication

- SKKM
- Corona Taskforce
- Federal Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection (BMSGPK) including the Ministry of Health
- Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)
- Vaccination service Vienna, public health insurance system, medical association
- NGOs (Austrian Red Cross, Caritas, Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund)
- Media (ORANGE 94.0 radio station, ORF as public broadcaster)
- Other associations (unemployment Agency, Austrian Economic Chamber of Trade, lobby for workers and employees)

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- The stepping down of chancellor Sebastian Kurz altered communication; the constant change of personnel influenced/changed the press conferences (e.g., scarce public appearances and overall less communication by Mückstein)

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Austrian Vaccination Strategy (Dec. '20)

Responsibility for crisis communication to vulnerable groups

- communication aimed at specific target groups was outsourced to public health stakeholders, social organisations, and the public sector (for example information specifically targeted at businesses, employees, sport clubs, migrants)
- Austrian Integration Fund, Integration House, AIDS house, CSO, Public sector

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- **Virological quartet** constituted of
- **chancellor** Sebastian Kurz (until October 2021, followed by Alexander Schallenberg until Dec. '21, then by Karl Nehammer)
- **vice-chancellor** Werner Kogler
- **health minister** Rudolf Anschober (until April '21)
- **interior minister** Karl Nehammer,
- other ministers joining occasionally

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)
- Corona task force, Corona Commission
- European Commission, European Medical Agency, WHO

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Elderly, children, non-native speakers/migrants, people living with health vulnerabilities, people living with disabilities

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures (Nov. '21)

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Collaboration with public health stakeholders (e.g., Vaccination Service Vienna) or NGOs (e.g., Red Cross) for vaccination campaigns (e.g., You+Me=Austria, #lassunsimpfen)
- New hotline run by AGES
- Working with community leaders and public health representatives to encourage those not yet vaccinated
- Reduction of press conferences, reduction of available hotlines (but new hotline by AGES).
- Reduction of information available on websites other than ministry of health, integration funds, ministry of education, and ministry of labour

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection (Sept 2022)

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur? How were strategies changed?

- New principles as in the Stocktaking and Framework for Action: no sarcasm, no false promises, use of deliberate untruths is admitted, no no-comment policy
- Vaccination campaigns focus on people who are uncertain (or in general willing), rather than trying to change attitudes towards the vaccines.

→ principles: honesty, understandability, transparency, speed

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

- Focus shifted towards motivating people to get vaccinated and/or the booster (#GemeinsamGeimpft)
- Focus on Long COVID.
- Shifting of the crisis management strategy towards 'living with corona' under Rauch

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Pandemic tiredness due to the complexity and long duration of the pandemic; controversial statements by experts and different estimations regarding the virus' danger; evolving nature of the scientific knowledge, leaving an impression of inconsistency; mis- and disinformation
- Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ) and MFG Austria – People Freedom Fundamental Rights (MFG) influenced the national COVID-19 communication and discourse through their anti-government and anti-vaccination rhetoric.
- there is a substantial lack of information on the COVID-19 vaccine and the vaccination programme for migrants; the campaign it shows a lack of inclusivity and diversity speaking only to a classically white Austrian audience and hereby ignoring migrant populations

Changes in how new/different vulnerable groups accounted for?

- Vaccination campaign focused on multilingualism, low-threshold access
- Target group specific education for foreign-language communities
- Focus on students being able to return to school; children and adolescents being allowed to get vaccinated

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 83,8 %¹
- Trust in Government decreased again during winter 2021 / 2022 (41,5 %), now (winter 2022 /2023) being at 49 %²
- Trust in science at 70 %³

→ However there is a lack of trust in government and science from those unwilling to get vaccinated

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Vaccination was made mandatory (Jan. '22)
→ Law was suspended in July '22 under the same government

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- The COVID-19 Pandemic – Stocktaking and Framework for Action ('22)

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups?

- none

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Federal government: chancellor Karl Nehammer, health minister Wolfgang Mückstein was replaced in March 2022 by Johannes Rauch, interior minister Karl Nehammer was replaced by Gerhard Karner in December 2021

Changes in the expert sources?

- Establishment of a new General Covid Crisis Coordination (GECKO since Dec. '21) onwards, focus on fighting Omicron (consultation of the government & operational support with the implementation of measures)

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Those resistant to get vaccinated
- Focus on children and adolescents with availability of vaccines for this group

Belgium

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Website of the NCCN crisiscenter.be
- Press conferences, national crisis websites (info-coronavirus.be), national media channels, print materials, posters, social media, general information number (free of charge), reports (Sciensano)

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 90,8 % have access to internet (Statista)
- 37,6 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Differs due to the two national languages
- Flemish: Eén (VRT) (public broadcaster), VTM (both 43-44 %), Het Laatste Nieuws online (51 %)
- French: RTL, La Une (RTBF) (public broadcaster) (both 46-48 %), RTL News online (37 %)
- Mostly via TV and online (incl. social media)
- 45 % trust in news overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, '20)

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Ministry of Health per language region, Ministry of Home Affairs, National Security Council, National Focal Point – Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences Risk Assessment Group – composed of representatives of the ministries of health, Risk Management Group – composed by permanent representatives from the health authorities and epidemiologists of Sciensano, National Crisis Centre (NCCN) – belonging to the Ministry of Home Affairs Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health); National Public Health Institute (Sciensano) – operating under the federal minister of Public Health and of Agriculture

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- General Emergency Plan ('03)¹
- National Pandemic Influenza Plan (WHO, '06)
- Advisory Report Regarding National Pandemic Influenza Plan ('09)
- Crisis Communication Guideline for local governments (by the NCCN, '07)
- Guidance on the use of social Media in Crisis Communication (by the NCCN, '13)

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Communication strategies are jointly coordinated between the FPS Public Health and NCCN
- Due to Belgium's political structure federal, regional, provincial and municipal leaders have their own responsibilities

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from WP2):

- Trust in government 35,5

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Minister of Security and Internal Affairs Pieter De Crem (succeeded by Annelies Verlinden in Oct. '20)

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Press conferences, national crisis websites (info-coronavirus.be), national media channels, print materials, posters, social media, general information number (free of charge), reports (Sciensano)
- Corona-Barometer (Jan. '21)

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- NCCN has a team of communication professionals who are in charge of monitoring public perception and opinions in times of crisis

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups:

- Local governments, The Combat Poverty, Insecurity and Social Exclusion Service (Mar 21), Wabliëft – Flemish Organization for clear language; Independent centre of expertise Gezond Leven (Healthy Living)
- Various non-profit organizations (e.g., Foyer, Gezondheit en Wetenschap)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures (Nov. '21)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Monitoring of public opinion and behavior
- Information dissemination was split up thematically between the federal government (regarding measures) and the NCCN (regarding infection data)
- Diversifying the number of communication channels
- Focus on raising awareness and information in the beginning, then understanding the new behaviors as part of a long-term lifestyle

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- NCCN collaborated with different organizations
- Implementation of non-digital communication, clear or simple language, translations, proactive initiatives, multilingual information
- Targeted information campaigns for vulnerable groups (e.g., youth with MAGDANOG?)
- Mobile app "Crisis Information Translated"
- Information for low-literacy and non-native speakers, young people (Watwat.be), ethnic-cultural minorities, elderly)

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioral advice, announcement of measures)

- Basic rules, updates, information on misinformation, hygiene concept, messages of solidarity and unity, vaccination encouragement

What barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Language and cultural barriers, sensory barriers (due to sight or hearing impairments), textual barriers

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- 49% trusted in science slightly or almost completely however 32% stated it to have decreased (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels sank to 30 % (2020)
- High level of perceived understanding of the measures

Governance Systems (GS)

Structure and responsibility for health crisis communication:

- National Crisis Center (NCCN), FPS Health, Social Debate & Communication Unit, Ministries of Health, creation of the Corona Commissioners Office (October '20). At the end of 2020 the Corona Commissariat transferred its coordination tasks back to the FPS Health and NCCN
- Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment; National Public Health Institute (Sciensano)
- Universities, regional governments, social services, ONG, community leaders, professional associations

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Belgium entered a federal phase, led by the NCCN in order to centralize information dissemination and communication.
- Regional governments could enact stronger measures but the communication on other administrative levels (e.g., Coordination and Crisis Centre of the Flemish Government) had to correspond to the federally determined message
- Information Unit coordinated communication on measures (jointly chaired by FPS Health and the NCCN) and establishing the office of a corona commissioner (Oct. 20)

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Many strategies were made, however not freely accessible for the public
- For vulnerable groups the project "the development and validation of strategies for multilingual and media accessible crisis communication" (ICC project) was launched by Sciensano (Feb 21)
- Vaccination Strategy (NCCN, '20)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Minister of Security and Internal Affairs Pieter de Crem (until Oct 20 succeeded by Annelies Verlinden)
- Social Debate and Communication Unit
- Coronavirus Commissioner Pedro Facon (elected in Oct 20 until April 22)
- Medical Specialists and Civil Servants

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Expert Strategy Exit Group (replaced by Celeval, then by the Expert Committee on Management Strategy (GEMS, in Dec. '20)
- Taskforce for vulnerable groups (est. Spring '20)
- WHO

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public,
- vulnerable groups such as Healthcare professionals, social workers, elderly, sub-Saharan communities, people with a low education or low socio-economic status, non-native speakers, youth, low-literate people

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Deactivation of the Corona-Barometer (Jan. until May '22)
- Termination of national press conferences by NCCN and Sciensano (March '22)
- End of news updates on the national coronavirus website (info-coronavirus.be)

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- Regarding the vaccination new principles were defined: clear and unambiguous messages, importance of accessible and easy to understand communication

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

- Focus on the booster and vaccination of those who weren't vaccinated yet
- More focus on social vulnerability

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Use of local community health workers to address barriers and gaps in vaccination

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- Vaccination strategy for 2022 emphasizes the importance of easy-language
- Tailored communication to specific vulnerable groups

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- End of the federal phase (March '22) and dissolution of the Corona Commissioner Office (April '22)
- Sovereignty over the coordination and communication regarding Covid-19 was transferred back to the regional authorities
- Power of the Corona Commissioner is transferred back to the FPS and NCCN (dissolution April 2022)

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Strategy Document About Testing, Isolation and Quarantine ('22)
- Evaluation of Testing Policy (EDC, '22)
- Thematic Report on Vaccination Coverage and Epidemiological Impact of the Vaccination Campaign (Sciensano, '21)
- Vaccination Strategy ('22)
- National Pandemic Preparedness Plan ('22)

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 90 % (Statista)
- Trust in the government levels 41 %

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Office of Corona Commissioner was dissolved in April '22

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General population
- Certain vulnerable groups such as patients at risk, elderly, young people and children, blind and deaf people, non-native speakers, low-literate people
- In regard to the vaccination strategy new vulnerable groups were identified or emphasized (non-native speakers, deaf or blind people, children and adolescents, patients at risk, the elderly, low-literate people)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
 T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
 T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

England

Model T0

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Letters ("stay at home"), television, traditional and social media, websites, illustrations, free COVID-19 app and other apps (Long Covid Recovery), campaign created for private instant messaging services, games (GoViral!), use of face-to-face interaction, paper formatting, short film
- Daily press conferences took place daily from (March 2020) until (June 2020). They would now only take place if something important needed to be communicated.

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- New resources available to certain vulnerable groups include text messaging tailored to those considered extremely vulnerable to COVID-19. NHS sent messages relating to why vulnerable people should self-isolate, every guidance such as how to access care and support while isolating, and wellbeing and emotional advice.
- Department of Health and Social Care (the main department responsible for government and legislation on safeguarding adults at risk)
- Cabinet Office Disability Unit
- New digital innovations included the following websites: Feebris, Neurolove.org, Peppy, Vinehealth, and Beam.

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- In the beginning communication was based on fear and danger, the focus shifted on uncertainty and self-care as well as safety, lastly on vaccination
- new "Build Back Better" strategy focused on strengthening trust in the health system
- Regular evaluation of the communication via national and UK-wide surveys

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- Rules and measures, minimizing the transmitting of the virus, information on Covid-19s spread and prevention
- Later on the vaccination, information on long-covid

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- Translation of information by Doctors of the World; British Red Cross provides a telephone hotline in more than 200 languages; Children's Charity Barnado created a helpline for ethnic family members, esp. children
- Organization Travelling Ahead provided information for Gypsy and Traveller Communities
- Social Care Wales provided information for elderly, care workers and takers, people with dementia or learning disabilities
- Easy to read information, use of large print, Braille and sign language

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Criticism of very vulnerable groups having been neglected
- UK population losing access to news due to the closing of independent media outlets

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- Youth first believed the government was handling Covid-19 well, fell from 72 % to 31 % in about a year
- Trust in the government levels sank to 34 % in the UK
- Inaccurate media reporting led to diminishing trust levels
- Inaccurate mass media reporting potentially damaging the public's trust in mainstream media
- Different responses across government caused confusion

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS)
- Government Communication Service (GCS)
- National Health Service (NHS)
- Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS)

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

No significant changes

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Joint statement between UK, CEPI and Industry Associations (March '22)
- UK Government Communication Plan 2021/2022 "Build Back Better"; COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing COVID-19 (UK, March '21)
- **2020 National Risk Register released**
- **Coronavirus Act 2020 implemented instead of CCA**

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- Outsourced to private or public organizations (e.g., Doctors of the World, British Red Cross, Travelling Ahead)
- Charities (e.g., British Heart Foundation, Children's Charity Barnado)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime Minister Boris Johnson
- Queen Elizabeth II
- Chief Medical Officers in England, Wales and UK
- British Health Secretary
- **Medical Officer Chris Whitty**
- **Former Home Secretary Priti Patel**

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (UK, SAGE)
- Cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit (March '20)

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Those with special medical conditions (chronic diseases), ethnic minorities, non-native speakers, youth and children, the elderly, Autism spectrum, Disabled, migrants

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- February 2022 press conference focused on "living with COVID-19." After this conference, no more took place.

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Ineffective messaging by ethnic minority Members of Parliament. Messaging was said to include "scepticism, complacency and mistrust by scientists and politicians compared to other local community members"

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- Communications and cross-government COVID-19 campaigns made sure to focus on encouraging vaccine uptake as the rollout expanded. This has included using efficient media channels.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit was decided to continue its work
- Election of a new prime minister in September and Oct. '22

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

New documents / guidelines / regulations on how to conduct crisis communication?

- Joint statement between UK, CEPI and Industry Associations (March '22)
- COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing COVID-19 (update July '22)

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- Building on relationships with influencers and local communities to reach ethnic minority groups with data about vaccines in multiple languages.

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 75.2 % (UK)¹
- Trust in science levels [73%]
- Trust in the government levels [41,5%]
- Trust in the media [34%]
- Communications were said to be low in honesty and credibility, and low in empathy. Communication also said to not be meeting community needs.

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Prime Minister Boris Johnson (until September '22, then shortly Liz Truss and since Oct. '22 Rishi Sunak)
- Queen Elizabeth II (until Sep. '22)

Changes in the expert sources?

- WHO .

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General population
- Pregnant women, people with learning disabilities or serious mental illnesses or other health conditions

Germany

Model T0

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What new means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Governmental press releases, informational websites (e.g., regarding fake news), media-savvy print and digital communication campaigns (e.g., hashtags #Ärmelhoch), infographics, policy documents, slogans (e.g., AHA), multilingual hotline
- Covid tracing and information app (Corona-Warn App)

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- Most critical information was available from the federal government in a wide range of languages; however, multilingual presentation of locally relevant information (such as changing regulations and recommendations) was highly dependent on the location
- National-level CSOs (such as Red Cross) and local-level CSOs (such as community centres, churches, etc.) helped disseminate governmental communications to vulnerable groups, but only rarely engaged in their own campaigns
- Increasingly: leveraging of multipliers within vulnerable populations (e.g., CSOs with longstanding relationships in certain communities; community leaders; role models like athletes and celebrities; etc.)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures (Nov. '21)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Principles of government communication: coordination, transparency, factual currency, understandability, reliability, selflessness, relevance to everyday lives
- Strategies applied: Use of humor and local idioms; Use of risk psychology and thereby focusing more on narrative descriptions than simply data and using shock messages, working with celebrities; appeals to emotion
- Umbrella campaign with several smaller campaigns
- Assessment of the communication effectiveness via national surveys (since July '21 also in other languages than German)
- Collaboration with different ministries, organizations, private companies, etc.

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- Information mainly in Germany, but multilingual and multicultural support was implemented, as well as easy German
- Use of testimonials representative of different social and cultural backgrounds for vaccination-advertising videos or famous influencers to target adolescents
- Use of multiple channels regarding different age groups for example (e.g. Die Sendung mit der Maus for children)
- Cooperation with "multipliers" with connections to vulnerable groups
- Working with NGOs in order to disseminate information to vulnerable groups
- FUNK (public broadcaster) addressed misinformation for adolescents and children

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- Measures and restrictions, basic rules, updates on the situation, information on misinformation, hygiene concept, messages of solidarity and unity
- Focus on shock and fear in the first wave, then resilience and vaccination in the next, as well as misinformation

What barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues,?)

- Language and cultural barriers (especially in regard to misinformation)
- Information overload and fatigue, misinformation
- Expert Committee of the Green Party criticized the governmental communication strategy (lack of clarity and consistency)

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.). According to the University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring Project, key figures as of 14.04.2020 (T1) were:

- Trust in health institutions (scale of 1 to 7): mean score 4.74
- Trust in federal government (scale of 1 to 7): mean score 4.42
- Frequency of mask wearing (frequency from 1 to 5): mean score 2.25
- Belief in conspiracy theories in general (scale of 1 to 7; mean of 5 items): mean score 4.23

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Federal Ministry of Health (BMG)
- Ministry of the Interior and for Home Affairs
- Federal Centre for Health Education (BZgA) – part of the Ministry of Health
- Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BKK) – executive agency of the Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community
- Media and communication agencies (public broadcasters, private media companies)
- Robert-Koch Institute (RKI) and Paul-Ehrlich Institute – both part of the Ministry of Health

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Changes in government due to the federal parliamentary election in Sep. '21
- Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?
- Several inquiries (Drucksache) were submitted to the federal government by MoP dealing with Covid-19 responses, health and risk communication
- Pandemic Influenza Plan (March '20)
- How We Will Bring COVID-19 Under Control (March '20 communiqué)
- Guideline Crisis Communication (Leitfaden Krisenkommunikation '14)

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- RKI published a general guidance for health officials to reach out to marginalized groups (July '21)
- Some NGOs also carried out campaigns, but mostly acted as disseminators (Federal Centre for Political Education, migrant advocacy organization ProAsyl, German Red Cross, Diakonie, Charité Berlin, etc.)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Ministry of Health, led by minister **Jens Spahn**
- Federal government, led by Chancellor Angela Merkel → Olaf Scholz
- State Secretary at the Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community Dr. Markus Kerber
- Prof. Lothar H. Wieler, Director of the RKI
- Increasingly: **Christian Drosten**, professor at the Charité

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Interdisciplinary group of external scientists
- RKI, PEI, Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research, Charité Institute of Virology
- Corona Expert Committee

Who are the recipients of communication?

- General public, different vulnerable groups
 - migrants, ethnic minorities, elderly, deaf, children & young people, medical personnel, persons living in poverty, migrants, refugees, homeless people
- Definition of vulnerability was continuously broadened, not only the elderly or those with severe diseases, but also those with physical, psychosocial, socio-economic vulnerabilities

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Corona-Warn App was put to rest mode as of June '23
- Overall decrease in the frequency of COVID-19-related communications, especially in the wake of the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

Changes in the level of digitization, education levels etc.

- On a population level, these indicators did not significantly shift.
- However, qualitative findings from the Mannheim case study suggest that local CSOs and other relevant actors notably increased their overall digital competence over the course of the pandemic.

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- The content of the crisis communication shifted to a primary focus on vaccination
- AHA-slogan was adjusted to AHA+L+A

What barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Criticism of lockdowns as having aggravated social vulnerability in unacceptable degrees, especially for children and youth.
- Criticism of nepotism regarding governmental stakeholders, as they contracted private communication agencies who had already worked with certain political parties (SPD)

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- More granular recommendations were issued for how to effectively communicate to and about a wider range of groups with non-health vulnerabilities: children, migration-background populations, etc.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Coronavirus Expert Council was established (Dec. '21)
 - Pandemic Working Group was established (PAIKO-AG, July '22)
- due to inconsistencies in the government and RKI communication regarding the vaccination
- Law on the Continuation of Regulations Concerning the Epidemic Situation of National Importance (submitted by June '22) makes a transparent evaluation of German Covid-19 communication planning obligatory

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Advice or statements by the governmental Coronavirus Expert Council (e.g., On the need for evidence-based risk and health communication, Jan. '22)
- Comprehensive policy evaluation report by a multidisciplinary Expert Committee (June '22)

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 85,4 % (Statista)
- Trust in science levels: 62 % (Wissenschaftsbarometer)
- Trust in the government fell further to 40 % in winter 2022 / 2023 (Statista)

According to the University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring Project, the deltas of key figures between 14.04.2020 (T1) and 29.11.2022 (T2) were:

- Trust in health institutions (scale of 1 to 7): mean score **4.74**, fell to **3.96**
- Trust in federal government (scale of 1 to 7): mean score **4.42**, fell to **3.28**
- Frequency of mask wearing (frequency from 1 to 5): mean score **2.25**, rose to **3.35**
- Belief in conspiracy theories in general (scale of 1 to 7; mean of 5 items): mean score **4.23**, fell to **3.99**

Actor Systems (A)

Fundamental roles and responsibilities in crisis communication did not change between T1 and T2. However, the election of a new government brought new individuals into these roles.

- Ministry of Health, led by minister Jens Spahn, followed by **Karl Lauterbach** (Dec. '21)
 - Federal government, led by Chancellor Olaf Scholz (since Dec. '21)
- Fundamental sources of scientific ground truth did not change between T1 and T2.
- Interdisciplinary group of external scientists
 - RKI, PEI
 - Standing Committee on Vaccination
 - Coronavirus Expert Council

Changes in the fundamental criteria by which vulnerable groups were identified and prioritised

- No change between T1 and T2. However, a wider range of groups were „officially“ recognised as vulnerable to impacts of the pandemic (including children and youth, socially vulnerable individuals and population groups, etc.).

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Greece

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Website of the GSCP – information is made available in different languages¹
- Campaigns, TV, radio spots, leaflets, brochures, electronic material, school visits.
- In all crises prior to COVID-19 governmental officials would conduct press releases and issue informational material via traditional and contemporary means, such as newspapers and official websites.

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 80,8 % have access to internet (Statista)
- Unfortunately there is a lack of a relevant research which may indicate the percentage of citizens who are technologically literate.
- 28,5 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Online: Newsbomb.gr (34 %), Dikaiologitika.gr, In.gr
- Print, radio or TV: SKAI news (55 %), ANT1 News, Alpha News
- Mainly online (92 %) or TV (71 %)
- 28 % trust in media overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Interaction Area (I)

Crisis communication on a nationwide, regional and local level, utilizing a top-down approach. Decision makers and policy shaping key figures would engage with regional and local points of authority, who would also base their communication with CSOs, the general public and vulnerable citizens, in accordance with the central government crisis communication modus operandi.

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from WP2):

- 23,5 % trust in government
- There are no indications that trust in government changed radically if at all during the first phase. According to a research of EKPA (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens), [48% of participants](#) indicate they trust the Government. Similar levels of trust are observed towards the Prime Minister and scientific community.

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Hellenic Ministry of Citizen Protection – General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP)
- Hellenic Ministry of Health
- National Public Health Organization (NPHO) – part of the Hellenic Ministry of Health
- Greek Centre for Disease Control (CDC) – public health organization (replaced by the National Public Health Organization in 2019)

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- National Civil Protection Plan (Xenocrates Plan (Ministerial Decision no. 1299/2003),
- National Influenza Pandemic Plan (2005, update 2009)

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Presidential parliamentary republic
→ Centralized government structure.
- Crisis communication was conducted via official channels, including traditional and contemporary means of communication in a variety of languages, tailored to the needs of several target groups (i.e. taking into consideration illiteracy, lack of digital skills, disabilities and challenges.)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- **Dr. Sotiris Tsiodras**, specializing in infectiology (infectious diseases), in charge of Greece's management of the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 crisis. Head of the Infection Experts Committee of the Ministry of Health.
- Prime Minister **Kyriakos Mitsotakis**
- Minister of Health **Vassilis Kikilias**
- Deputy Minister for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection **Nikos Hardalias**
- President of the NPHO Theoklis Zaoutis
- General Secretary of Civil Protection (GSCP)

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- EODY
- Government Committee is headed by the President of the Council of Economic Experts.

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public.
- People at a high risk of severe or fatal complications from an influenza infection.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Daily or weekly press conferences, websites, national media channels, billboards, social media, radio, implementation of a telephone line, TV spots, travel notices
- Similarly to the T0, during T1 the activities following were conducted as a part of crisis communication.
- Website of the GSCP – information continued to be made available in different languages
- Campaigns, TV, radio spots, leaflets, brochures, electronic material. School visits ceased during COVID-19.

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- During COVID-19, officials would conduct press releases and issue informational material via traditional and contemporary means, such as newspapers and official websites.
- A plethora of NGOs would cooperate with governmental organizations in crisis communication and/or would continue to conduct information awareness activities in relation to COVID-19 health protocols and regulations. Some of these NGOs are Diotima and Agkalia, among others. These NGOs would particularly emphasize in vulnerable groups such as single parent citizens, people living under the line of poverty, homeless citizens etc.
- It is highly likely that the governmental mechanism employed a communication group to address the communication requirements that particularities of COVID-19, due to the fact that tailored communication was conducted during this period and emphasized on both the general population and specific target groups such as people at high risk.

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Partnerships with international agencies, centralized communication strategy, use of slogans
- Several governmental agencies launched campaigns
- Realization of nationwide surveys

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- Translation of the COVID-19 guidelines into seven different languages
- Working with famous actors to convince the elderly of the vaccination
- Working with gynecologists to reach pregnant women
- Press briefings were also broadcast in sign language
- Collaboration with different ministries and working with representatives of those groups, famous people

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- First to create awareness, then spreading information and then combatting misinformation as well as getting vaccinated, the dangers of long-covid
- Measures and restrictions, basic rules, updates on the situation, information on misinformation, hygiene concept

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Misinformation, communication plan focused on the general population

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- 48 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, 30 % stated their trust to have increased (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels increased (35 %, also in regard to the management of the pandemic and as an official source of information.
- A [recent study](#) indicates that 57% of citizens would actively avoid being informed by the Media, thus, trust in Media has severely declined.
- Citizens would often criticize the frequency of information (daily briefs) which would negatively influence their psychological state due to the increasingly negative situation as well as the rapidly changing scientific information which would relate to the rules and regulations.

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- General Secretary of Civil Protection (GSCP)
- Hellenic Ministry of Health; Hellenic Ministry of Citizen Protection
- National Public Health Organization (NPHO)
- National Vaccination Committee (NCC)
- Universities (e.g., EKPA, AUth)
- NGOs (Prolepsis Institute, medecins sans frontières)
- Professional associations (Hellenic association of cardiologists)

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Appointment of a new minister of health

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- National COVID-19 Communication Strategy
- National Plan in addressing Influenza pandemic (2009)
- National Plan of Action for Public Health 2021 – 2025.
- Legislative Content Act, 42 / A / 25.02.2020, [Urgent measures to prevent and limit the spread of coronavirus.](#)
- All aforementioned sources indicate that crisis communication will be conducted by relevant expert, governmental authorities such as the Ministry of Health.

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- Outsourcing to national non-government organizations (Starvos Niarchos Foundation, Oloi mazi mporoume, PRAKSIS; Médecins Sans Frontières; Hellenic Society of Cardiology, Hellenic Society)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Head of the expert committee on infectious diseases, **Dr. Sotiris Tsiordas**
- Prime Minister **Kyriakos Mitsotakis**
- Minister of Health **Vassilis Kikilias** (replaced by Thanos Plevris on Aug. '21)
- Deputy Minister of Health Mina Gaga (since Aug. '21)
- President of the National Vaccination Committee
- Ministry of Health and the General Secretary of Primary Healthcare Marios Themistocleous
- Deputy Minister for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection Nikos Hardalias
- President of the NPHO Theoklis Zaoutis
- Minister of Education and Religious Affairs Niki Kerameus
- Deputy Minister of Labour and Social Affairs Dmna Michailidou
- Professor at the Medical School of NKUA Sotirios Tsiodras (until May '20)

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- IOM
- UNHCR
- National Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public, later on also tourists
- To the vaccination: pregnant women, adolescents, children, groups with strong religious interest, Roma communities,
- Refugees, migrants, asylum seekers, prisoners, single parents, low SES groups, the elderly, people with medical issues and caregivers

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- The frequency of communication methods and means would continue to persist. The emphasis would be altered and shifted from rules and regulations, and healthcare protocols towards the vaccination campaign. Contemporary means such as televised daily briefs would likely outweigh traditional means such as flyers in terms of frequency.

Changes in the level of digitization, education levels etc.

- No relevant widespread data is available in relation to the changes that were observed in relation to the Educational level, Digital skills & access of Greek citizens between the later pandemic phases such as T2. It is likely that the statistics would not differ vastly if at all between T0 and T2.

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- Governmental organisations would continue to cooperate under the established partnerships with NGOs in relation to COVID-19 information awareness activities and promoting the vaccination campaign, via all means and methods available, including traditional and contemporary means.
- There is no indication that the principles of communication were changed.

Changes in the content of the crisis communication were observed as crisis communicators emphasized in raising awareness in relation to the vaccination campaign.

- The main barriers that were encountered would continue to persist throughout all pandemic phases and these were mainly the digital divide and literacy than language issues.
- No relevant changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups were observed.

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.). The statistics during T1 and T2 would have similarities in relation to trust in government, science and media.

- Overall vaccination rate 82,6 % (Statista)
- 48 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, 30 % stated their trust to have increased (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels increased strongly (27%), also in regard to the management of the pandemic and as an official source of information.
- A [recent study](#) indicates that 57% of citizens would actively avoid being informed by the Media, thus, trust in Media has severely declined.
- Citizens would often criticize the frequency of information (daily briefs) which would negatively influence their psychological state due to the increasingly negative situation as well as the rapidly changing scientific information which would relate to the rules and regulations.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Reshuffling of the cabinet in the Greek Government

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Update to the COVID-19 Pandemic: Stocktaking and Framework for Action
- Overall, in relation to the vaccination strategy, vulnerable individuals would have priority over the general population.

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups:

- No relevant changes were observed. NGOs and GO, such as agkalia and Diotima would continue to engage with crisis communication in their own capacity and in partnership with other institutions.

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication?

- Head of the expert committee on infectious diseases, **Dr. Sotiris Tsiordas**.
- Prime Minister **Kyriakos Mitsotakis**
- Minister of Health **Thanos Plevris**.
- It is important to note that the frequency of daily briefs were significantly reduced during this phase.

Changes in the expert sources?

- No changes in expert sources were identified.
- WHO
- IOM
- UNHCR
- National Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- No changes to vulnerable groups were identified. All vulnerable groups (elderly, homeless citizens, substance abusers, children etc) were prioritised in receiving the vaccine before its administration to the general public.

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout

T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Italy

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)
 What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- National communication campaign "I don't take risks"³ for natural disasters
- Websites: authority websites and social media e.g.
- <https://www.governo.it/it/la-presidenza-del-consiglio-dei-ministri>
- <https://www.salute.gov.it/portale/home.html>
- <https://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/it/>

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 88,1 % have access to internet (Statista)
- 17,9 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)
- 49,8% of households of people aged 65 and plus (Istat, 2022)

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Online: TgCom24 online (24 %), Sky Tg24 online, Fanpage
- TV, radio & print: Rai TV News (44 %), Mediaset TV News, La7 TV News, TgCom24, Corriere della Sera, La Repubblica, Il Sole 24 Ore, Il Fatto Quotidiano
- Mainly online or via TV
- 29 % trust in media overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

Interaction Area (I)
 n/a

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
 - 27,5 % trust in government

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Prime Minister
- Council of Ministers
- National Civil Protection Service
- National Health Institute
- Italian Red Cross
- mayors¹

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- Emergency Plan for an Influenza Pandemic (2002, update 2006)
- National communication campaign "I don't take risks"² – for natural disasters

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Decentralized system based on three levels: state, region and local boards
 → Regional and municipality governments

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime Minister Giuseppe Conte
- → Who was the main actor communicating. Please emphasize this by making it bold and putting it in first place **depending on crisis**

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Technical and Scientific Committee
- Experts in government authorities, depending on crisis

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- The elderly

TIMEFRAME
 T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- TV spots, websites, social media, daily press conferences, traditional and new media, television and radio commercials, infographics, reports for experts of social health
 - PM Conte used interviews, social media and press conferences
 - PM Draghi did not use social media or interviews,
- Press conferences (Daily), websites, TV campaigns, media advertisement

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- Booklet *Practical Guide for Caregivers of the Elderly* realized by e ISS in collaboration with the National Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work (Inail) and the Center for Promotion and Development of Geriatric Care (Cepsag)
- Dedicated webpage of the Ministry of Health for frail old people
- Toll-free phone number for over 65 promoted by Senior Italia FederAnziani, WINDTRE and SIPEM SoS Federazione
- Toll-free phone number for reporting domestic violence. (Department of Equal opportunities)
- The Agency for Childhood and Adolescence (AGIA), has tailored the decalogue of rules to be followed by the general population to avoid the spread of the contagion with a language suitable for children, both in Italian and in English

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Working with sports or other TV personalities (Facciamolo per noi)
- Contes strategy was based on emotional and massive communication, Draghis on an informative and discreet style
- Later on a focus on science based facts in order to combat misinformation, being transparent

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- A practical guide for caregivers of the Elderly was issued in several languages by the ISS
- MoH offered a webpage on Covid-19 for especially the elderly
- Departement for Equal Opportunities launched a toll-free number for reporting domestic violence and an online campaign (#LibraPuo)
- Ministry of Education provided information fitted to the language of children and adolescents

What was the content of the crisis communication?

- Measures, trust in scientific community, creating awareness, information on the evolution of the pandemic,
- Later on focus vaccination campaigns (The Hugging Room, Vaccines in the Workplace – Unite for Safe Recovery, etc.); awareness campaigns on misinformation and fake news

Which barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered?

- STC only “did a general reference to fragility” in the beginning, leading to communication being unspecific for vulnerable groups making them more vulnerable to Covid-19

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- Almost 55 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, 30 % stated their trust to have increased (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels increased up to 29 %#
- Citizens experienced the communication as insufficient (regarding the first wave)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures (Nov. '21)

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Ministry of Health (MOH)
- Civil Protection Department – supervised by the prime minister
- regional and municipality governments
- National Institute of Health (ISS) – part of the Ministry of Health
- public health stakeholders, experts

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Declaration of the state of emergency
- Establishment of the Draghi government (Feb. '21)

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- National Health Plan in Response to a Possible COVID-19 Pandemic Emergency (WHEN?)
- National Strategic-Operational Plan for Pandemic Influenza, Preparedness and Response (PanFlu '21)
- Formal Communication Strategy (during the first wave, however not made explicit)
 - Prevention and Response to COVID-19: Evolving Strategy and Planning in the Transition Phase for the Autumn-Winter Period (second wave)
- Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups:
- Ministry of Health, ISS, Ministry of Education, Prime Minister, in cooperation with some CSOs or professional associations:
- Example: to prevent and report domestic violence a memorandum of understanding has been signed between the Minister for Equal Opportunities and the Family, Elena Bonetti, and the Federation of Pharmacists Orders, Federfarma and Assofarm.

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime-Minister Giuseppe Conte (until Feb. '21 then Mario Draghi)
- General of the Army Corps Francesco Paolo Figliuolo was appointed extraordinary commissioner for the Covid-19 emergency
- private companies
- Public and private broadcasters

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Scientific Technical Committee (STC, consisting of several ministries as well as the ISS)
- Task Force on Data Science and Online Disinformation

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public and specific vulnerable groups (the elderly, caregivers)
- due to the vaccination (elderly, health care workers, police, teachers)
- women, especially women at risk of domestic violence, children, teenagers, people with bodily or psychological conditions
- PanFlu: people with disabilities, homeless, lower socio-economic status, migrants and asylum seekers, those living in detention

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Decrease in the frequency of communication
- Fewer press conferences/end of the press conferences. Decreased attention in the media. Less frequency in data release (by the ISS)

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- End of the state of emergency in April 2022

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

- Promotion of the second booster especially for the vulnerable

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- No new barriers

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- No changes

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- 2022 general election and new government
- End of the state of emergency (April '22)

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- None

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups?

- No changes

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Resignation of Draghi led to the election of Giorgia Meloni (Oct. '22)
- extraordinary commissioner for the Covid-19 emergency (dissolved in March 2022)
- Vaccination Campaign Completion Unit was created in March '22 spearheaded by Army General Tommaso Petroni (until Dec, '22)

Changes in the expert sources?

- WHO
- Technical-Scientific Committee (dissolved in March 2022)
- Vaccination Campaign Completion Unit (March 2022 until Dec. 2022)

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General population
- Elderly
- Young people

Outcomes (O)

• Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 89,9 %
- Trust in the government levels 32%

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Portugal

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Website of ANEPC and YouTube channel¹, governmental platforms
- Government official (<https://www.portugal.gov.pt/>)
- President official (<https://www.presidencia.pt/>)
- website Instagram and Facebook of the government and ministries Television and radio and newspapers (government buys time on major channels)

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 81 % have access to internet (INE, 2019)
- 25,4 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)
- 50.6% of men have secondary education; and 58.9% of women.
- the early school leaving rate for men is 13.7% and for women it is 7.4%.
- -70% of the population having internet access in 2019, according to Eurostat data
- -More than 40% of Portuguese seniors do not use the internet (JN, 2020)
- no data were found on residents who do not speak the language but the High Commission for Migration (ACM) has provided, since the beginning of this century, a Telephone Translation Service (STT) in 69 languages, including Cape Verde and Guinea Bissau creoles

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Online: Notícias ao Minuto (30 %), Sapo, Correio da Manhã online
- TV, radio & print: Sic News (72 %), TVI News, RTP News (public broadcaster, 47 %)
- Mainly online and via TV
- 56 % trust in news overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from WP2):

- 52 % trust in government 44% (2019) Trust in science levels- Before the pandemic (T0), a survey found that 86% of Portuguese respondents had confidence in the scientific community (Eurobarometer, 2019)
- 34% of Portuguese respondents stated that they trusted their national government. (Source: European Parliament, Eurobarometer, 2019);
- 52 % trust in government (Gallup World Pole, 2018)

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- National overall authority
- President- Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa
- Prime Minister-António Costa
- Regional autonomy
- Local autonomy
- Government and Public Health Authorities:
- DGS (Directorate General of Health) -Graça Freitas
- SNS (National Health System)- Marta Temido
- ARS (Regional Health Authority)
- Portuguese National Authority for Emergency and Civil Protection (ANEPC) – part of the Ministry of Home Affairs
- National Civil Protection Commission – a body composed by representatives of all ministries and governmental entities with competences in civil protection
- The monarchy in Portugal is a symbolic institution. The President of the Republic, Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa, is known for his proximity to the people and his presence in difficult situations.
- The Portuguese Red Cross is an NGO that works in relief and emergency, psychosocial support and disaster preparedness. The Portuguese Red Cross plays an active role in responding to crises and disseminating relevant information during large-scale events.
- Mass Media: RTP, SIC and TVI are examples of television channels, newspapers and radio stations that play an active role in covering and communicating crises in Portugal. These media have teams specializing in emergency coverage and play a crucial role in disseminating up-to-date information to the public. Professional
- Associations: The Ordem dos Médicos (doctor's order) is a professional association that provides specific information and guidance in health crisis situations. The Bar Association is a professional association that plays a relevant role in crises related to legal issues. Order of Psychologists; P; National School of Public Health

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- National Pandemic Influenza Plan (2007)
- National Civil Protection System
- National Plan for Risk Prevention and Emergency Response (PNRPE).

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Semi-presidential democratic republic

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- President Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa
- Prime Minister António Costa

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- DGS
- SNS

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- News, press releases, video press conferences, official ministry websites, television, leaflets, brochures,
- The government reached out to the general public, mainly through press conferences and announcements, having also used its official websites, and having also created a "Stayaway" application (for locating infected people, which was heavily criticized for freedom and security issues)
- Channels were created, such as COVID-19: Somos ON, and the APP. Sites were updated on a weekly basis, producing weekly "red lines" reports
- COVID-19: Estamos ON" (COVID-19: We Are ON)
- Significant increase in the use of social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter to share information and awareness about the pandemic.

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups? unavailable to many people:

- employment contracts (and/or precariousness and labor rights);-financial capacity to manage the socio-economic crisis;- monitoring of chronic diseases and clinical follow-up;- mental health support; small houses with a household with many people-educational/digital/economic resources to support children in distance learning;
- It was made available:-two to three weeks after confinement, host schools were created for children who were unable to study at a distance (parents working; not having digital resources; children at risk, etc.)-temporary centers were created for the homeless

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout (until Nov. '21)

Interaction Area

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Following the strategies of the National Contingency Plan against Influenza: transparent and accurate information, cooperation, accountability, use of opinion leaders, simplicity yet effective
- Partnership of the DGS with the Journal O Polígrafo concerning misinformation
- Government favored the use of Twitter, DGS favored Facebook
- Administration, priority groups and generic approaches to the vaccine are therefore the dominant themes actively promoted by official sources on the digital channels they control.
- What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?
- Use of community representatives, multiple languages in order to inform vulnerable groups
- Public appearances of the prime minister in Infarmed were translated into sign language
- Targeted information for migrants and Roma people by the Health Unit in the Alentejo Region (e.g., by using representatives of the Roma community)
- Use of multiple languages (11 in total) and sign language by the DGS
- Website specifically designed for children by Ideias com História
- Doctors Without Borders (MSF) carried out, in the first half of 2021, a video with a view to preventing Covid-19, entitled "Nu ten ke previni (We have to prevent)" in Creole, African dialect

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioral advice, announcement of measures)

- Rules and legislation, vaccination campaigns,

What barriers for were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.) (vulnerable groups)?

- Misinformation, confusion, loss of trust in the government and politics
- Need to include behavioral science in the communication strategy; having the same protagonists communicating; In the beginning journalists criticized that the Prime Minister and President did not answer questions regarding Covid-19 sufficiently
- Group of scientists sent a letter to the government demanding behavioral science to be included in the management of the pandemic
- A lot of criticism was aimed at the fact that the government did not adapt the information campaign to certain (vulnerable) groups
- Difficulties for the elderly and low-literate people to understand information I)

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication

- 57 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, 43 % stated increased trust (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels increased 52% (2020)
- Director of the DFS became associated with politics and lost the confidence of the citizens
- Scientists write to the Government asking for access to data on covid-19:
- Government criticized for lack of crisis communication plan;
- The percentage of those who support a government of experts increased after the emergence of the pandemic by about ten percentage points, standing at 69% in 2021 (Monteiro & Jalali, 2022)

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Council of Ministers
- Minister of Health
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs
- Ministry of the Interior
- General Department of Health (DGS) – part of the Ministry of Health
- Working Conditions Authority
- Order of the Portuguese Psychologists (OPP), The Social Sciences Institute, The Human Sciences Faculty of Lisbon, the Portuguese Medical Associa

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Presidential election in Jan. '21 and local election in Sep. '21
- Changes regarding the governmental personas due to national, local and legislative elections in 2021

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Task force for the elaboration of a vaccination plan was implemented (April 2021)
- Guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception
- National Plan for Preparation and Response for Disease of the new Coronavirus
- Health Plan for Autumn-Winter 2020-21
- UNESCO document combatting misinformation

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups:

- Community initiatives (IPDJ, ANAFRE, Health Unit in the Alentejo Region)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime Minister António Costa
- **General Director of Health Graça Freitas** (disappeared after Feb. '21 in line with her new communication strategy)
- **Health Minister Marta Temido**, President Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa (re-elected on Jan. '21)
- Secretaries of State of Health, some governors

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Psychologists
- Communication support group for the vaccination task force

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Specific (vulnerable) groups (Roma communities, young people, healthcare workers, caregivers, medically high risk groups, the elderly (students, foreign citizens, people with disabilities, financially disadvantaged, migrants))
- low-paid workers (manual and service workers);

Changes in which vulnerable groups were accounted for/defined?

- the vulnerable are becoming even more disadvantaged and more vulnerable as is common in crises (Carmo at. Al., 2021)

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Barometro COVID, 2022
- Changes in the level of digitization, education levels etc.
- the level of education has increased, 58.8% (+0.8%) of men have secondary education, and 67% of women (+8%); the level of higher education also increased, men with 25.8% (+5%) and women with 36.7% (+6%); internet access (increased 5% from T0)
- The "Digital School" Programme, promoted by the Ministry of Education and managed by the General Secretariat for Education and Science (SGEC), with the aim of guaranteeing student access to computer equipment with an internet connection and digital teaching resources (computers were offered and hotspots to students). (2022)
- Proportion of individuals aged between 16 and 74 with basic digital skills, or above basic 51.8% 2019; having risen to 55.3% in 2021

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur? What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- between 50 and 80 different languages are spoken and used by students in Portuguese schools in context family, often associated with the use of Portuguese, and those with more presence are effectively the creole sayings of the Portuguese-speaking African Countries (PALOP), with emphasis on for the Cape Verdean language.
- there are no statistics on how many residents do not speak Portuguese
- Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?
- There were no changes in the strategies, only new factors of accumulation of inequalities were reflected (for example educational inequalities)

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Further changes to the governmental structure due to the Socialist Party winning national elections in 2021 (March '22)
- 20 % of the government will be cut
- Legislative elections in Jan. '22
- Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?
- New documents / guidelines / regulations on how to conduct crisis communication?
 1. Guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception) developed by the DGS and the Ministry of Health;
 2. National Plan of Preparation and Response for Disease of the New Coronavirus (COVID-19)].
 3. (Health Plan for the Autumn-Winter 2020-21).March 2021, Vice Admiral Gouveia e Melo was appointed the new coordinator of the COVID-19 Vaccination Plan

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- -*1 results have been contradictory = 80% reporting that they trusted the government to handle the crisis. (ISPUP, 2021) versus 53.6% of respondents reporting that they did not trust the government to handle the crisis (University of Coimbra, 2021)
- 42.2% of respondents reporting that they had a positive opinion of the government's handling of the crisis (University of Lisbon)
- Overall vaccination rate 94,2 % (Statista)
- Overall vaccination rate-85% (DGS, 2021)
- 92.57% of Portuguese people are already fully vaccinated against covid-19. (DGS. 2022)
- found that trust in the government had decreased since the start of the pandemic, with 53.6% of respondents reporting that they did not trust the government to handle the crisis. (University of Coimbra, 2021)
- January 2022 by the found that trust in the government had decreased slightly since the start of the pandemic, with 42.2% of respondents reporting that they had a positive opinion of the government's handling of the crisis. (University of Lisbon, 2022)
- What barriers, problems were encountered?
- A survey conducted by Aximage in March 2021, during the COVID-19 pandemic, found that 43.7% of Portuguese respondents trusted the government's measures to combat the pandemic. (Source: Aximage, "COVID-19: Perception and attitudes of the Portuguese," published on March 25, 2021)
- Trust in the government levels 38% (2021)

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Prime Minister António Costa
- Health Minister Marta Temido, President Marcelo Rebelo de Souca (re-elected on Jan. '21)
- Changes in the expert sources?
- Portuguese League Against Cancer (LPCC); Amnesty International Portugal; Doctors Without Borders (MSF); Ordem dos Médicos (Order of Doctors); Order of Lawyers
- WHO
- Task forces
- 1st task force for measures and vaccine, then behavioral scientists, government advice and for confinement/deconfinement phases (reports red lines)
- Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?
- The Minister of Health, Marta Temido, said that the government was concerned about controlling the impact of covid-19 on the most vulnerable, especially on the elderly, through the increase in infections and deaths that has been registered in July 2022.
- Extraordinary support for the most vulnerable families (GOV/Dec., 2022)
- General population
- Elderly
- Young people
- Changes in which vulnerable groups were accounted for/defined?
- In the second phase (T1 + T2), vulnerability was perceived taking into account a more biopsychosocial human view, and socioeconomic issues were taken into account (loneliness; poverty; low social capital; intersection of inequalities, etc.)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Spain

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Videos, posters, websites (www.proteccioncivil.org/), brochures, social media such as Twitter¹
- One daily press conference was held during the pandemic by the Director of the Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center of Spain.

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), residents who are not familiar with the language, etc.; Digital skills, education levels, etc.

- 36 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)
- 96% of the Spanish homes have internet access. Spanish Institute of Statistics (INE, 2021)
- 100% of the homes with dependent children have internet access. Spanish Institute of Statistics (INE, 2021)

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Online: El País online (23 %), El Mundo online, 20 Minutos online
- TV, radio & print: Antena 3 News (48 %), LaSexta News, TVE News (public broadcaster, 35 %)
- Mainly online (79 %) and via TV (63 %)
- 36 % trust in news overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
- 23 % trust in government

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Ministry of Health on National level
- Secretary of State for Communication (SECOM) – belonging to the office of the prime minister
- Ministry of the Interior – along with the Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE)
- National Crisis Centre (CCAES) – dependant on the Ministry of Health.
- Each Autonomous Community has the Health competencies transferred, and therefore they also manage the regional Health System, including communication. During the pandemic, however, this was taken over by the central government to unify the message.

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- National Influenza Plan (2005, update 2006)
- The National Civil Protection Strategy (2020) states that crisis communication and information is done by the Ministry of the Interior
- A Health Crisis Communication Plan as it didn't exist before the pandemic.

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Parliamentary monarchy with a decentralized state model

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- **Director of CCEAS Fernando Simón**
- Prime minister Pedro Sanchez
- Minister of Health Salvador Illa

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Ministry of Health
- Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center of Spain.

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- No specific vulnerable groups were specifically addressed.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Press conferences, webpages, mass media, website of the Ministry of Health, press releases, videos, social media, media spots, posters, banners
- No new communication channels other than twitter or other social media were established

What resources are (un-)available to certain vulnerable groups?

- No special campaign was addressed for vulnerable groups and all the population whatever the status should have gotten all the information, through NGO's or other means.
- All the information was provided only in Spanish, but vulnerable groups are almost totally integrated in an NGO or social services.

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Communication principles: continuous communication, seriousness, eliciting a sense of control and unity, factuality
- In the beginning the communication was reactive, eliciting a state of emergency, then it became more proactive and educational
- Strategy of limiting the media exposure of high-level decision makers, increasing the involvement of technical staff and middle managers
→ Decentralized and multi-layered constellation of spokespersons

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- No special campaign was designed for vulnerable groups.

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- Medical/public health information, political information, national security information, educational information
- Vaccination, recommendations, measures, emotional well-being, information and data on the pandemic

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Challenges due to the decentralized political system
- Contradictory messages or erroneous claims, campaigns from negationists, contradictory news from the different regions.
- Lack of infrastructure, slowness of information dissemination

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Prime Minister (= President)
- Secretariat of State for Communication
- National Crisis Centre (CCAES),
- Ministry of Health (yet rather insignificant), local governments of the autonomous regions
- Ministry of the Interior – along with the Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPE)
- Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS)
- NGOs (Spanish Red Cross, Social Services)

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- State of alarm was declared in March '20 until June '20 and again in Oct. '20
- State of emergency was declared in Oct. '20
→ Both were declared unconstitutional later on
- Communication was centralized

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- COVID-19 vaccination strategy in Spain. Guidelines ('20)

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups:

- Nor the government or any other organization was responsible; but social services did their part as the primary contact with vulnerable groups.

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

• After the first wave regional governments became the main actors in managing and communicating the pandemic

- **Director of the CCAES Fernando Simón**
- Minister of Health Salvador Illa (replaced by Carolina Darias in Jan. '21)
- President / Prime Minister of the Government Pedro Sánchez

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Center of Spain
- Coronavirus Technical Management Committee
- Experts and technicians from the Ministry of Health
- Advisory Committee for the COVID Vaccination Strategy
- Vaccination Technical Working Group (GTV)
- European Medicines Agency (EMA)
- Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Vulnerable groups were only defined in regard to the vaccination
→ the elderly, people with medical diseases, migrants, non-native speakers, those in irregular legal situations

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- 54 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, whereas 40 % stated increased trust (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Trust in the government levels increased to 25% (2020)
- Survey indicated that a majority approved of the governments strategies, also in term of communication
- Results also indicate a high compliance with the recommendations and measures
- Only Spain and US governments were not trusted by the citizens when it came to information provided during the pandemic. (Moreno A., Fuentes-Lara C., Navarro C. Covid-19 communication management in Spain: exploring the effect of information-seeking behavior and message reception in public's evaluation. Profesional de la Información. 2020;29:1-16)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout (Nov. '21)

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- Implementation of a free of charge hotline for suicidal people
- Press conferences to address the pandemic specifically ceased.

Changes in the level of digitization, education levels etc.

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- Shift to focus on the vaccination, reducing perceived risks and side effects

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

- Promotion of the second booster
 - Shift away from measures and risks, to the acute phase of the pandemic having been overcome
- Cumulative incidence of Covid-19 is no longer reported daily in the media

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- The barriers in the past continued to exist as they were not addressed.

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- There were no new campaigns for vulnerable groups.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- March 28th 2022 the government stops gathering data of infections in the general population, and gathers only infections of older than 60.
- End of the pandemic declared July 4th 2023.

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Crisis communication continued the same, with no new regulations or guidelines. Only the frequency of press conferences or the responsible of them changed, but no new plans were established.

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- None

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Minister of Health Carolina Darias was replaced by José Miñones (March '23)
- Miñones has had no relevance in Covid communication since his appointment.

Changes in the expert sources?

- No Newly established task forces, most of those established in T1 have been dissolved and others transformed. Back to the usual before the pandemic with some changes from lessons learned.

Changes in main target populations? Any vulnerable groups addressed

- No changes

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout

T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 85,9 % (Statista) 84,9% as of May 2023 (LaRazon)
- Trust in the government levels decreased to 21% (2021)

Sweden

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

- Website Krisinformation.se ('09) and Dinsäkerhet.se¹ and other social media
- Authorities' websites/social media accounts
- Printed leaflets and other material
- Billboard ads

Level of digitization (persons with access to internet), education level, etc.

- 98,8 % have access to internet (Statista)
- 38,3 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2020)
- Lower daily use of Internet among older citizens, (66-75, 93%, 76+, 69%) (Svenskarna och Internet 2019)

Common sources of information (information-seeking behaviour) (e.g., mass media)

- Online: Aftonbladet online (42 %), Expressen online, SVT News online
- TV, radio & print: SVT News (public television, 54 %), TV4 News, SR News
- Mainly online (84 %) and via TV (64 %)
- 38 % trust in news overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from WP2):

- 57 % trust in government (2019)

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication, even before COVID-19

- Ministry of Health and Social Affairs
- Swedish Civil Contingency Agency (SCCA)
- National Board of Health and Welfare (NBHW)
- Public Health Agency (PHA)
- Swedish Food Agency
- Swedish Board of Agriculture
- Regions and municipalities
- County Administrative Boards

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- Pandemic Influenza Plan (2005, update 2019)
- Communication Policy ('12, followed by the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs, Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs)
- Guide on Communication in the Event of a Pandemic (PHA)
- Relies heavily on autonomous government agencies

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime Minister Stefan Löfven
- Representatives from responsible authorities

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- ECDC
- Experts in government authorities, depending on crisis

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Medically vulnerable groups

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Press conferences, interviews, social media, telephone services, digital / traditional billboards, Kirsinformation.se and other governmental websites, new media, postcards, vaccine podcast, interviews in media, SMS, telephone services
- PHA provided information material to health organizations, adjusted to regional settings
- Information material in many foreign languages as well as sign language and easy-Swedish

What resources are available to certain vulnerable groups?

- Websites for non-Swedish speaking groups
- Graphic icons
- Interpersonal communication - vaccine interpreters in migrant dense areas

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout (until Nov. '21)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- Different entities were responsible for different information (SCCA disseminated information on the pandemic, misinformation, PHA disseminated information on the vaccination, NBHW information on vaccination for health care professionals)
- Principles of communication: information must be accurate, clear, prompt, reliable, respectful

What strategies were applied to address vulnerable populations?

- Identifying target groups, adapting language, imagery, graphic design, information channels, vaccination campaigns were both factually as well as emotionally based, in general evidence-based information, information material in public places (for travellers)
- Employment of young health and vaccinations guides in order to increase vaccination motivation in areas mainly populated by vulnerable people
- Multilingual support (Covid-19 information made available in 29 languages), information in easy-Swedish, all textual information is also available as sound clips
- Social media was used to reach the younger population

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- Government information, testing, national preparedness, current situation, education on how to prevent Covid, vaccination, recommendations, risks and threats, evaluation of crisis management, raising awareness, providing reassurance
- Personal responsibility and morality (logos-oriented rhetoric)

What barriers for vulnerable groups were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Language and cultural as information was insufficient for non-native speakers, especially regarding the vaccination

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- 52 % trusted in science slightly or almost completely, whereas most stated their trust level to have stayed similar (March 2021, Eurofond, 2020)
- Increase of trust in the government levels (62 % in 2020)
- high trust in the PHA and public television or radio, people felt well informed, trust increased during the pandemic
- Swedes found themselves well informed, press conferences were considered a success despite being 'old-fashioned'
- The Corona Commission criticized the handle and organization of elderly care
- Political opposition requested more and stronger supportive measures and more restrictions

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Ministry of Health and Social Affairs
- National Board of Health and Welfare (NBHW)
- Public Health Agency (PHA)
- Swedish Civil Contingency Agency (SCCA)
- Swedish Medical Products Agency (SMPA)
- Regions and municipalities

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Passing of the Pandemic Act (Jan '21) that changes the prerequisites for managing the pandemic
- Reorganization of the management of the pandemic by prime minister Andersson#

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- National Vaccination Plan (PHA, Dec. 2020)
- Development of a separate communication plan for vulnerable groups (by the PHA)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Royal family (especially King Carl Gustav)
- National board of Health and Welfare, government offices, Prime Minister Stefan Löfven (until Nov. '21, replaced by Magdalena Andersson)
- Minister of Finance occasionally
- Minister of Health and Social Affairs
- Minister of Finance, Minister of Foreign Affairs
- Johan Carlsson director of the PHA (resigned in Nov. '21, replaced by Karin Tegmark Wisell)
- State epidemiologist **Anders Tegnell**
- National and regional authorities regarding vaccination campaigns
- Regional infection control doctors

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- ECDC
- The Corona Commission
- PHA

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Specific (vulnerable) groups (non-native speakers, people with special needs or in special circumstances such as pregnancy, mentally ill, ethnic minorities, disabled, elderly)
- Vacation travellers

Model T2

Wales

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources are available for crisis communication in the country and how are they used by different actors?

From the Civil Contingencies Act 2004 (updated until 2012):

- Wales Resilience Forum organising communications throughout institutions, general public and the UK government, and cascading to Local Resilience Forums
- Press conferences, communication with all media, especially local radio and tv for simple and important messages, and written media for complex information
- Structure of priority from survivors, their significant others, local people and the public at large
- BBC's local radio service is recognised as an emergency broadcaster for the UK; in particular: BBC's 'Connecting in a Crisis' framework

Level of digitization, residents who are not familiar with the language, etc.

- 91,5 % have access to internet (UK, Statista)
- 40,6 % have a tertiary education (Eurostat, 2019)
- 96,7 % speak Welsh or English natively 22 % of those non-native speakers stated not being able to speak English well or at all¹
- 'Essential digital skills' level: 67%, ability to use the internet: 73% (businessnewsWales.com 10/6/20)

Common sources of information (for UK)

- Online: BBC News online (45 %), Guardian online, MailOnline
- TV, radio & print: BBC News (56 %), ITV News, Sky News
- Mainly online (77 %) and via TV (55 %)
- 28 % trust in news overall (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2020)

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from WP2):

- 20% trust in the government in the UK

Governance Systems (GS)

Who is responsible for (health) crisis communication?

- Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS)
- Government Communication Service
- National Health Service (NHS, public health care system in the UK)
- The Health and Social Services Directorate
- Wales Resilience Forum

What crisis communication plans already existed?

- Contingency Planning for a Possible Influenza Pandemic ('06)
- Preparing for Pandemic Influenza. Guide for Local Planners ('07, update '13)
- National Framework to protect public from spread of virus, severe illness and deaths (2007); Wales Framework for Managing Major Infectious Disease Emergencies ('14)
- Emergency Planning Framework (UK), Emergency Response Plan (Wales, '16)
- Strategy to assess impact, scale and mobilize response to mitigate effects of pandemic (2011), UK Pandemic Influenza Communications Strategy ('12)
- National Security Strategy and Strategic Defence and Security Review ('15 – '19)

What are processes / rules / regulations within the crisis communication?

- Department of health (DH) informs the Cabinet office¹
- In case of a prolonged event the NCC will be alerted as well, briefings will be developed by the DH
- Chief medical officers are responsible for the communication to the public
- There will be tailored communication to vulnerable groups

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Queen Elizabeth II
- Chief Medical Officers in England, Wales and UK
- Prime Minister Boris Johnson (before 2019 Theresa May)

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Joint Emergency Service Group (agglomeration of all emergency services in Wales, the UK armed forces and others)
- Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE)

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Vulnerable people (non-native speakers, blind or deaf, people with disabilities, foreign nationals, asylum seekers, refugees)¹

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic (until Jan. '20)

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What (new) means of communication & communication channels were established?

- Letters ("stay at home"), television, traditional and social media, websites, illustrations, free COVID-19 app and other apps (Long Covid Recovery), campaign created for private instant messaging services, games (GoViral!), use of face-to-face interaction, paper formatting, short film
- Wales Resilience Forum and Local Resilience Forums, all press releases via the BBC, all media used and written media for more complex messages all used as planned for.
- Social media had much more importance than expected in 2012 and the potential for miscommunication and fake news underestimated.
- All media used throughout the pandemic: radio remained very important, given its more accessible use potential.

What resources are available to certain vulnerable groups?

- Until Autumn 2020, the Welsh government and NHS Wales websites did not have easy-read, many translations versions for official information.
 - Websites of organisations that represent a particular vulnerable group (e.g. people with learning disabilities)
 - Social media: Many Facebook pages that are specifically targeted at a particular (small) group, small local area, or membership of an organization (e.g. for Gypsy Travellers in Pembrokeshire)
 - Telephone helplines, websites, leaflets
- <https://111.wales.nhs.uk/>
<https://www.gov.wales/coronavirus>
<https://www.swansea.gov.uk/coronavirusadvice?lang=en> (doesn't exist anymore)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout (until Nov. '21)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the crisis communication implemented when the pandemic hit?

- In the beginning communication was based on fear and danger, the focus shifted on uncertainty and self-care as well as safety, lastly on vaccination
- Use of "we" and "us" in order to signify unity
- new "Build Back Better" strategy focused on strengthening trust in the health system
- Regular evaluation of the communication via national and UK-wide surveys

What was the content of the crisis communication? (e.g., behavioural advice, announcement of measures)

- Rules and measures, minimizing the transmitting of the virus, information on Covid-19s spread and prevention
- Later on the vaccination, information on long-covid

What strategies were applied (to address vulnerable populations)?

- Translation of information by Doctors of the World; British Red Cross provides a telephone hotline in more than 200 languages; Children's Charity Barnado created a helpline for ethnic family members, esp. children
- Organization Travelling Ahead provided information for Gypsy and Traveller Communities
- Social Care Wales provided information for elderly, care workers and takers, people with dementia or learning disabilities
- Easy to read information, use of large print, Braille and sign language

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Criticism of very vulnerable groups having been neglected
- UK population losing access to news due to the closing of independent media outlets

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, protests, etc.)

- Youth first believed the government was handling Covid-19 well, fell from 72 % to 31 % in about a year
- Trust in the government levels was 34 % in the UK 2020
- Trust in media (dashboard)
- Inaccurate mass media reporting potentially damaging the public's trust in mainstream media
- Different responses across government caused confusion
- The most vocal and new group that has the strongest criticism of the Welsh pandemic response is the Welsh chapter of the 'Covid-19 Bereaved Families for Justice'. They have been pushing for a Wales-specific covid inquiry.

Governance Systems (GS)

Responsibility for crisis communication:

- Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS)
- Government Communication Service
- National Health Service (NHS)
- Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS)
- Wales Resilience Forum
- The Health and Social Services Directorate
- Public Health Wales
- Local Resilience Forums
- Technical Advisory Committee (TAC) and Technical Advisory Group (TAG) and their subcommittees.

Changes in government structure / responsibility for crisis communication?

- Wales had the power to manage the pandemic independently
- Wales faced general elections in May '21
→ Did not impact the communication greatly

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- UK Government Communication Plan 2021/2022 "Build Back Better"
- COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing COVID-19 (UK, March '21)
- Leading Wales out of the Coronavirus Pandemic: A Framework for Recovery ('20)
- Coronavirus Control Plan (March '21 updated in July and Oct.)
- Evaluation of testing and tracing (March '21)
- Evaluation of COVID-19 vaccination auditor (June '21)

Responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups

- Outsourced to private or public organizations (e.g., Doctors of the World, British Red Cross, Travelling Ahead)
- Charities (e.g., British Heart Foundation, Children's Charity Barnado)

Actor Systems (A)

Who is responsible for / involved in crisis communication?

- Prime Minister Boris Johnson
- Queen Elizabeth II
- Chief Medical Officers in England, Wales and UK
- British Health Secretary
- Welsh Minister of Health Vaughn Gething was replaced by Eluned Morgan (May '21)

Who/what were the expert sources?

- WHO
- Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (UK, SAGE)
- Cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit (March '20)
- Technical Advisory Group (Wales)

Who are the recipients of communication? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General public
- Those with special medical conditions (chronic diseases), ethnic minorities, non-native speakers, youth and children, the elderly, Autism spectrum, Disabled, migrants
- Changes in which vulnerable groups were accounted for/defined?

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in the means and use of communication & communication channels?

- All media used throughout the pandemic: radio remained very important, given its more accessible use potential.
- Press conferences became less in 2021 and 2022 and only took place with new announcements on an ad hoc basis (e.g. with travel restriction updates). Were certain means of communication (press conferences) used less frequently? Did they fade out, were new ones established? List them with a time frame of when they were used
- "How are you doing campaign" with a focus on self-care and resources

Changes in the level of digitization, education levels etc.

- Educational level: (see comments below for explanation:) Census 2021: Out of a total of 2.6 million usual residents aged 16 and over in Wales, 807,000 (31.5%) reported that their highest qualification was at level 4 or above. 19.9% (510,000) had no qualifications. 17.2% (441,000) reported that their highest qualification was at level 3, 14.4% (367,000) had a highest qualification at level 2 and 8.7% (223,000) had a highest qualification at level 1.
- Digital skills & access rose during the pandemic in Wales; the 'Essential digital skills' level rose to 77%, (Welsh Government 2022)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 beginning/first lockdown until vaccination rollout
T2: Omicron until now / until end of data collection

Interaction Area (I)

What changes in response implementation did occur?

- Measures were lifted because of the much lower chance people would be hospitalized or die from infection with Omicron variants
- Far fewer messages from the government and health institutions, with less focus on covid in the media (taken over by the Ukraine war)

Changes in the content of the crisis communication (e.g., vaccination)

- focus on living with the virus and returning to pre-pandemic normality
- Focus on living with the virus; accepting it will remain part of people's world
- Messages more aimed at vulnerable populations instead the public as a whole.

What barriers were encountered? (e.g., digital divide, language issues, etc.)?

- Some barriers lifted; easy-read versions and many translations were made available. Digital skills courses were offered earlier on already in the pandemic and this upskilling has paid off

Changes in the strategies accounting for vulnerable groups?

- Message character changed from insistent 'you must stay home/shield, etc' to 'it's safe if you do, but it's your choice', so the authoritative tone diminished.

Outcomes (O)

Outcome of crisis communication (e.g., increase or decrease in public trust, behaviour change, levels of understanding, etc.)

- Overall vaccination rate 75.2 % (UK)¹
- Trust in science levels, government levels [please give information], and the media is high in Wales according to the 'State of the State 2021-22' report.
- Criticism of the Welsh Government's crisis communication has culminated into a cross-party Sennedd-led committee that will review the Welsh Government's pandemic response.
- Trust in government of the UK 41.5% in 2021

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure & responsibilities for crisis communication?

- Cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit was decided to continue its work
- Wales faced local election in May '22
→ Did not impact the communication greatly

Changes to crisis communication / preparedness plans?

- Joint statement between UK, CEPI and Industry Associations (March 2022)
- COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing COVID-19 (update July '22)
- Government response to the COVID-19 Committee's Living in a COVID world: A long-term approach to resilience and wellbeing report; Coronavirus Control Plan (updated Sep. '22)
- Living safely with COVID19 in Wales: risk communication and behavioural science perspectives (March '22)
- Communicable Disease Outbreak (July '22)

Changes in responsibility to communicate with (specific) vulnerable groups?

- It was more personalised; GPs took over the guidance role for their patients from Public Health Wales and the Welsh Government.

Actor Systems (A)

Changes in the responsibility of persons involved in crisis communication

- Prime Minister Boris Johnson (until July '22)
- Queen Elizabeth II (until Sep. '22)
- Jean White (until August '20): Chief Nursing Officer

Changes in the expert sources?

- WHO
- Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic Advisory Group that advised on the adverse health effects of COVID-19 has not published since 16/12/21
- The Technical Advisory Cell still publishes statistics and advice on Covid-19

Changes in main target populations? Were any vulnerable groups addressed?

- General population
- Pregnant women, people with learning disabilities or serious mental illnesses or other health conditions